

I-CISK
HUMAN CENTRED CLIMATE SERVICES

Deliverable D5.5

Business model storylines for sustainable CS exploitation in the Living Labs

June 2025

Innovating Climate services through Integrating Scientific and local Knowledge

Deliverable Title:	Business model storylines for sustainable CS exploitation in the Living Labs
Author(s):	Alexandros Ziogas, Apostolos Tzimas
Contributing Authors(s):	Schalk Jan van Anandel, Annelies Broekman, Paolo Mazzoli, Györgyi Bela, Charles Wamucii, Aristeia Balamatsia, Vakho Chitishvili, Daniele Castellana
Date	June 2025
Suggested citation:	Ziogas A., Tzimas A., van Anandel Schalk Jan et al., 2025: Business model storylines for sustainable CS exploitation in the Living Labs, I-CISK Deliverable 5.5, Available online at www.icisk.eu/resources
Availability:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU: This report is public <input type="checkbox"/> CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document Revisions:

Author	Revision	Date
Alexandros Ziogas, Apostolos Tzimas	First draft	16 April 2025
Micha Werner and Paolo Mazzoli	Revisions	April 2025
Micha Werner	Revisions	May 2025
Alexandros Ziogas, Apostolos Tzimas	Final version	6/6/2025

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Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
AEMET	State Meteorological Agency of the Spanish Government
ARPAE	Regional Agency for Prevention, Environment and Energy of Emilia-Romagna, Italy
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
CC	Climate Change
CCA	Climate Change Adaption
CDS	Copernicus Climate Data Store
CEMS	Copernicus Emergency Management Service
CHIRPS	Climate Hazards Group InfraRed Precipitation with Station data quasi-global dataset
CLMS	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CS	Climate Service
DMA	Disaster management agency
DRR	Disaster Risk Reduction
DX.X	I-CISK deliverable (X.X refers to deliverable number)
EAP	Early action protocol
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-range Weather Forecasts
EO	Earth Observation
EU	European Union
EWS	Early Warning System
FAO	United Nations Food and Agriculture Organisation
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GDHY	Global Dataset of Historical Yields
GEOS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
GloFAS	CEMS Global Flood Awareness System
ITA LL	The Italian Living Lab - Emilia-Romagna Living Lab
KNMI	Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute
LL	Living Lab
LRCS	Lesotho Red Cross Society
MAP	Multi actor platform
MSX	I-CISK Milestone (X refers to milestone number)
NCCC	National climate change committee
NDVI	Normalised Difference Vegetation Index
NEA	National Environment Agency of Georgia
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NUST	Namibia University of Science and Technology
OAK	Organization for the Development of Crete (OAK in Greek)
OKIR	Hungarian National Environmental Information System
PET	Potential Evapotranspiration
PER	Preparedness for effective response
PERT	Program Evaluation Review Technique (diagram/chart)
REDIAM	The Environmental Information Network of Andalusia, Spain
S2S	Subseasonal to Seasonal
SEECOF	Southeastern Europe Climate Outlook Forum
SMHI	Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute
TAMSAT	Tropical Applications of Meteorology using SATellite data and ground-based observations
TX.X	I-CISK Task (X.X refers to work package and task number)
UHI	Urban heat islands
UN	United Nations

Acronym	Definition
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation
VOI	Value of Information
WFP	World Food Programme
WPX	I-CISK Work Package (X refers to work package number)

Summary

This report, part of Work Package 5 of the I-CISK project, presents the analysis undertaken for the drafting of business model storylines for the sustainable exploitation of Climate Services (CS) developed within the seven Living Labs (LLs) established under the I-CISK project.

The methodology applied builds on a tiered analytical framework, emphasizing a bottom-up approach that starts from specific use cases and expands to potential broader market applications. The analysis comprises four (4) iterative steps:

1. Define the boundaries of analysis for the use case;
2. Understand the value chain of forecasting services and identify the socio-economic and environmental benefits associated with the services;
3. Quantify and monetize the value (wherever possible) of benefits identified

And then

4. Extend the analysis to a broader market

The core of the analysis focuses on the Value of Information (VoI), evaluating economic, social, and environmental benefits derived from improved climatic data and forecasting capabilities. When monetizing the benefits was not possible due to restrictions (data availability, maturity of CS etc), a semi-quantitative scaling method has been used to highlight the relative importance of each dimension (e.g., LOW to EXCEPTIONAL).

Each of the steps of the tiered approach provides a user story (business story) of the CS, which gradually builds up in detail and extent of analysis. There are services with strong social/environmental or gains other than economic (e.g. reputational). This tiered approach allows for the assessment of a storyline for every CS, independent of factors which may confine the extent of analysis such as the type of value and the beneficiaries that are associated with the CS. This offers the desired flexibility because not all of the CS developed can or need to reach the final tier of the analysis.

The CSs developed under I-CISK offer high societal and environmental value, while economic viability varies depending on the context. Institutional integration, public sector adoption, and cross-sector collaboration are key to long-term sustainability. A full commercial market analysis is not recommended for every CS, especially where primary value lies in public good and resilience building.

1 Introduction

This report describes the work undertaken for the drafting of the business model storylines which will support the sustainable Climate Services (CSs) exploitation co-developed within the LL. The work has been undertaken in the frame of the 5th Work Package of the project (Climate Service Implementation and Business Development), under Task 5.5 which focuses on establishing sustainable business model for human-centred climate services, as a function of the value-proposition of the climate services and commensurate with the institutional mandates, governance structures, data availability, human and technological capacities. A focus has been given on the downstream value chain generated when transitioning from upstream climate services—centred on data provision and modelling—to downstream human-centred services embedded in decision-making processes. A four-tiered framework has been applied and a bottom-up approach has been followed for the three first tiers towards more detailed business model storylines, based on the end-user support within the LLs.

It is important to highlight that the notion of a “business model” within I-CISK reflects a spectrum of exploitation pathways. For some CSs, particularly in contexts such as Spain, Hungary, Georgia, and Lesotho, this does not necessarily imply commercial exploitation. Instead, these models focus on public value creation, institutional integration, and co-production with end-users. This broader perspective aligns with previous Horizon 2020 projects such as MARCO, EUMACS, and CLARA, which demonstrated that Climate Services can achieve sustainability through policy adoption, institutional embedding, or the use of open data frameworks, even without direct commercial transactions.

2 Theoretical background

The key components identified in most of the Business Model frameworks include the Value Model (opportunity, problem to be solved, value propositions), the Technological Model (R&D management), the Distribution Model (sales and marketing organizational structure), and the Financial Model (revenue modelling, cost structure, profitability and cash generation/management) as presented in Figure 1.

In the present analysis we focus on the Value Model, and more specifically on:

- The targeted problems the proposed Climate Services (CSs) aim to solve
- The targeted users of the developed CSs
- The current practices in place and the need for having an advanced solution to address these problems
- The proposed CSs and the advantages of I-CISK proposition compared to existing CSs
- The benefits from adopting I-CISK Services compared to current practices

Figure 1: Business Model components

2.1 Defining the I-CISK services value model

The value that new or improved climatic data and information can convey to End-Users, although recognized, is not directly evident. Several studies have suggested frameworks for conceptualizing the economic Value of Information (VOI) from earth science data (including decision making using meteorological and hydrological forecasts and climatic services). The approach followed here to assess the value of I-CISK Climatic Services in the seven Living Labs (LL) addresses VOI as a measure of the economic value the user may be willing to pay for additional information, or improved information, as long as the expected gain exceeds the cost of the information— inclusive of the cost of gathering and processing these data to render them useful in the particular circumstance.

It is noted that beyond the economic value, social and environmental gains and/or losses, not necessarily expressed with a money indicator, should also be considered in the overall value extraction model. However, as with most non-market driven indicators, putting an economic value on the environmental or social impact is rather complex. The aim at this stage is not so much to put an economic value on these factors but to

highlight them as significant within the context of the use case relying on specific expertise. For these non-monetized benefits appropriate indicators that properly represent potential benefits and a semi-quantitative scaling can be implemented in order to evaluate the benefits.

Common steps are identified to guide the evaluation process which include:

- Define the boundaries of analysis for the use case;
- Understand the value chain of forecasting services and identify the socio-economic and environmental benefits associated with the services;
- Quantify and monetize the value (wherever possible) of benefits identified;

And then:

- Extend the analysis to a broader market

The steps are further developed in MS26 (document “Towards Milestone MS26 - Guidelines for Value Chain assessment”, June 2024), a document that has been used as a road map towards building the business model storylines within the LLs of the I-CISK project. The process described is summarized in the graph of Figure 2. The first three steps of the analysis adopt a user-focused approach (bottom-up approach) which is particularly important to understand how specific user(s) perceive(s) the added value of the particular Climatic Service and determine the Value Proposition from using the I-CISK Climatic Services compared to following current management practices.

Where the analysis can demonstrate potential economic gains or avoided costs, quantification is most preferable to lead to actual financial benefits. In other cases, appropriate indicators that represent well potential benefits and a semi-quantitative scaling, as presented in Table 1, can be implemented in order to evaluate the benefits.

Table 1: Scaling of benefits

NULL – There are no perceivable benefits in this dimension, and no potential for such benefits to emerge is anticipated.	
LATENT – There are, in general, potential benefits, but concrete benefits have not been identified or described in this particular instance.	
	LOW
	MODERATE
MANIFEST – At least one benefit has been identified, with overall significance LOW/MODERATE/HIGH/EXCEPTIONAL	HIGH
	EXCEPTIONAL

The final iteration towards the Business User Story extrapolates the analysis beyond the defined boundaries of the case, through a thorough market analysis which can provide the necessary information. To this end the market analysis framework that has been suggested as part of the Milestone MS25 - Commercial exploitation strategies (November 2022), is applied to create a comprehensive User Story and even beyond to guide towards establishing a concrete and descriptive business model.

The approached followed is structured in tiers with each of the steps providing the user story (business story) of a CS, which gradually builds up in detail and extent of analysis. As noted previously, there are services with

strong social/environmental or gains other than economic (e.g. reputational). This tiered approach allows for the assessment of a storyline for every CS, independent of factors which may confine the extend of analysis such as the type of value and the beneficiaries which are associated with the CS. This offers flexibility given the variability and number of CS developed under the different LLs within the I-CISK project (i.e. not all of the CS developed can or need to reach the final tier, the fourth iteration level, see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Process for value chain analysis

The assessment towards the business model storylines through the tiered approach presented in the previous, is described in the following chapters for each of the I-CISK LLs.

3 Business model storyline for the Rijnland Living Lab (Netherlands)

3.1 Background and context

The CS that has been co-developed in the Rijnland LL (Netherlands) addresses drought challenges in the present and future climate. The local water authorities seek to improve operational mitigation measures and develop long term adaptation strategies, together with and timely communicated to actor groups that are using the surface water system.

As described in Deliverable D1.1. (Masih et al., 2022), the Rijnland LL is situated on the west-coast of the Netherlands, on the North Sea, between the cities of The Hague and Amsterdam. The Rijnland water authority (<https://www.rijnland.net/>) is an important institution responsible for water management in this region. The LL area is mostly flat and below sea level. Extensive dunes along the coast are important for protection against the sea, but also for water supply to the cities through Managed Aquifer Recharge schemes. The surface water system serves both irrigation and drainage, with pumping stations discharging excess water to interconnected canals and out to the North Sea. During dry spells fresh water is let in from the Rhine River, and supplied to low-lying polders through the same interconnected canals. However, when the discharge of the River Rhine is too low because of a drought in the Rhine basin, salt intrusion from the North Sea may reach the fresh water intake of Rijnland at Gouda. This intake has to then temporarily be stopped to avoid too high a salinity in the Rijnland surface water for agricultural use, and instead an alternative inlet location more upstream is activated. This auxiliary inlet is, however, has a reduced capacity such that salinity in the Rijnland area may gradually go up. A second challenge with drought can come from a potential precipitation deficit over the area itself, which may cause drought damage to peat embankments becoming unstable, and, especially when freshwater intake is limited, may also lead to increased surface water salinity levels. To reduce the salinity load to the system, ship lock operations from the Noordzeekanaal, are then limited for water tourism as one of the first mitigation measures, as saline water enters the system during locking processes.

I-CISK co-developed with the Rijnland water authority, water tourism actors, and agricultural sector representatives, a climate service that aims to provide timely pre-alerts of possible upcoming drought, to optimise and better prepare for mitigation measures, and for the water authority to provide timely alerts to water users of these measures and their impacts (Figure 3 and Figure 4).

Figure 3: Seasonal streamflow prediction of Rhine River at Lobith station, with user-defined alert levels indicated.

Figure 4: Seasonal prediction of potential precipitation deficit over the Netherlands, zooming in to Rijnland. Colours on the map correspond to user-defined case drought alert levels. The graph below the map shows the observation-based and forecast potential precipitation deficit for the location selected with point on the map.

3.2 First iteration: Defining boundaries of analysis

At this stage, the boundaries of the analysis for the use case are clearly set. These refer to:

- ❖ The geographical and sectoral focus
- ❖ The targeted users of the developed service
- ❖ The targeted problems the proposed service aim to solve
- ❖ The current practices in place and the need for having an advanced solution to address these problems

The user-focused approach (bottom-up approach) is described in the following for the main sector that this service addresses, leading to the 1st iteration step of the assessment (estimation of the value proposition).

Water management sector - optimisation, preparation, and communication of operational drought measures and awareness raising and strategizing drought risk management in a changing climate

Location: The Rijnland water system is situated in mid-western part of the Netherlands, between Amsterdam and Den Haag (Figure 5). The water system mainly consists of inter-connected surface water canals serving agricultural areas, commercial and tourism shipping, nature areas, and municipalities (receiving waters of waste water treatment plants). The climate of Rijnland, the Netherlands, is temperate oceanic climate (Köppen classification: Cfb), with rain throughout the year. The Rijnland area receives a yearly average of 850 mm precipitation, occurring throughout the months of the year, with reference evapotranspiration at 550 mm per year. In summer months, however, due to higher temperatures, potential evapotranspiration may exceed precipitation. Climate change is projected to lead to higher

temperatures, more pronounced (extreme) events, both wet and dry, and sea level rise.

Figure 5: The command area of Rijnland, with key structures indicated for water system operation during droughts.

End User(s): The water management organisation responsible for design, maintenance, and operation of the water system is the Rijnland water authority (Hoogheemraadschap Rijnland). Operation of regulating structures, pumping stations and inlets, is one of the key tasks to maintain the area-average surface water level within a narrow band of 10 cm target level and the salinity level below high agricultural standards. Minimising too high water-levels (floods), and high salinity periods (droughts), while ensuring bank stability (flood safety) and ship lock operation for ship navigation, is supported by a decision support system with hydrometeorological observed and forecast data and hydrological and system operation models as input.

Challenge: While flood risk management and real-time services for flood control have traditionally been at the forefront of efforts of the water authority, recent droughts (e.g. in 2018) and climate change outlooks have strengthened the activities towards enhancing operational and strategic drought planning services. The challenge identified is twofold: operational drought mitigation measures require preparation time and time to communicate to affected water users beyond the lead time of decision support services currently in place (2 days automatic to max 2 weeks manual), and developing smart long-term drought adaptation measures in a changing climate requires active engagement of water users in the area and integration with their adaptation strategies.

Current practices in place (AS-IS Scenario): Currently, in the summer months, April to September, an expert-based drought report is collated on monthly (in case of no indication of upcoming drought) to weekly intervals (in case of expected or ongoing drought). This report contains the current situation of the water system in the command area, as well as the discharge in the River Rhine as an indicator for securing low-salinity freshwater at the inlet; cumulative potential precipitation deficit, as an indicator for local drought and related potential bank stability problems and fresh water needs for agriculture and keeping salinity in check; and salinity level observations at several locations in the water system, together with a local and national outlooks up to a maximum of two weeks of the discharge in the Rhine and potential precipitation deficit. The report starts with a general drought status. During ongoing drought events, an overview of active mitigation measures, including limitations of ship lock operations affecting water tourism (thus reducing the salinity load) and stopping of the water inlet at Gouda and activating the auxiliary but reduced capacity fresh water inlet via Bodegraven (thus affecting agricultural water users).

Solution (User Requirements)

ID	User requirements		
	As a <ROLE>,	I would like to <GOAL>	to <BENEFIT>
NL1	As a water managerI would like to have regular (weekly) updates of the forecasted potential precipitation deficit for the coming month , from April to September...	...to timely prepare for drought mitigation measures and engage and inform actors involved and affected (dike inspection staff, water tourism and agricultural water users).
NL2	As a water managerI would like to have regular (weekly) updates of the forecasted Rhine river discharge at Lobith for the coming monthto timely prepare for drought mitigation measures and engage and inform actors involved and affected (neighbouring water authorities, water tourism and agricultural water users)

Solution (TO-BE Scenario): I-CISK aspires to expand the information base for Rijnland water authorities' drought management by incorporating sub-seasonal to seasonal forecasts (1-week to 7 months lead time) of local potential precipitation deficit and streamflow of Rhine river at Lobith into a climate service for drought management. Combined with pre-alert (awareness) probabilistic thresholds the climate service would also provide operational drought pre-alerts in the drought-prone season from April to December.

Value Proposition (Goal of the service): Timely forecasts of possible upcoming drought will enable the Rijnland water authority to optimise and plan better for operational drought mitigation measures and communicate these measures and their adverse effects to water users in the area. When combined with user-centred climate change information on droughts, the climate service will also foster active engagement of water users in discussing and developing adaptation strategies. This service will contribute to increased drought resilience and climate change adaptation of the Rijnland area and water system actors as a whole.

3.3 Second iteration: Understanding the value chain

To understand how the use of the CS for providing drought alerts helps actors along the value chain to address the challenges they face at an operational level, a description of the value chain is built in a 4-tier analysis

based on the methodological framework described in MS26 (Guidelines for Value Chain assessment, June 2024), which is summarised in Figure 6. The goal at this point is the analysis to be sufficiently informed to enable the primary user to develop the understanding of the economic benefits and to complete a User Story.

Tier 1 is the “supplier” of the climatic data i.e. the seasonal forecasting data of discharge, temperature (for estimating potential reference evapotranspiration), and precipitation. ECMWF as a pan-European and global met-service (meteorological service provider) generates and provides state-of-the-art climatic data of seasonal meteorological forecasts which may be used by downstream services “as is”, post-processed e.g. in this case bias corrected by SMHI (Swedish national hydrometeorological service provider with Pan-European and Global R&D and products), and/or are repurposed through impact modelling (in present case SMHI by using the hydrological model E-HYPE to create seasonal forecasting of river flows) which widens the services of climatic data. Past and present observed local hydrometeorological observations for LL Rijnland, to provide initial conditions of the seasonal drought forecast and real-time context with the present situation are provided by KNMI (national met-service of the Netherlands). Their benefit from providing climatic data could be: (a) scientific: receiving feedback which allows to enhance their data quality, (b) economic, through the provision of data services and (c) business-oriented, by achieving reputational gains and expanding their partnerships and data provision services.

Tier 2 is the “primary user” (this is also referred to as intermediary user) of the climatic service. 52N and IHE Delft co-develop within the Rijnland LL MAP a drought alert service that transforms the value of the climatic service, acting as **knowledge purveyor** between the supplier (tier 1) and the end user (tier 3) of the climatic service. Through this process, 52N (a Spatial Information Research, non-profit company) enhances its ability to provide added value (innovation gains), develops services which increase its market share and provide additional revenue (economic gains) and builds on its reputational profile which also supports the expansion of partnerships (entrepreneurship gains). IHE Delft, as an academic institute, enhance their research capacity in the field of climate services, with gained knowledge and experience also feeding into their educational programmes (MSc and PhD programmes in the water sector), achieving reputational gains both as research partner and educational institute.

Tier 3 is the “secondary user” i.e. the end user of the service provided by the primary user. The Water Authority, Hoogheemraadschap Rijnland (Rijnland), may add the developed pilot CS to their information and communication sources they use for drought management, with the added lead time of drought pre-alerts beyond two weeks being the key added value. This allows Rijnland to better prepare for and optimise operational water management measures that mitigate impact of drought on bank stability and water salinity. This increases the effectiveness and efficiency of these measures, reducing costs and increasing compliance with the duty of care for the water system and its users. As these drought mitigation measures impact water tourism activities, e.g. boating, and agriculture, e.g. horticulture and crop growers, earlier communication of upcoming drought and potential water management measures, increases trust in the water authority with these users (reputational gain), reducing complaints (cost reduction), and enables water users to, in turn, better plan for and optimise their own drought event management measures.

Figure 6: Understanding of the value chain for the Climate Services developed in the Rijnland Living Lab (Netherlands).

Tier 4 includes the other economic sectors which are associated indirectly with the Rijnland water system's drought management as well as the wider “citizens, society and the environment” in the Rijnland area, which are the end beneficiaries of the climatic service. Better services (water, shipping, agriculture) support Rijnland's continued attractiveness for socio-economic activities and living (reputational gains) which may support increase of or provide stability to the region's economy in a changing climate with increasing pressure on the water system. The citizens and society enjoy the end result of the climate service as enhanced non-saline water availability, navigability, and better environmental conditions. Due to earlier and better drought mitigation decisions and communication, they may enjoy less disruption of tourism activities and reduced agricultural revenue losses (economic gains). Further, better water management, improved environmental conditions, and enhanced water transport-infrastructure conditions translate into broader societal gains.

3.4 Third iteration: Analyse the benefits

Up to this point, the analysis has focused on understanding and setting out the perimeter of the case analysis. The next stage is to analyse the benefits identified and quantify them where possible. It is noted that the analysis presented in the following, targets the assessment of part of the value identified in the 2nd Tier of the value chain analysis.

Where the analysis can demonstrate potential economic gains or avoided costs, quantification is most preferable to lead to actual financial benefits. However, at this point economic gain is not very clear and is also mixed with social and environmental gains. This is why the evaluation of the benefits of the service is based on a qualitative assessment.

Water management sector – qualitative assessment of gains

The water authority of Rijnland sees the potential to benefit from 2-to 4-week lead time drought alerts by;

- improved planning of staff for inspection of embankments (in the summer holiday season this is an extra challenge);
- improved and more timely discussion with neighbouring water authorities on activating the pre-arranged alternative fresh-water intake point further upstream along the River Rhine and transport route from the intake point to the Rijnland water system;
- increasing efficiency and decreasing adverse effects of drought mitigation measures (e.g. delaying having to stop the intake at Gouda because of too high salinity by reducing the intake earlier and scheduling reduced shipping-lock operations),
- improving reputation and reducing complaints by earlier communication with water users, e.g. water tourism and agriculture.

While a rough quantitative estimate of some of these gains could be made (e.g. cost reduction on staff time handling complaints), for others, like reputation gain, this is not possible. We therefore provide a qualitative assessment (see Table 1 for the scale)

With a programme of embankment strengthening being implemented in parallel with this project, the water authority expects the need for extensive staff numbers for dike inspection to have reduced, leading the expected gain of this aspect to be:

LOW

The expected benefit of having more time for discussing (negotiating) on when and how to start regional drought mitigation measure of the alternative (but reduced) water intake, is considered to be:

MODERATE ●●● to **HIGH** ●●●●.

The added value of more in advance alerts and communication with water users in the area, thus improving reputation and trust and reducing complaints, which has been expressed as a concern in earlier events such as the 2018 drought, is considered as:

HIGH ●●●●.

Water tourism sector – qualitative assessment of gains

The water tourism will be aided mainly with earlier decision on the change of boating plans and routes, thus avoiding waiting times in boat jams at ship locks. This constitutes monetary value in reduced fuel and expenses because of delays and detour and incurred costs at delayed or cancelled accommodation for example. However, as these activities are in free time, not in work time, the expected benefits are assessed as:

MODERATE ●●●.

Agricultural sector – qualitative assessment of gains

The agricultural sector can gain from optimised and better planned drought mitigation actions they take themselves, and subsequently cost savings in reducing crop damage, increasing revenues. With the seasonal forecasts being probabilistic, however, quantification of these mixed monetary benefits is complex and uncertain. We therefore start at identifying the potential qualitative added benefit as being:

HIGH ●●●●.

3.5 Fourth iteration: Analysis beyond the defined boundaries

The climate service that has been co-developed in the Rijnland LL primarily targets the command area of the Rijnland water authority, meaning that the LL is identified as the primary market segment for the service. The Rijnland water authority is the primary end user identified. Although, the potential added value of the drought alert pilot application beyond the confines of the command area of the Rijnland water authority is promising because other local water authorities throughout the Netherlands face similar challenges with drought. Since the primary market segment is small – and given the fact that this market is not the key exploitation objective of the developed CS, a full Market Analysis is not considered relevant.

4 Business model storyline for the Andalucía Living Lab (Spain)

4.1 Background and context

For the Spanish case, five complementary CS focussing on drought were developed. These address four main economic sectors: Natural Park managers, livestock farmers (Iberian pork and milk production) and olive oil producers. The results were obtained through active engagement of multiple actors during the first three years of project duration, thus providing a consolidated perception of the main interests, stakes and rationale of local decision-making processes. The analysis revealed that no commercial use is envisioned for the CS produced by the Spanish case, provided that the sustainability strategy is addressing mandated public authorities from the Government of Andalusia to integrate the tool in their drought risk management strategy. The CS will be delivered to the target users in the format of a webtool and APP, both including maps and graphics that can be downloaded.

The five complementary climate services that have been developed in the Andalucía Living Lab are:

Climate service 1 spatially adapted seasonal (6-12 months) monthly precipitation and temperature predictions at a spatial scale adapted to the needs of the users (200 m) (Figure 7). For this service the ECMWF-SEAS5 seasonal prediction models (51 members) are bias-corrected for each percentile of the cumulative distribution function (Empirical quantile mapping) based on daily data time series from the dense network of AEMET stations.

The products generated are continuous maps of monthly (6-month) future precipitation and temperature predictions for the most representative percentiles (5, 10, 25, 50, 75, 90, and 95) of the 51 members, and maps of the spatial variability of the interquartile range for the 51 members.

Figure 7: Screenshot of the visualization of CS1 – seasonal predictions.

Climate service 2 Decadal (10 years) climate impact projections regarding monthly precipitation and temperature that is adjusted to the spatial scale of the region (approximately 200 m) (Figure 8). For generating this service, Geostatistical downscaling of Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS) projections for the RCP4.5

scenario (medium CO2 emissions, temperature increase between 1.8 and 3.1 °C) have been used to produce continuous maps at 1 km spatial resolution of monthly future precipitation and temperature predictions for the period 2025-2040.

Figure 8: Screenshot of the visualization of CS2 – 10 years climate impact projections (mock up).

Climate service 3: Historical temperature and precipitation data in a format adapted to the preferences and needs of the users. For generating this service (Figure 9) post-processed monthly historical records (filtered and aggregated from daily data) of precipitation and average temperature at AEMET stations (January 1950 to January 2025) have been used to produce continuous maps of precipitation, temperature, and drought indices (SPI, SPEI) at 250 m spatial resolution, generated using geostatistical techniques from monthly historical records (January 1990 to January 2025). The service incorporates query tools to assess trend dynamics e.g. comparing two selected months/years, two locations, or two variables for the same or different time ranges (Figure 10).

Figure 9: Screenshot of the visualization of CS3 – historical climate maps for comparative analysis.

Figure 10: Screenshot of the visualization of CS3 – local meteorological stations historical data.

Climate service 4: I-CISK developed olive tree production indicators based on historical climate information (CS 3) and historical production data from OLIFE cooperative in order to estimate future production based on climate predictions (CS2) and projections (CS 1).

Furthermore, the service includes agro-climatic indicators produced by Copernicus CS, and tailored to the regional interest and scale (Figure 11). In this case, one of the agroclimatic indicators from the “Copernicus Agroclimatic Indicators from 1951 to 2099” service derived from climate projections has been integrated as an agroclimatic and phenological service. The indicator describes the longest interval of consecutive days with daily precipitation less than 1 mm over a 3-month period, coinciding with the 4 seasons: Dec-Jan-Feb (INV), Mar-Apr-May (PRI), Jun-Jul-Aug (VER), Sep-Oct-Nov (OTO). The indicator is offered at a spatial resolution of 50 km and for the period 2011-2040.

Figure 11: screenshot of the visualization of CS3 – local meteorological stations historical.

Climate service 5: A hydrogeological characterization of groundwater bodies in the region aspiring to link its evolution with climate modelling and evolution of uses. It includes continuous maps, vectoral maps and qualitative information based on local experiences contrasted with literature (see Figure 12).

Figure 12: screenshot of the visualization of CS5 – hydrogeological characterization of groundwater bodies.

The business model storylines process is tailored to the context of the LL and this procedure enriched the understanding of opportunities related to the services developed. All services produced are tailored to the needs of all targeted economic sectors, therefore the business model analysis is performed as a cluster.

4.2 First iteration: defining boundaries of analysis

Location: The Andalusia living lab is located between the Guadalquivir and Guadiana River basin districts (Figure 13). It focuses primarily on the *comarca* (region) of Los Pedroches, a primarily agricultural area located in the north of the province of Córdoba, in the autonomous region of Andalucía, Spain. It also includes the Sierra de Cazorla, Segura and Las Villas Natural Park in the upper Guadalquivir RBD as a complementary site for testing the climate model and climate services developed for forest landscapes. The Comarca is a primarily rainfed agricultural region, where different land use systems and landscapes coexist: the Dehesa, the *olivares de sierra* (mountain olive groves), the agricultural plains, and the Mediterranean forests of the Sierra de Cardena and Montoro Natural Park. The *Dehesa* is an agrosilvopastoral system unique to the Iberian Peninsula where oak trees, native grasses and free-range livestock – primarily Iberian black pigs, sheep and cows – interact under management. The *Dehesa* occupies almost 60% of Los Pedroches region, and is one of the best preserved in the Peninsula. The *olivares de sierra* is a unique olive production system in the southern part of the region, where the steep terrain requires traditional management and harvesting practices, and where remnants of the original Mediterranean forest can still be found. Agricultural activities – Iberian pig, sheep and beef products, olive oil, and other agricultural production – are the main source of income in the region.

Figure 13: The region of Los Pedroches, Córdoba, Spain. Source: prepared by the authors using data collected from [IGN](#), [EEA](#) and [MITECO](#).

End User(s): The Andalusia living lab stakeholder platform reflects the focus on the agricultural sector, both rainfed olive production and extensive livestock farming, as well as on the management of natural forested areas and associated uses, such as hunting tourism. The LL map of actors integrates Water basin authorities for Guadiana and Guadalquivir River basins, responsible for water resources planning and management, as well as drought and flood risk management. Andalusian Government Environmental Evaluation and Analysis Service responsible for REDIAM (Environmental Information Network of Andalusia) is producing georeferenced environmental information of Andalucía in a single portal. On forestry the LL counts on Natural Park authorities for Sierra de Cardeña and Montoro Natural Park, as well as the Center for Forest Management, Experimentation and Training of Cazorla within the Cazorla, Segura and Las Villas natural park. Related to the forestry sector, but strongly linked also to agriculture and marketing of products and tourism, the living lab includes the Andalusian Federation of Hunters (FAC). Rural development agency Adroches is the local action group that has managed the LEADER EU funds since 1995. While from the farming sectors the lab integrates an olive producing cooperative OLIPE, milk production and *dehesa* pig farming cooperatives COVAP, as well as the R&D department CICAP. The research sector is also represented with Andalusian Institute for Agricultural, Fisheries, Food and Organic Production Research and Training (IFAPA) contributing with insights from their long-standing experience developing research projects on the subject in the region.

Challenge: Drought events are considered the main climate hazard in this region. Agricultural activities, which are the main economic activity, are primarily rainfed, and thus exposure to drought risks is high. The *dehesa* agroforestry production system and the *olivares de sierra* olive oil production systems have co-evolved with periodic droughts that are characteristic to the Mediterranean climate of the *comarca* of Los Pedroches. However, due to climate change, longer and more intense drought periods are impacting agricultural practices. The 2017-2024 drought period is the longest on record in the region and affected domestic water supply and agricultural activities. New measures have been implemented to ensure water supply for livestock and to address economic impacts resulting from decreased agricultural production. In addition, over the past 20 years a thriving milk production livestock farming has developed, which is more water-intensive than traditional

farming practices and have generated water quality impacts that are affecting water supply. In the same line, forest conservation management, like plantations in degraded areas, are seriously affected by the impacts of rising temperatures and changes in rainfall patterns. Currently there are only two meteorological stations in the *comarca* de Los Pedroches so that current CS do not provide climate information adapted to local needs.

Current practices in place (AS-IS Scenario): The *comarca* of Los Pedroches has been enduring a historic drought episode during the time of the project. Interest and demand for climate services is therefore high at the moment. Local climate service producers from the Andalusian government publish climate information, but a specific communication strategy is not in place, and tailored information (both spatially and temporally) is not available. Additionally, the formats used limit accessibility for practitioners and layman users. Currently, actors engaged in the LL mostly rely on short term meteorological forecasts or traditional knowledge.

Solution (User Requirements)

ID	User requirements		
	As a <ROLE>	I would like to <GOAL>	to <BENEFIT>
ES1	As an olive oil producing cooperativeI would like to estimate if next year's spring (feb- may) will be humid , especially if it will rain in marchto envision production levels and decide upon stock management of the oil produced last year, close selling and price agreements , and to manage human resources .
ES2	As an olive oil producing cooperativeI would like to know what the climate change projections are in a 10-30 year (precipitation and temperature)to inform the commercial and infrastructure investment policies of the cooperative.
ES3	As an olive oil producing cooperativeI would like to know what the expected temperature will be this year in may to estimate flowering intensity of the olive trees and calibrate fertilisation as well as estimate production levels .
ES4	As an olive oil producing cooperativeI would like to know how much it will rain next springto inform pruning and harvesting planning .
ES5	As a nature conservation public authority	...I would like to know more precise information on precipitation patterns in the forested area for next spring...	...to inform on meadow productivity estimations , needed to nourish protected fauna.
ES6	As a dairy farm manager I would like to know how many days temperature will exceed 35 degrees to inform barn adaptations needed for caw comfort.
ES7	As a Dehesa farm manager I would like to know the groundwater dynamics in my field...	... to inform if the temporary pond in the field will have water during autumn.

ID	User requirements		
	As a <ROLE>,	I would like to <GOAL>	to <BENEFIT>
ES8	As a hunting association...	... I would like to know when summer ends next year...	... to inform the estimations about when the game will start reproducing .
ES9	As a water management authority...	... I would like to know drought index projections to inform drought risk management rulings.
ES10	As a research institute I would like to know the most downscaled possible climate change projections in the region...	... to inform comparative studies on foreseen climate change impacts.

Solution (TO-BE Scenario):

For each climate service, we provide an example of impact stories to underpin the kind of needs from the MAP are satisfied by I-CISK CS development.

CS1 End-user: Natural Park

Situation: Each year the Natural Park needs to estimate the number and species of trees seedlings needed for next season to restore and maintain the forest in the natural park area.

Complication: reduced rainfall and changing precipitation patterns in late spring increases the mortality of young trees planted.

Question: no sound information on seasonal and sub-seasonal precipitation predictions for the upcoming year is available.

Answer: ICISK provides a prediction of precipitation for the relevant period and spatially focusing on the natural park area, thus facilitating drought risk management when buying new trees for the next season.

CS2 End-user: dairy farmer

Situation: Dairy cow milk production levels decrease with extreme heat. Water is necessary for drinking, cleaning and for maintaining cool temperatures in the cow sheds, for instance through indoor sprinklers or other more advanced methods. Farms need to foresee the number of animals needed and guarantee its climatic comfort to maintain milk production and ensure the economic viability of the farm.

Complication: dairy farms need to plan long term investments, such as cow sheds and cooling systems, as well as future water availability to run the farm.

Question: There are no climate forecasts that can help plan this decision making at farm scale.

Answer: I-CISK provides downscaled climate forecasts tailored to the needs of dairy farming in Los Pedroches, allowing to reduce the risk of long-term investments.

CS3 End-user: all citizens

Situation: Local population in the Los Pedroches area perceive drought episodes in accordance to their memory of past episodes; additionally, management decisions are often based on past experiences rather than on scientific evidence.

Complication: impacts of drought on daily lives of the Los Pedroches society are increasing, implying economic loss and emotional trauma.

Question: Los Pedroches society has no easy access to scientific evidence on past climatic conditions to corroborate their beliefs and improve their decision making.

Answer: I-CISK provides a visual tool to navigate and explore past climatic conditions in the region, so that people can relate the drought impacts suffered in the past to this data as well as to help interpreting the predicted and forecasted conditions.

CS4 End-user: olive oil production

Situation: Rainfed olive production is highly affected by climatic conditions. Producers experience difficulties to fine-tune the operational calendar of agronomic activities in the field to increase tree resilience.

Complication: climate variability due to climate change compromises the effectiveness of traditional decision-making criteria.

Question: relevant agro-climatic indicators are not accessible and causal relations between climatic conditions and final olive production yields are often unclear.

Answer: I-CISK tailors existing agro-climatic indicators published by Copernicus to local conditions in Los Pedroches and produces a pilot investigation to correlate climatic conditions to the production obtained.

CS5 End-user: livestock farmer

Situation: farm management decision making relies mainly on market prices, while risk management based on climate is weak.

Complication: drought-related impacts increase water needs and increases the use of groundwater resources in the region.

Question: due to the lack of hydrogeological information, livestock farmers cannot estimate future water availability in the short-medium term.

Answer: I-CISK provides a characterization of groundwater bodies and their relation to climatic conditions, fostering enhanced decision making to improve water management of livestock farms in Los Pedroches.

Value Proposition (Goal of the service): The climate service information impacts the core decision making process for olive oil, milk and *dehesa* farmers, as well as it provides key input for forest management, like restoration actions, as well as envisioning scarcity management needs related to groundwater exploitation in the region. The climate service contributes to enhancing adaptation and resilience towards drought in the region, allowing to improve production and economic management decisions. Therefore, the economic values enhanced by the CS in the Andalusian LL are linked to agriculture production mainly. The developed CS also contributes to changing the perception of drought at socio-cultural level, providing sound data to compare with past events. This aspect is politically relevant as to induce behavioural changes needed to reduce vulnerability.

4.3 Second iteration: understanding the value chain

As described in table in Figure 14, the value chain for CS1, 2 and 3 has been analysed through the different tiers of service provision. **Tier 1** is the “supplier” of the climatic data i.e. the seasonal forecasting data of essential variables or impact models results. EU, through dedicated services and programs such as Copernicus, provides climatic data to a large end-user group. ECMWF as a scientific organization generates and provides high quality climatic data of seasonal forecasts which may be used by downstream services “as is” or are repurposed through impact modelling by scientific institutes (in the present case by SMHI) which widen the services of climatic data (e.g. seasonal forecasting of river flows). For the Spanish case, also the National Meteorological Organization (AEMET) as well as REDIAM (Environmental Information Network of Andalusia), an agency of Andalusian Government Environmental Evaluation and Analysis Service, are included. Furthermore, the olive producers cooperative OLIFE, also has a limited network of informal data gathering on precipitation, so we consider them as providers of information too. These actors benefit from the services through:

- ECMWF can incur scientific gains, as I-CISK CS provides user feedback to service providers relevant to improve the quality of information produced.
- AEMET can gain societal benefits, as I-CISK CS can increase the recognition for the work delivered by meteorological services by increasing information accessibility to end users.
- The olive growers cooperative OLIPE can gain environmental benefits, as I CISK CS help raising awareness for the need for adaptation measures to be put in place in the face of the impacts of climate change.
- Copernicus can gain innovation benefits from increased investments in climate data analysis, as I-CISK CS gains visibility in the population influencing the political agenda.
- REDIAM can gain innovation benefits, as I-CISK CS is able to reach a broad public with useful research results and new science into society programs can be enhanced, as well as funding opportunities to further develop the work started by the project.

Tier 2 is the “primary user” (this is also referred to as intermediary user) of the climatic service, and for the Spanish case these are identified as REDIAM and IFAPA, as well as the river basin authorities, provided they work on raw data and develop intermediate climate services. These actors benefit from the services through:

- IFAPA can gain scientific benefits through increasing academic publications enhanced by the CS development and use, as well as complementarity to other research projects in course in the region.
- REDIAM can gain regulatory benefits, as improved climate data by I-CISK can sustain revision of current risk management protocols.
- River basin authorities can gain societal benefits provided users are better informed by I-CISK CS and better prepared for drought risk management

Tier 3 is the “secondary user” i.e. the end user of the service provided by the primary user. For the Spanish case, farming cooperatives, food chain retailers and public authorities such as the natural parks are key beneficiaries. These actors benefit from the services through:

- I-CISK CS allow innovation benefits for the farming cooperatives, as it fosters climate conscious business practices, improving risk management with respect to current practices, thus potentially reducing economic losses and allowing for innovation in entrepreneurship models.
- Public authorities can gain environmental benefits from I-CISK CS through improved preparedness for facing the impacts of drought, inducing the development of complementary solutions for supply, avoiding emergency induced over exploitation of local water bodies and fraudulent behaviour (unlicensed wells or use of wells beyond licensing agreements).
- I-CISK CS can provide benefits to farming cooperatives in terms of innovation in business practices also fostering a stronger relation between the cooperatives and scientific actors, generating a creative environment potentially enhancing innovative practices reducing overall vulnerability of the region.

Tier 4 includes the other economic sectors, which for the Spanish case are consumers (olive oil, milk and cheese, Iberian ham, hunters), natural site visitors, pupils (capacity building beneficiaries) and citizens as direct water consumers. It is important to state that the inhabitants of Los Pedroches were not supplied with piped drinking water for over a year, and the impacts of drought are very strongly perceived in the community. Therefore, improved drought management, risk management and awareness are key to ensure improved food security and citizen wellbeing. These key factors are strongly linked to the depletion of water related and terrestrial ecosystems health, main tourism provisions related to natural heritage, gastronomy and hunting activities. Representatives of these key economic sectors participated in the living lab because of their interest in reducing economic losses and seeking adaptation options to avoid job losses. Drought has influenced political stability in the region, confronting territories and water users, thus climate services introducing evidence-based information are also key to fight misinformation and manipulation of public opinion. In this sense the CS number 3 was developed, so as to be able to confront the perception of past drought episodes with real data.

I-CISK CS can provide societal benefits to citizens by contributing to safeguarding public health, provided droughts and associated health waves are affecting local society in many ways, but specially in terms of sanitary discomfort and water-borne diseases, as well as plagues related to the overall environmental degradation induced by drought. CS can provide regulatory benefits to public authorities managing natural parks and other emergency services affecting the local population, helping to improve the quality of current wildfire-risk alerts, but also sanitary alerts and other early warning systems in place. The CS developed can provide environmental benefits to the population of Los Pedroches reducing natural resource depletion, especially water related environments, as an effect of better drought management and improved knowledge about the hydrogeological features of the area. In the same line, CS can provide environmental benefits through reduced impact on biodiversity, both in freshwater environments, as well as terrestrial ecosystems, due to improved information available to Los Pedroches communities.

Climate service number 4 is particularly interesting for olive oil producers but aims at paving the way to an increased use of the Copernicus agroclimatic indicators for different farming sectors. Current service is very much tailored to this particular setting, but given the importance of olive groves in the landscape, other actors of the living lab also indicated the potential indirect effects of this service. The tier analysis has similar results to the other services, and will enhance risk management, avoiding losses and protecting the rural economy it sustains.

Olive oil can be stored, so market fluctuations can be palliated through stock management. This service is most directly linked to production costs, but these were impossible to quantify given the huge diversity of farming models (mountainous areas, plane areas, small or bigger enterprises, age of the farmer and many other factors).

For climate service number 5 the analysis shows how the hydro-geological characterization contributes, complementing the services above. In this case the river basin authorities are also providers of primary information, related to the impact of the climatic conditions on the local water bodies. It is important to note that the region does not have abundant freshwater streams directly supplying the different users. This means that groundwater resources are key. Groundwater bodies are defined and monitored as by the water Framework Directive (2000/60/CE), but detailed information how on how groundwater flows in the Los Pedroches landscape are available. Local drought resilience is strongly linked to land use, therefore these services have strong value, not only in terms of improved land use and groundwater exploitation options, but also in terms of an improved understanding of this landscape by local society. This socio-political value strongly emerged in the conversations held during field work and ad hoc surveys.

Figure 14: Understanding the value chain for Climate Services CS1, CS2 & CS3 (par. 4.2) developed in the Andalucía Living Lab (Spain).

4.4 Third iteration: Analyse the benefits

The Spanish Living lab MAP includes several different socioeconomic profiles, which means that benefits are many and diverse. This is an advantage for the sustainability of the CS produced by I-CISK as raising interest from different sectors increases the number of decisions that take climate related risks into account. In this sense, we can identify that most benefits are obtained by reduced drought related losses.

For this analysis we focus on CS 1 seasonal predictions for the *dehesa* livestock breeding sector, as this is the economically strongest value chain in Los Pedroches (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Demand for climate services offered by the I-CISK project based on economic sector (note that SC is CS in Spanish, denoting the five CS developed in the project).

CS1 reduces production cost losses induced by drought, especially regarding the following production factors:

- Each year the farmer decides the carrying capacity of the *dehesa*, breeding or buying the correct number of young swine on a yearly basis. Agroforestry resources define the need for buying additional fodder for the pigs.
- If the estimation of additional fodder is not correct that could lead to additional expenses for further supply, which could range up to a moderate economic burden, based on the annual budget
- Additionally, the swine need to be supplied beverage water in the plot. Usually there are temporary ponds and little streams in the landscape that farmers count on for supply.
- If the estimation of available water resources is not correct, this could lead to an under-(or over) estimation of the additional water which should be bought for the Dehesa farm. That could lead to additional costs which could range up to a moderate economic burden, based on the annual budget.
- Further, seasonal temperature and rain patterns are key factors in the decision timeline for pruning the oak trees. Correct pruning will increase the tree health and comfort.
- If pruning is not optimal, this will reduce the quantity of fodder the pigs will have. That could lead to additional costs to buy complementary fodder, which could range up to a moderate economic burden, based on the annual budget.

Based on the above reasonable steps towards identification of the value chain and on the scaling of benefits given in Table 1, the service demonstrates two specific benefits for cost reduction. Based on the reasoning of “avoided costs” which are identified by the end-user as low to medium, the benefit of the service is identified as:

LOW ●● to MODERATE ●●●.

4.5 Fourth iteration: Analysis beyond the defined boundaries

For the Spanish case we identify the MAP of the living lab as a primary market segment, provided the service was entirely tailored to the most characteristic features of Los Pedroches. For users outside the region the I-CISK service could be adapted. In this sense, I-CISK can promote the adoption of user centred services to other regions fostering new projects to be developed to promote the approach, but this is not the primary focus of the CS developed in this LL.

It is important to remark that the establishing of the living lab multi-actor platform itself is an added value of the project. In the first place because it has provided territorial cohesion and dialogue between key actors that were not in contact before the project. The new relations established can provide a more transversal reaction to the need for adaptation, boosting co-benefits between the measures adopted in each sector.

The most prominent users of the service produced are the livestock farmers, followed by other agricultural practices, such as olive oil production, that are the primary actors in this market segment. Still, this is a very small segment and there is no point on proceeding with a full market analysis because this market is not the key exploitation objective of the Climate Service.

The key actor for sustainability of the CS produced in the Spanish case after the end of the project has been identified as REDIAM, the public purveyor of climate services established by the regional government. No commercial use would be envisioned, as the service would be integrated in other publicly available climate services published by this organisation, e-g- on wildfire fire risk.

Based on the above, this market is not the key exploitation objective of the developed CSs and therefore, a full market analysis would not be relevant.

5 Business model storyline for the Emilia Romagna Living Lab (Italy)

5.1 Background and context

The Emilia-Romagna Living Lab (ITA LL) is embedded in the upper Secchia River catchment, an area spanning the provinces of Modena and Reggio Emilia in Northern Italy. This region faces increasing climate challenges, notably droughts and water scarcity, which demand innovative approaches to water resource management co – developed with the contribution of the Multi Actor Platform involved on the Lab activities. The ITA LL focuses indeed on co-developing a Climate Service (CS) prototype tailored to support decision-making processes for water allocation and resource planning amidst these challenges.

The co-design process has been anchored in a collaborative engagement with key stakeholders, including the Regional Environmental Agency (ARPAE), Land Reclamation Consortia, water utility companies, and hydropower producers. Leveraging a Multi-Actor Platform (MAP), the Living Lab has iteratively refined the CS through workshops, interviews, and interactive boards, addressing both short-term coping strategies and long-term adaptation measures.

At the core of the CS is a data-driven framework combining real-time monitoring, historical records, and predictive models. It integrates upstream river discharge forecasts (provided by external providers and services like Copernicus or SMHI) with local environmental data (observed discharge at existing gauging stations and relevant thresholds set for decision making during drought periods), offering stakeholders actionable insights into water availability and flow management. This service aims to enhance operational efficiency, reduce administrative burdens, and improve compliance with environmental regulations. An example of the main page of the service is provided below.

Figure 16: Example of Climate Service landing page and buttons to select specific river station to provide discharge forecast.

By embedding the CS into existing governance structures, such as the periodic Drought Observatory and regional Resilience Plans, the ITA LL seeks to facilitate proactive water management strategies. This integration underscores the value proposition of the CS we are trying to define, in minimizing economic losses during droughts, promoting environmental sustainability, and supporting equitable water distribution. Additionally, it offers a pathway to scale similar approaches across other regions, demonstrating the replicability and scalability of the service to many similar hydraulic nodes existing across the Region.

For this reason, the type of information to display is being iteratively refined to provide relevant information and forecasts tailored to local needs and specific decision-making processes, as illustrated in the following example.

The subsequent sections outline the iterative steps taken to estimate the CS value, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative approaches, and examine the potential pathways for its sustainable implementation and commercial exploitation.

Figure 17: Example of forecast discharge displays selectable through the GUI; custom forecast window on a daily basis (upper) to be matched with critical thresholds like minimum environmental flow, along with cumulated values (lower) on a monthly basis relevant for users that can manage storage systems.

5.2 First iteration: Defining boundaries of analysis

At this stage, the boundaries of the analysis for the ITA LL use case have been clearly defined. These boundaries encompass the following aspects:

- ❖ The geographical and sectoral focus
- ❖ The targeted users of the developed service

- ❖ The targeted problems the proposed service aim to solve
- ❖ The current practices in place and the need for having an advanced solution to address these problems

We defined the boundaries of the problem starting from dedicated interviews with users, to form the foundation of the 1st iteration step of the Value of Information (VoI) assessment. This step aims to estimate the value proposition of the Climate Service (CS) by evaluating its potential to enhance decision-making processes, improve resource allocation, and address regional water management challenges effectively.

Location: The Emilia-Romagna Living Lab is situated in the upper Secchia River catchment, with the outlet at the Castellarano Weir in the Emilia Romagna region. This area spans the provinces of Modena and Reggio Emilia (Figure 18) and covers approximately 700 square kilometres. The Secchia River catchment is vital for the region's agricultural and industrial activities, providing essential water resources for irrigation, industry and hydropower. The river is a critical part of the local water management infrastructure, with key features including the Castellarano Weir, which helps regulate water flow and distribution. The region is characterized by its Mediterranean climate, which presents unique challenges in terms of water availability and management, with prolonged summer droughts, making it an ideal setting for developing and implementing innovative climate services focused on water resource management amidst increasing climatic variability and extreme weather events.

Figure 18: Castallarano weir on the Secchia River, which spans the upper provinces of Reggio Emilia and Modena in the Emilia Romagna Region, Italy.

End User(s): The primary end users of the Emilia-Romagna Living Lab include the *Regione Emilia-Romagna* (Regional Authority, RER), responsible for regional policymaking and water resource

management, and the *Consorzi di Bonifica* (Land Reclamation and Irrigation Consortia), which manage irrigation systems and ensure water distribution for agriculture (serving an area of over 360'00 hectares). Key stakeholders also encompass the Regional Environmental Agency (ARPAE), which monitors and assesses water resources providing data and emitting periodic bulletins on drought, multiutility companies like IRETI (that manages integrated water service in 242 municipalities of Emilia Romagna) and hydropower producers such as AREN Spa (that manages an installed capacity of 3.2 MW along the river and provides an expected annual clean energy production around 11 GWh/year). These entities collaborate to develop and refine strategies, such as the Climate Service under development within I-CISK, aimed at enhancing water management practices and addressing the challenges posed by climate change.

 Challenge: The Emilia-Romagna region faces significant challenges in **managing its water resources due to the impacts of climate change, including** prolonged droughts, water scarcity, and the need for effective allocation of water among agricultural, industrial, and environmental users. The extreme drought of 2022 underscored the region's vulnerability and the limitations of current water management practices. Balancing the demands of a diverse set of water users, while ensuring environmental sustainability and economic viability, requires innovative solutions and adaptive strategies to cope with these evolving challenges.

 Current practices in place (AS-IS Scenario): Current water management practices in Emilia-Romagna rely heavily **on historical data, real-time monitoring, and** established emergency protocols. The Regional Environmental Agency (ARPAE) Uses River stage and discharge data from gauging stations inform decision-making processes based on traffic light style thresholds approved by the Regional Government. During periods of drought, stakeholders convene through platforms such as the **Drought Observatory Table** to coordinate responses and implement measures like water withdrawal reductions. Despite these efforts, the decision-making **process is largely reactive, based on observed conditions and past experiences.** The integration of advanced climate services and long-term forecasts into operational planning is limited but represents a critical area for future development to enhance resilience and sustainability in water resource management.

Solution (User Requirements)

ID	User requirements		
	As a <ROLE>,	I would like to <GOAL>	to <BENEFIT>
ITA01	Technician of the Environmental Agency	Have detailed forecasts of river discharge for the next 15 days, compared with historical data,	to evaluate the integration of our products with new forecasts and improve the accuracy of our water resource management decisions.
ITA02	Technician of the Land Reclamation Authority	Have comprehensive data on river discharge and hydrometric levels, including short-term and long-term forecasts, Access projections on seasonal water availability and variability	Better anticipate emergency measures, optimize water distribution adjustments, and prioritize distribution among different sources Develop proactive irrigation plans and reduce reliance on costly or less sustainable water sources

ID	User requirements		
	As a <ROLE>,	I would like to <GOAL>	to <BENEFIT>
ITA03	Technician of the Regional Government	<p>Know the short-term river discharge forecasts at key points in advance</p> <p>Promote use of predictive tools to improve the balance between water demand and ecological needs inside shared pre-approved protocols (“resilience plans”)</p> <p>Integrate user drive initiatives inside the traffic light-style alerts on forecast thresholds particularly in “yellow” area</p>	<p>Enhance the decision-making capabilities of water resource managers and adopt updated rules for environmental flow management while preserving ecological values</p> <p>Reduce instances of regulatory non-compliance and administrative interventions</p> <p>Enhance operational decision-making and avoid unnecessary escalation to drought emergency protocols</p>
ITA04	Technician of a Water Utility Company	<p>Access real-time data from single hydrometric stations and other critical points, including forecast and historical data</p> <p>Receive early warning notifications for significant flow changes</p>	<p>Enhance our emergency response measures and ensure uninterrupted water supply to our customers</p> <p>Mitigate risks of water supply interruptions and alert in advance for possible reactivation</p>
ITA05	Hydropower Plant Operator,	Have accurate discharge forecasts for up to 15 days, presented in both graphical and tabular formats	Schedule maintenance during low flow periods, minimize the impact on energy production, and ensure optimal operational efficiency

Solution (TO-BE Scenario): The proposed solution for the Emilia-Romagna Living Lab enhances water resource management through an advanced climate service. **It integrates real-time or offline monitoring data and predictive models to provide river discharge forecasts.** Users access a user-friendly interface displaying forecasts, historical data, and real-time information, with pre-defined visualizations and threshold indicators to support decision-making. The solution **seamlessly integrates with ARPAE’s monitoring network for comprehensive data coverage and updates basing on recorded discharges and fixed thresholds.**

Autonomous access to the service to inform stakeholders of potential water scarcity risks, enabling **proactive management** and timely emergency measures (like scheduling storage or maintenance) and reducing economic impacts.

Usage of shared protocols that include use of the service (such as in the Resilience plans to be proposed by stakeholders and approved by the Region) to take informed decisions inside actual frameworks of traffic light style thresholds reducing administrative burdens for the Region.

Value Proposition (Goal of the service): The main goal we follow to evaluate the service value is driven by consideration shared with the **Regional Authority**, and it is to facilitate the adoption of an integrated climate service platform designed to enhance the decision-making capabilities of water resource managers (like other stakeholders involved in the MAP) in the Emilia-Romagna region. By

providing accurate and timely forecasts, the service reduces the traditional reliance on reactive practices based on historical data, **enabling more effective management** of water resources. This approach aims at minimizing the need for **derogations** from minimum vital flows, offering in principle both significant **environmental benefits** while simultaneously reducing **administrative burdens** associated with governance

The platform empowers intermediate users by providing them with the tools and information necessary to make **informed decisions** at the appropriate scale, thereby decentralizing water management and improving response times. This **delegation of responsibilities** reduces operational complexity and allows for greater flexibility in addressing localized issues. The service **is not conflicting, but instead complementing** seamlessly with other tools already used, such as [Irrinet](#) and Irriframe for water demand and irrigation needs.

Another source of potential value is optimization of the use of available water resources, reducing the impacts of scarcity on agriculture and industry, and **lowering costs** associated with alternative water sources. It supports compliance with regulatory requirements, offering advanced tools for managing environmental flows and ensuring adherence to water usage permits, thus mitigating the risks of penalties and promoting ecological sustainability.

Furthermore, the service enhances stakeholder confidence by enabling intermediate users to act independently in pre-alert scenarios, the so called "yellow zones," fostering a proactive approach to water management and reducing administrative delays otherwise required. With this respect the CS may be included in the **Resilience plans** to be adopted and approved.

To encourage widespread adoption, the Regional Authority may provide **financial support** for necessary instrumentation and training. This support not only incentivizes use but also ensures that the service can achieve its full potential in delivering sustainable, efficient, and resilient water management for the Emilia-Romagna region.

5.3 Second iteration: Understanding the value chain

The value chain for the Climate Service (CS) developed in the Italian Living Lab (ITA LL) is described using a four-tier framework, reflecting the roles and benefits of key actors. This analysis illustrates how the CS supports operational improvements in water resource management, regulatory compliance, and societal benefits in the Emilia-Romagna region.

Tier 1: The “supplier” of climatic data

The first tier comprises scientific institutions and open repositories that provide high-quality climate data. These include SMHI, which offers river discharge forecasts, and the Copernicus Climate Data Store (powered by ECMWF), which delivers open-access (as in the [new Copernicus CDS](#) powered by ECMWF) or *pay for* river discharge forecasts. These suppliers may benefit either directly from revenue generation through upstream data services, or the enhancement of data collection and analysis capabilities and reputational gains by supporting downstream applications of their data. Feedback from users further enhances the quality and relevance of the provided datasets.

Tier 2: The “primary user” (knowledge purveyor)

In this tier, GECOsystema (a consulting engineering and research SME) serves as an example of the service provider, transforms raw climate data into actionable insights tailored to the needs of local stakeholders. GECOsystema processes and integrates data into operational workflows, enhancing decision-making tools for regional water management. Their benefits include economic gains through service provision, innovation through the development of tailored climate solutions, and reputational growth that supports expanded partnerships and service reach.

Tier 3: The “secondary users” (end users)

The end users include the Regional Government (Regione Emilia-Romagna) and Land Reclamation Consortia (Consorti di Bonifica). These entities apply the CS in their strategic and operational decision-making processes, such as water allocation, drought management, and compliance with environmental regulations. The Regional Government uses the CS to reduce administrative burdens and improve governance, while the consortia optimize water distribution and access to lower-cost water sources. Both users benefit from improved operational efficiency, regulatory compliance, and reduced costs associated with extraordinary deliberations during drought periods.

Tier 4: Wider “citizens, society, and the environment”

This tier represents the broader beneficiaries of the CS, including farmers served by the consortia, citizens benefiting from improved water availability, and the riverine ecosystem maintained in good status. Farmers experience greater water security, especially during droughts, while citizens enjoy stable or reduced water costs and improved environmental conditions. The riverine ecosystem benefits from better flow management, reducing the number of low-flow days and ensuring ecological sustainability. Together, these outcomes enhance societal resilience and quality of life.

Figure 19: Understanding of the proposed value chain for the Climate Services developed in the Emilia Romagna Living Lab (Italy).

5.4 Third iteration: Analyse the benefits

The third iteration of the analysis focuses on quantifying and assessing the economic benefits and feasibility of the Climate Service for the Emilia-Romagna Living Lab. Based on stakeholder engagement, the discussion has identified two primary dimensions of benefit realization: reduction of administrative burdens and incentivized adoption of the service.

The following iterative analysis demonstrates the Climate Service's potential to deliver tangible economic benefits by, for example, reducing administrative costs and incentivizing its implementation.

By embedding the service into the region's operational and governance frameworks, Emilia-Romagna can achieve greater efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and resilience in water resource management.

Regional Government– quantifying the gains and possible incentives

Reducing Administrative Burdens

The current framework for water resource management in Emilia-Romagna relies on reactive emergency interventions, particularly during drought periods. These involve acts such as derogations from the Minimum Ecologic Discharge (*Deflusso Minimo Vitale /DMV, Deflusso Ecologico /DE*) and extraordinary deliberations for preventive reservoir filling. These procedures are:

- Time-consuming, requiring inter-institutional coordination.
- Administratively costly, involving technical assessments, legal procedures, and multi-stakeholder consultations.

By integrating the Climate Service within regional Resilience Plans, to be proposed by major users like - Irrigation Consortia and approved by the Region, these procedures can be significantly streamlined or, in many cases, avoided altogether. The cost savings have been roughly estimated for the sake of this analysis with the collaboration of the representatives of the Regional Government:

- Derogation procedures: Each derogation for DMV adjustments costs at least €1,000; the region handles an average of five per year, totalling €5,000 annually.
- Deliberation procedures: Each extraordinary deliberation costs at least €5,000, with 1 to 3 occurring per year, averaging €10,000 per year for major hydraulic nodes.
- Personnel costs for monitoring and enforcement are also reduced as automated forecasting replaces part of the manual oversight currently required.

In total, for a major hydraulic node such as Castellarano Weir, preliminary estimations suggest potential **annual administrative savings** of **€15,000 to €20,000** solely from reducing redundant bureaucratic procedures.

Additionally, the Climate Service allows for pre-approved resilience strategies that eliminate the need for repeated derogation requests, and a more agile decision-making process, reducing delays in emergency responses.

Incentivizing Adoption through Regional Funding

To accelerate adoption, the Regional Government is considering direct financial incentives for the acquisition and deployment of the Climate Service by key stakeholders, such as the Irrigation Consortia and water utilities. These incentives focus on:

- Hardware and software acquisition – Funding the installation of hydrological monitoring stations to couple with the predictive modelling software and to pilot water management inside the resilience planning
- Data integration and real-time forecasting – this is more linked directly to the software implementation of the service

After discussion with the Regional government we have co-developed an example of hypothetical public funding of the Climate Service through Regional Programs. It should be noted that this does not constitute extraordinary funding, but rather a reallocation of already planned financial resources for agriculture, directing them towards the Climate Service as one of the eligible measures within existing investment programs. This ensures that the service is financed within the current budget framework, without requiring additional public expenditure.

One possible channel for financing the acquisition and maintenance of the Climate Service is adapting an existing program under the *Programma di Sviluppo Rurale* – PSR ⁽¹⁾. This could provide one-time funding for the purchase, for example of five-year operational costs of the service, ensuring its full integration into regional water management frameworks.

Existing program currently supports investments in sustainable and resilient agricultural infrastructure, and its structure could be adapted to fund the Climate Service could be as follows:

Minimum eligible expenditure are **€10,000** in disadvantaged areas or **€20,000** in standard areas

Maximum funding per beneficiary per sector: **€1.5 million** (including hardware and software)

Grant coverage:

- 40% for standard beneficiaries
- 50% for young farmers and disadvantaged areas
- 60% for projects with significant environmental benefits (e.g., resilient orchards)

Applying this framework, the Climate Service could be positioned as an environmental resilience measure, allowing stakeholders to benefit from a **60% co-financing rate**. This would significantly lower the upfront investment cost for any uptaker such as Reclamation Consortia and multi-utility companies, facilitating widespread adoption.

Furthermore, given the administrative constraints associated with regional funding, financing could be allocated entirely in **Year 0**, covering:

- Hardware acquisition and installation costs.
- Software licensing and maintenance for five years.
- Initial user training and integration with existing platforms.

¹Rural Development Programme, co-financed by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development - EAFRD, under the Common Agricultural Policy - CAP

Optimizing the management of the Minimum Ecological Discharge and storage.

To further explore the potential of the Climate Service in enhancing water governance, we have also developed considerations with the Regional Government regarding its role in optimizing the management of the Minimum Ecological Discharge (Deflusso Minimo Vitale/Deflusso Ecologico - DMV/DE) and pre-emptive storage, particularly during and before-after the summer period. These discussions, which build upon exchanges with both the Regional Government and Irrigation Consortia altogether, focus on a more flexible and adaptive approach to DMV regulation, allowing for extended withdrawals during peak agricultural demand while ensuring ecological sustainability through compensatory releases in adjacent seasons. These aspects are detailed in the following section.

Optimizing Agricultural Water Management through the Climate Service

The Context: Water Pricing and Resource Management in Reclamation Consortia

The discussions with the Central Emilia Reclamation Consortium highlighted the complexity of water pricing and distribution mechanisms in irrigation systems. The Consortium does not charge a market price for water but applies a tributary contribution system, divided into a fixed fee and a variable fee.

The fixed fee accounts for 80-85% of the total costs and covers infrastructure maintenance, network management, and resource monitoring. The variable fee, which represents only 15-20% of the costs, is proportional to the water volumes withdrawn and depends on factors such as crop type, irrigation period, and local availability.

The comparison between the Po River Basin and the Secchia River Basin illustrates the different constraints affecting water users:

- Po River Basin: Water is available throughout the season, with a lower cost per cubic meter (around 0.03 €/m³) but a higher fixed fee due to extensive infrastructure and higher guaranteed availability.
- Secchia River Basin: Water is scarce and distributed in strict rotation schedules, leading to higher per-unit costs (3-4 times higher than Po) but lower fixed fees. During peak demand, supply is insufficient, and withdrawals are sometimes suspended due to low river flow.

The rigid structure of current water management policies limits flexibility, particularly in drought-prone areas. The Climate Service (CS) can improve forecasting accuracy, enabling better planning of withdrawals and releases to mitigate water scarcity during critical periods. However, effective integration requires a governance model that considers both operational and economic sustainability.

Many water management policies, such as Piani Territoriali Ambientali (PTA) and EU directives, often oversimplify the complexities of irrigation consortia. The assumption that reducing withdrawals lowers costs is misleading, as most costs in large-scale irrigation infrastructures are fixed, independent of water use. Similarly, the idea that only users should pay for water ignores the fact that a well-maintained irrigation network benefits all landowners, influencing land value and agricultural productivity. A more effective approach should focus on collective water management at the basin scale, rewarding district-wide efficiency rather than individual reductions. Water governance should also be assessed at the system level, ensuring that efficiency measures do not unintentionally increase overall losses.

By integrating the Climate Service into regional resilience plans, adaptive ecological flow management and forecast-driven decision-making can provide greater flexibility for agricultural users. This approach aligns

economic and environmental priorities, ensuring sustainable resource use while maintaining irrigation access during peak demand periods.

Enhancing Water Availability through Adaptive Ecological Flow Management

One possible way of applications of the Climate Service in agriculture is its potential to support a **more flexible and adaptive approach** to Deflusso Ecologico (DMV, Ecological Flow). The current system applies to two fixed seasonal values—summer and winter—which do not fully account for seasonal variations in water availability or the actual needs of agricultural users.

Introducing a **multi-level DMV**, supported by the forecast system to activate timely all required management measures such as storage, could improve water management by adjusting flow requirements to **match demand and availability** throughout the year. For example, in **July and August**, ecological flow requirements could be reduced from 1.49/1.59 m³/s to 1 m³/s at key control points such as Castellarano and Ponte Veggia, allowing for extended irrigation during peak demand. This reduction could be compensated by increased ecological flow releases in April and May, which currently follow winter levels but could be adjusted to rebalance the system. Flows in June and September would remain unchanged, ensuring stability across seasons.

This adjustment would create additional water availability for agriculture in the summer without altering the total annual flow balance. An approximate reduction of 0.5 m³/s reduction in ecological flow for 60 days in July and August would result in **2.6 million cubic meters of additional water**, which could be reallocated to agricultural users while maintaining overall environmental sustainability.

By integrating this approach into **regional resilience plans (PDRs)**, water distribution could be optimized based on climate forecasts.

The Role of the Climate Service in Governance and Operational Efficiency

For this adaptive model to be viable, it must be incorporated into existing water governance frameworks and validated through regional policies (the already mentioned PDRs). The Climate Service can facilitate this transition by **providing actionable forecasts**, improving decision-making, and enabling better coordination between ecological and agricultural water needs.

Through forecast-driven decision support, water withdrawals can be dynamically managed, **enhancing** chances that ecological flow requirements are respected while maximizing water use efficiency. The service can also **automate the process of preventive channels** filling, which is currently subject to additional costs and administrative procedures. By integrating this functionality into PDR protocols, reservoirs could be filled based on predictive models, eliminating the need for extraordinary approvals and reducing unnecessary operational costs (see also previous chapter description of the *Regional Government* expect gains).

A more adaptive water management strategy, supported by climate forecasting, would provide greater flexibility for agricultural users, at least key players like Consortia enabling them to **extend irrigation periods** in times of high demand while compensating with increased releases during other seasons. This approach **aligns agricultural and environmental priorities**, offering a sustainable solution to the challenges posed by climate variability and water scarcity.

Qualitative Estimation of Gains

To further assess the value of the Climate Service for agricultural water management, we apply a qualitative estimation of the benefits following the approach outlined in the I-CISK Guidelines for Value Chain Assessment

(see MS26, Assessment of downstream value chain, June 2024). Based on stakeholder consultations and previous analyses, the expected benefits can be estimated as follows:

Economic Gains: The Climate Service promotes efficiency in water allocation, reducing loss of water volumes, while increasing availability during peak irrigation periods. By improving planning and reducing the need for emergency measures, irrigation consortia and regional authorities can lower operational costs and optimize water use. Using the framework in Table 1, these gains align with a **MODERATE** rating, particularly in terms of avoided costs from reactive measures.

Environmental Gains: By supporting a more adaptive ecological flow strategy, the Climate Service balances agricultural withdrawals with environmental needs. This enhances ecosystem resilience by ensuring sufficient flow in critical periods, reducing extreme low-flow events that harm biodiversity. This dimension is rated **MODERATE** expecting a long-term sustainability impact.

Social Gains: Farmers and water users benefit from greater predictability and reduced competition for water during drought periods, increasing resilience in the agricultural sector and, linked to the previous benefit a more usable riverine ecosystem for citizens. Improved governance and stability in water availability contribute to regional economic stability. These gains align with a **LOW** classification in the assessment framework.

This qualitative estimation highlights that the Climate Service is able to provide tangible value in improving water governance, reducing administrative burdens, and ensuring a more sustainable and efficient use of water resources in Emilia-Romagna.

5.5 Fourth iteration: analysis beyond the defined boundaries

5.5.1 Market Segmentation

Defining the segments

The Climate Service co-developed in the Castellarano Living Lab is designed to support decision-making in the water sector, with a specific focus on **sub-seasonal to seasonal river discharge forecasts**. The service leverages both open data and regional calibration to offer localized, actionable insights.

Given its tailored nature and integration with existing planning tools (e.g. a Water management plan at various levels), the service targets a **B2G (Business-to-Government)** and **B2B (Business-to-Business)** mode.

The main market segments across Europe (the analysis has been tied to this geographical area for the moment) are identified as:

- **Regional Public Authorities** responsible for water resources planning and emergency response (e.g. regional governments, basin authorities)
- **Water Reclamation and Irrigation Consortia**, managing agricultural distribution and compliance with ecological flow regulations
- **Public and private water utilities**, managing urban and industrial supply under changing hydrological conditions
- **Hydropower operators**, interested in short-term forecasts to optimize production while respecting environmental constraints

- **Consulting and engineering firms** integrating forecasting products into climate adaptation projects (here the interest in minor interest due to potential competition)
- **Cross-border institutions** involved in river basin management (e.g. Po, Danube, the company GECOSistema taking care of the Lab has indeed experience in proposing similar services to such wider institution in other contexts such as flood mapping services)

These user segments across Europe are increasingly looking for decision-support tools that help them manage water under growing pressure from climate variability and regulatory complexity. This trend is reinforced by the EU Water Framework Directive (WFD), which promotes the use of such tools to enhance compliance, improve planning under drought and low-flow conditions, support the implementation of ecological flows, and foster adaptive water governance.²³ Moreover, recent EU-funded projects have demonstrated the role of forecasting systems in enabling proactive reservoir management, simplifying administrative procedures, and strengthening resilience in agriculture and water utilities.⁴⁵ Particularly tools shall be able to :

- Improve planning and decisions during droughts and low-flow periods
- Support legal compliance and reduce administrative burdens
- Enable adaptive governance (e.g. with modular ecological flow rules)
- Optimize water distribution and storage efficiency

Selecting target groups

Among these, the most attractive and likely reachable target groups, basing on the discussion and interviews in the Lab as well as the Company's (GECOSistema) judgment and own experience of over two decades of activity on the field have been identified in:

1. **Irrigation Consortia and Basin Authorities:** (Particularly in Southern and Eastern Europe These actors are often responsible for water allocation in drought-prone areas, where institutional capacity is high but forecasting capabilities are limited. The pressing need for better prediction tools and the compatibility with existing resilience planning frameworks (PDRs) make them ideal early adopters.
2. **Regional Governments and Environmental Agencies:** These entities oversee compliance with ecological flow requirements and emergency declarations. They would benefit from reduced bureaucracy and improved planning reliability, as demonstrated in the Emilia-Romagna use case.
3. **Hydropower Operators in mountain (e.g. Alpine and Apennine) Regions:** Forecasting tools can inform reservoir operations, optimizing energy output while ensuring compliance with minimum flow requirements.
4. **Multi-utility Companies operating in multiple sectors (water, energy, environment):** These actors can leverage the service to integrate forecasts into broader sustainability and risk management portfolios.

While various institutions (e.g., Copernicus CEMS, ECMWF, or academic providers) offer seasonal or sub-seasonal river discharge forecasts, these **services are typically generic, pan-European, and not locally calibrated**. They provide raw or semi-processed data products that require significant post-processing, making them less suitable for operational use by local or regional water managers without additional support or

² European Commission – Water Framework Directive: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/water/water-framework-directive_en

³ U Guidance Document on Ecological Flows (CIS No.31): [https://circabc.europa.eu/sd/a/4063d635-957b-4b6f-bfd4-b51b0acb2570/Guidance%20No%2031%20-%20Ecological%20flows%20\(final%20version\).pdf](https://circabc.europa.eu/sd/a/4063d635-957b-4b6f-bfd4-b51b0acb2570/Guidance%20No%2031%20-%20Ecological%20flows%20(final%20version).pdf)

⁴ MARCLAIMED Project – AI-powered tools for water scarcity: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101136799>

⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/869550?>

adaptation.

The Climate Service developed within the Italian Living Lab offers a distinctive advantage by being:

- Tailored to local hydrological and administrative contexts
- Integrated into existing decision-making protocols
- Co-designed with public authorities and consortia, ensuring usability and governance alignment

In the public sector, particularly among regional governments and irrigation consortia, there are potentially less operational competitors offering integrated, context-specific forecasting services. Most existing solutions are either research-based, lack spatial/temporal granularity, or are not actionable within public planning instruments.

Conversely, in the private sector, particularly among hydropower operators and large multi-utilities, there is a growing presence of proprietary in-house tools or private consultants offering forecasting capabilities ⁽⁶⁾. These actors may already use data streams from public services (e.g., Copernicus) combined with their internal models or investments in AI/forecasting infrastructure, making this segment more competitive and cost sensitive.

Therefore, C4 is rated relatively high (few competitors) for public and governance-linked user groups, and moderate to low for private-sector actors, where the market is more fragmented but also more commercially dynamic. This segmentation reflects both opportunity and differentiation potential in scaling the service across Europe.

Table 2: Group Attractiveness Scorecard – for the ITA LL prototyped CS.

I-CISK Services Component:	Climate Services for River discharge forecast					
Market Segment	Criteria					Total Score
	[C1] The customer group has a pressing need and is willing to act upon it.	[C2] Our offering can satisfy that need.	[C3] We can easily communicate/ access the customer group.	[C4] There are no known competitors addressing this need.	[C5] The customer group is substantial and potentially profitable.	
Irrigation Consortia & Basin Authorities	4	5	4	3	4	20

⁶ <https://waterjade.com/>

Market Segment	Criteria					Total Score
	[C1] The customer group has a pressing need and is willing to act upon it.	[C2] Our offering can satisfy that need.	[C3] We can easily communicate/ access the customer group.	[C4] There are no known competitors addressing this need.	[C5] The customer group is substantial and potentially profitable.	
Regional Governments & Environmental Agencies	5	5	4	4	4	22
Hydropower Operators	3	5	3	2	5	18
Multi-utility Companies	3	4	3	2	5	17

General Notes:

A rating of 1 denotes the statement is totally inaccurate, a rating of 5 denotes the statement is totally accurate.

As far as criterion C3 is concerned a rating of:

5 is attributed when the geographical and the core business attributes of the client group coincides with the Developer’s main business activities

3-4 is attributed when only one of the geographical or the core business attributes of the client group coincides with Developer’s main business activities

1-2 is attributed when none of the geographical and core business attributes of the client group coincides with Developer’s main business activities

As far as criterion C4, it is assumed that existing competitors have equal access to markets irrespective of the geographical attributes of the client group (Many if not the most competitors operate internationally). Therefore, the rating differentiates only on the basis of addressing the identified needs.

5.5.2 Market Analysis

Estimating the potential size of the target market

To substantiate the market analysis for the hydrological forecasting Climate Service developed in the Italian Living Lab, it is essential to provide reasonable figures regarding the number of potential institutional users across Europe. Below is an estimation of key target groups, supported by available sources:

1. Regional Water Authorities and Basin Organizations:

The European Union comprises numerous regional and local entities responsible for water management, including basin authorities and regional environmental agencies. While a precise count is challenging due to varying administrative structures across member states, institutions with strategic planning and regulatory mandates—such as River Basin Authorities, Regional Environmental Agencies, or competent water authorities in charge of implementing the Water Framework Directive (WFD) and approving ecological flows and water permits—are fewer in number.

Each EU member state typically has a limited number of **River Basin District Authorities**, often coordinated at the national level but managed regionally, along with a handful of **regional water or environmental agencies** with planning mandates (e.g., ARPAE in Emilia-Romagna or CHE in Spain). Governance structures vary across Europe, with centralized systems in some countries (e.g., Rijkswaterstaat in the Netherlands) and decentralized frameworks in others (e.g., Italy, France, Spain).

Based on this institutional landscape, a conservative estimate places the number of planning-level public authorities across Europe at approximately **100 to 150 entities**. This figure aligns with the number of **River Basin Districts (RBDs)** officially recognized under the EU **Water Framework Directive (WFD)**⁽⁷⁾, within which water governance is typically managed by one or more competent regional or sub-regional bodies⁽⁸⁾. Additional institutions, such as regional environmental agencies, further complement this governance framework, especially in decentralized systems. Collectively, these entities form a relatively small but strategically important market segment, directly engaged in water allocation, ecological flow regulation, and climate adaptation planning.

2. Irrigation Consortia and Associations:

Irrigation plays a significant role in European agriculture, particularly in southern regions. In 2016, the total agricultural area equipped for irrigation in the EU was 15.5 million hectares, with 10.2 million hectares actually irrigated. Countries like Spain and Italy reported the largest irrigable areas, with 3.6 million and 4.1 million hectares, respectively.

The European Union of Water Management Associations (EUWMA) represents over 8,600 individual organizations covering more than 50 million hectares, including Italy's **Consorzi di bonifica**, which are integral to the country's irrigation infrastructure.^{9 10 11}

While specific numbers of irrigation consortia are not detailed in the available sources, the extensive irrigated areas suggest a substantial number of such organizations. Given the scale of irrigation activities, it is plausible to estimate an order of magnitude of around **1,000** irrigation consortia and associations across Europe, dealing with water scarcity issues, particularly concentrated in Mediterranean countries such as Italy, Spain, France, and Greece.

3. Hydropower Operators:

Determining the exact number of hydropower operators in the European Union (EU) is challenging due to the

⁷https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/water/water-framework-directive_en

⁸<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/publications/state-of-water>

⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/European_Union_of_Water_Management_Associations?

¹⁰ https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2019/644216/EPRS_BRI%282019%29644216_EN.pdf?

¹¹ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Agri-environmental_indicator_-_irrigation

diverse ownership structures and varying scales of operations across member states. While comprehensive data specifying the number of operators is limited, insights can be drawn from the number of hydropower facilities and the structure of the industry.

According to the **European Environment Agency (EEA)**, there are numerous hydropower plants across Europe, categorized by size and capacity. The EEA provides data on existing, under-construction, and planned hydropower plants ⁽¹²⁾.

Additionally, the **Hydropower Europe Regional Profile** indicates that as of 2023, countries like Norway have a significant number of operational hydropower projects. For instance, Norway added 118 MW in installed capacity, bringing the total number of operating projects in the country to 1,330. This information suggests a substantial number of facilities across Europe, implying a large number of operators. More details can be found here ⁽¹³⁾.

Given that many operators manage multiple facilities, and considering the prevalence of both large-scale operators and numerous smaller entities, the estimate of over **1,000 hydropower** operators across the EU appears prudential. However, it is important to note that this figure is an approximation, as definitive data on the exact number of operators is not easily available in public domain sources.

4. Multi-Utility Companies:

Multi-utility companies that integrate water and energy services are expanding their sustainability and resilience portfolios, with a growing interest in data-driven solutions for risk reduction. While specific numbers are not detailed in the available sources, the presence of such companies across Europe indicates a notable market segment for Climate Service, despite the low scoring in the previous attractiveness analysis no further attempt to evaluate this specific market has been done as part of the present analysis.

Conclusion:

Based on the available data and reasonable estimations, the potential market for hydrological forecasting Climate Service includes:

- Approximately **100 to 150 regional water authorities and basin organisations**.
- Around **1,000 irrigation consortia and associations**, primarily in Mediterranean countries.
- Over **1,000 hydropower operators** across the EU.
- A significant number of multi-utility companies are involved in water and energy services, but no specific quantification has been carried on.

These estimations provide a foundation for assessing the market potential and strategizing the deployment of Climate Service across Europe.

Although the potential market across Europe includes several hundred relevant institutions, a more prudent and methodologically sound adoption forecast must account for the structural barriers to entry typical of the public sector. These include the slow pace of institutional procurement, varying degrees of digital readiness, the need for regulatory alignment, and budgetary planning cycles that often span multiple years. Additionally, the service is in a pre-operational phase and requires co-design with users, further slowing immediate uptake.

Therefore, assuming an initial market penetration rate of just 1–2% among the most eligible public and semi-public water management bodies—such as regional environmental agencies, basin authorities, and irrigation consortia—a more conservative and credible estimate would place the number of early adopters at **10 to 15 institutions by 2026**. These would likely be concentrated in countries and regions with active climate adaptation planning (e.g., Italy, Spain, France) and prior engagement in pilot initiatives like the I-CISK Living Labs. From this foundation, growth can accelerate in the following years through inter-institutional learning,

¹² <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/maps-and-charts/recorded-hydropower-plants-in-europe?>

¹³ <https://www.hydropower.org/region-profiles/europe>

inclusion in resilience plans, and policy reinforcement.

5.5.3 Analysing trends and responding to opportunities and threats

Goal of the product or service:	<i>To provide public and semi-public water managers with a localized, operational forecast tool to improve water allocation, reduce emergency measures, and ensure environmental compliance.</i>
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The Climate Service developed in the Italian Living Lab aims to address strategic needs in water management by offering high-resolution, locally adapted, and governance-compatible seasonal discharge forecasts. In this section, we apply a **SWOT** analysis framework to better understand how external trends and internal capabilities affect the service’s deployment potential.

Strengths

- Strong co-design with target users (regional authorities, consortia), ensuring relevance and institutional compatibility.
- Can be tailored to local hydrological contexts and embedded in existing planning instruments.
- Reduces administrative burden by pre-authorizing resilience actions.
- Combines technical forecasting capacity with user-centric governance applications.

Weaknesses

- Dependence on regional funding mechanisms for scaling and adoption, at least in the Lab developed case
- Limited in-house visibility outside pilot regions.
- Potential challenges in long-term maintenance and support in resource-constrained administrations.
- Requires training and institutional alignment to be used operationally.

Opportunities

- EU regulatory trends (WFD, Climate Adaptation Mission) support innovative like predictive and data-driven water governance.
- Increasing exposure to droughts and water conflicts increases urgency for tools that can enable fair and efficient allocation.
- Availability of rural development funds and resilience funds for adoption.
- Growing momentum for adaptive ecological flow management in Mediterranean countries.

Threats

- Fragmented governance across regions may delay coherent adoption strategies.
- Potential competition from large-scale providers offering generic, low-resolution services.
- Uncertainty in funding cycles or political turnover may disrupt service continuity.
- Risk of low uptake if not formally embedded in regulatory or planning obligations.

The Climate Service is indeed well positioned to respond to clear market demands in the European public water management landscape. Its added value lies in its operational usability, institutional co-creation, and alignment with emerging water governance frameworks. However, unlocking its full potential requires a

proactive strategy to navigate administrative fragmentation, funding constraints, and visibility challenges. The SWOT approach outlined above will be used to inform future steps in service refinement and market positioning.

5.5.4 Estimating the market growth rate

Estimating the future growth of the European market for climate services in the water management sector requires a careful balance between increasing institutional demand and persistent structural constraints. While the urgency for advanced planning tools—particularly those supporting drought management, water allocation, and ecological flow governance—is rising due to climate pressures and EU policy shifts, the diffusion of such services remains conditioned by limited administrative capacity, procurement inertia, and fragmented governance structures.

The **EU-funded MARCO project** (Market Research for a Climate Services Observatory) projected substantial potential for climate services across various sectors, including water, emphasizing the growing relevance of user-centric, operational forecasting tools by 2030. However, it also highlighted the immaturity of many local markets—particularly in southern Europe—and the challenges of scaling downstream services like tailored hydrological forecasts.¹⁴

Public institutions such as irrigation consortia, basin authorities, and regional agencies—the core target groups of the Italian Climate Service—often require additional incentives or regulatory mandates to adopt such tools. Funding constraints, administrative complexity, and the need for long-term institutional alignment suggest that uptake will likely follow a **gradual and segmented pathway**.⁽¹⁵⁾

Given this context, and focusing on the priority European market of public and semi-public water management bodies, a **moderate and conservative growth trajectory** is anticipated. Starting from an estimated **10–15 institutional adopters by 2026**, a **compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of approximately 7–10%** is plausible through 2030. This projection assumes:

- Continued support for climate adaptation and resilience through EU frameworks (e.g., WFD, EU Adaptation Mission, CAP Strategic Plans). (¹²)
- Availability of public financing (e.g., PSR, LIFE, national resilience funds) to co-finance acquisition and onboarding.
- A gradual learning curve, supported by successful demonstration pilots such as the Castellarano Living Lab, and institutional exchange.

In numerical terms, this trajectory could bring the number of active users to approximately and **60–80 in 5 years**, mainly concentrated in Mediterranean countries and in regions with existing resilience planning mandates.

In conclusion, the climate service market in the water governance sector is clearly **emerging**, but its growth is expected to be **incremental and policy-driven**, rather than exponential. Long-term scale-up will hinge on continued alignment with regulatory frameworks, proof of operational value, and integration into public investment strategies—rather than on pure market dynamics.

5.5.5 Competition and profitability

Competitor Identification Framework

Based on the Peteraf and Bergen Competitor Identification Framework, we have assessed a range of organizations and platforms that either directly or indirectly overlap with the value proposition of the Climate

¹⁴ <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/metadata/projects/market-research-for-a-climate-services-observatory>

¹⁵ https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/eu-adaptation-policy/sector-policies/water-management/index_html

Service developed in the Italian Living Lab. These competitors vary in terms of how well they address the same needs (market correspondence) and their technical capabilities (capability equivalence).

In the upper right quadrant (Quadrant I), where both needs and capabilities match, we identify actors such as **Tomorrow.io** ⁽¹⁶⁾, a leading provider of weather intelligence services that offers customized forecast solutions for operational decision-making. Similarly, **Meteomatics** ⁽¹⁷⁾ provides high-resolution weather APIs and tailored forecasting models, with use cases applicable to water utilities and public authorities. These platforms pose the most direct competition, especially in high-value markets seeking comprehensive forecasting services.

In the lower right quadrant (Quadrant II), where market needs correspond but capability equivalence is still emerging, we position players like **CropX**. ⁽¹⁸⁾, and similar platforms tailored more for on-farm management of the farm rather than basin-level governance or collective infrastructure planning. They support decision-making at the farm scale using IoT and agronomic models but do not offer modular ecological flow management or integration with public governance frameworks.

WaPOR ⁽¹⁹⁾, developed by FAO, also fits into this quadrant. Although it offers valuable satellite data for water productivity, it lacks predictive features and is primarily used for monitoring and scenario evaluation rather than adaptive planning and forecast.

In the upper left quadrant (Quadrant IV), **Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS)**,²⁰ and **ECMWF** ⁽²¹⁾ are positioned. These are foundational providers of climate and weather data and serve as enablers for many downstream applications. However, they require significant technical capacity to be operationally useful and do not provide decision-support interfaces directly targeting regional irrigation consortia or water authorities. Their capability is high, but the alignment with practical decision-making needs is less direct.

At the national or regional level, **ARPAE-SIMC** ⁽²²⁾ and the related **Open Data Portal of Emilia-Romagna** ⁸²³ are relevant. They are situated closer to Quadrant III, as they provide important observational data and some forecasts, but their services are not designed to meet the adaptive, forecast-based governance needs addressed by the Climate Service, or to compete with pay for services; however they could be in principle extended to offer for free the forecast service the CS provides, weather is may act as a competitor or a potential client. It is questionable at this stage of analysis.

Finally, a notable player is **Waterjade**⁽²⁴⁾, a company based in Italy offering hydrological forecasting and decision support tools. Waterjade targets utilities and public authorities with a focus on water availability forecasting and drought management. Its offering shares several functional goals with the Climate Service but seems to focus more on early warning systems than on institutional integration with resilience plans or modular ecological flow policies. Given its technical robustness and growing presence in the Italian market, Waterjade could be considered a vertical differentiator or even a potential collaborator, depending on future developments.

This landscape confirms that while there are strong competitors in adjacent spaces, the specific combination of functionalities, user engagement mechanisms, and institutional alignment proposed by the Climate Service has its own value proposition, especially in the context of modular ecological flow management and integration into resilience governance protocols.

¹⁶ <https://www.tomorrow.io/>

¹⁷ <https://www.meteomatics.com/>

¹⁸ <https://cropx.com/>

¹⁹ https://wapor.apps.fao.org/home/WAPOR_2/1

²⁰ <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/>

²¹ <https://www.ecmwf.int/>

²² <https://www.arpae.it/sim/>

²³ <https://dati.emilia-romagna.it/>

²⁴ <https://waterjade.com/>

Here follows the list and the graphic representation of the analysed competitors:

C1 – Tomorrow.io: Weather intelligence platform for operational decision-making.

C2 – Meteomatics: High-resolution weather API and forecasting services.

C3 – CropX: Soil and agronomic decision-support system focused on farm-level applications.

C4 – WaPOR (FAO): Water productivity monitoring platform based on satellite data.

C5 – Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS): EU’s main climate data access infrastructure.

C6 – ECMWF: European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts.

C7 – ARPAE-SIMC: Regional meteorological and hydrological service in Emilia-Romagna.

C8 – Dati Emilia-Romagna (Open Data Portal): Regional open data portal for environmental and weather data.

C9 – Waterjade: Decision support and hydrological forecasting for utilities and public entities.

Figure 20: Competitor Identification Framework estimated for the ITA LL prototyped CS.

Competitive Strength Heatmap

Following the identification and classification of competitors in previous section, a comparative analysis of their capabilities has been conducted using the Competitive Strength Grid adapted from what has been proposed in (Asker and McLoughlin,2010). This framework evaluates how well each competitor performs across seven key strategic dimensions relevant to the Climate Service developed in the Italian Living Lab.

The dimensions identified include: **forecasting accuracy, operational usability, integration with governance processes (e.g. resilience planning), support for modular ecological flow management, service customizability, adoption potential among institutional users, and interoperability with hydrological infrastructure.**

The results are visualized in a heatmap, which shows that the Climate Service developed in the Italian Living Lab performs well across all dimensions, especially in those where public governance and policy alignment are critical—namely, Governance Integration, Ecological Flow Support, and Institutional Adoption.

Among commercial competitors, Tomorrow.io and Meteomatics may in principle offer forecasting performance and usability but lack deep integration with water governance frameworks or ecological flow policy mechanisms. Their services are largely built for private-sector or operational users, rather than institutional planning bodies.

Waterjade emerges as a particularly relevant player in this landscape. It exploits advanced technologies to boost performances of the forecast, and shows moderate strength in Governance Integration, targeting utilities and public authorities with drought forecasting and water availability models. However, it currently focuses more on short term management rather than medium to long term resilience planning or DE management.

On the other end of the spectrum, organizations such as ARPAE-SIMC, Copernicus CDS, and ECMWF provide high-quality monitoring or high level data services, but with limited usability for direct operational planning at the local level. These tools lack customizable interfaces and institutional integration, which are central to the Italian Climate Service offering.

Platforms like **CropX** and **WaPOR** support farm-level management and water productivity analysis but do not include predictive components or basin-level governance tools. Their utility for irrigation consortia and public water managers is therefore limited.

The analysis confirms that, despite some partial overlaps, **no single competitor** currently combines forecasting, ecological flow support, and integration with public water governance to the same extent as the Climate Service developed under I-CISK. This represents a clear strategic niche and a significant differentiating advantage.

The visual representation of the derived Competitive Strength Grid is proposed hereafter:

Figure 21 – Competitive Strength Heatmap for the ITA LL prototyped CS.

Cost-Volume-Profit Analysis

The Cost-Volume-Profit (CVP) analysis provides a forecast of how the Climate Service (CS) can become

financially sustainable and investment-worthy within a public-sector deployment framework. The model estimates profitability based on revised unit costs, updated subscription fees, and a realistic market penetration scenario focused on regional and basin-level water authorities.

Service Revenue Model

The Climate Service developed in the Italian Living Lab is structured as a **subscription-based solution targeting institutional and semi-public users**, such as irrigation consortia, basin authorities, and regional environmental agencies. These organizations typically serve multiple downstream users—such as farmers or local utilities—and are therefore well-positioned to invest in shared infrastructure and forecasting services that generate value for wider stakeholder groups. Their public-service mandate and role in regional water governance frameworks make them suitable adopters of tools that enhance both operational planning and compliance.

The pricing model combines an **initial customization and onboarding fee** with a **recurring annual license**, structured to balance affordability with sustainability. New clients pay **€20,000 in the first year**, covering site-specific data integration, system configuration, and onboarding. From year two, the **annual license fee is set at €8,000**, including data updates, system maintenance, and ongoing user support.

Crucially, these figures are not arbitrary: they reflect a **qualitative assessment of value co-developed with stakeholders** during bilateral interviews and workshops in the Italian case study. Discussions with key actors such as the **Emilia Centrale Irrigation Consortium** and **regional representatives** confirmed that this level of investment is **both realistic and justifiable**, especially when considering the added value of the service in reducing administrative burdens, supporting modular ecological flow planning, and enabling cost-effective drought preparedness. These benefits were explicitly recognized in the stakeholder validation exercises and value co-assessment phases.

Furthermore, the pricing aligns with real and well-known **funding schemes already available** to these institutions—such as CAP/PSR measures, LIFE projects, and national or regional resilience budgets—making the Climate Service not only cost-effective but also **financially accessible**. It is designed to support high-value, tailored deployments at basin level, leveraging institutional capacity while reducing the cost of inaction.

Cost Structure

The Climate Service developed in the Italian Living Lab follows a hybrid cost model, combining one-time setup investments with recurring operational expenses. This structure is designed to foster both scalability and affordability for public-sector users such as basin authorities, irrigation consortia, and regional agencies. The cost figures presented here are based on industrial benchmarks from Italian SMEs with experience in delivering cloud-based environmental services.

The cost breakdown is as follows:

Table 3: cost breakdown structure for the ITA prototyped CS

Component	Type	Unit Cost (€)
Customization on user data/context	Fixed (Yr1)	€4,000 per user
Training, onboarding and adaptation	Fixed (Yr1)	€1,000 per user
Hosting, data provision, platform updates	Variable	€2,000/year per user
Technical support and helpdesk	Variable	€1,500/year per user
Outreach, marketing, regional coordination	Fixed	€25,000 (5-year spread)
Development and modelling upgrades	Fixed	€25,000 (5-year spread)

Total fixed costs are projected at **€50,000** over five years, covering the initial development, stakeholder engagement, ongoing marketing activities, and periodic updates to the hydrological and forecasting modules.

Per-user onboarding in **Year 1** amounts to **€5,000** (€4,000 for customization and €1,000 for training and setup), ensuring full adaptation of the service to local data systems, workflows, and institutional governance contexts. From **Year 2** onward, the **annual operating cost per user** is **€3,500**, covering cloud hosting, continuous data integration, platform updates, and technical support.

This cost configuration supports high-quality service delivery while keeping the financial barrier to adoption low for institutional clients. Moreover, the model assumes that the service is provided by an SME that already has baseline cloud infrastructure and qualified staff in place, allowing operational synergies and efficient cost management across a broader portfolio of services.

The cost-revenue summary table has been revised accordingly:

Table 4: Revenue projections for the ITA LL prototyped CS.

Year	Users	Revenue (€)	Variable Costs (€)	Fixed Costs (€)	Net Profit (€)
2026	5	100,000	17,500	10,000	72,500
2027	10	80,000	35,000	10,000	35,000
2028	15	120,000	52,500	10,000	57,500
2029	20	160,000	70,000	10,000	80,000
2030	25	200,000	87,500	10,000	102,500

The projections show a **cumulative net profit of approximately €400,000 over five years**, with **break-even reached in Year 1**. The service maintains an **average gross margin above 56%** from the second year onward, a result made possible by the low marginal cost structure and predictable subscription-based revenue.

From a strategic perspective, the model confirms that this Climate Service—while designed for public-sector applications—offers a **viable and attractive commercial opportunity for SMEs**. It is especially well suited as a **complementary product in the portfolio of a small-sized company** already active in climate, water, or digital governance solutions. The assumption of pre-existing internal capacity (staff, infrastructure) further improves its financial sustainability and return on investment.

This configuration also aligns with public funding mechanisms (PSR, LIFE, CAP, regional resilience budgets), making it easier for institutional users to procure and maintain the service without relying on extraordinary resources.

Overall, the Climate Service is positioned as a **scalable, policy-aligned, and economically viable tool**, capable of integrating into modern water governance and environmental management frameworks across Europe.

Assessment of risks

To assess the likelihood of success or failure of the Climate Service developed in the Italian Living Lab, we applied the innovation risk matrix developed by George S. Day (2007)⁽²⁵⁾, which evaluates ventures based on their proximity to existing product capabilities and market knowledge. The assumption underlying the matrix is that the more distant the new venture is from a company's core competencies and familiar markets, the higher the risk of failure.

The risk assessment was conducted through two lenses:

25

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/5568092_Is_it_real_Can_we_win_Is_it_worth_doing_Managing_risk_and_reward_in_an_innovation_portfolio

- The **degree of familiarity with the intended market** (Table 5)
- The **closeness of the proposed service to existing capabilities and assets** (Table 6)

In Table 5, most scores fall between 1 and 3, suggesting a moderate degree of familiarity with the intended market. Although some aspects such as customer relationships and branding are still emerging, others—such as understanding of public institutional behaviour and decision processes—score reasonably well thanks to the co-creation and engagement activities conducted within the Living Lab. These institutions (e.g., irrigation consortia, basin authorities) are already known stakeholders, and their needs have been explored and validated during the service development process. However, the lack of structured commercial relationships and institutional procurement experience explains the cautious scoring.

In Table 6, the product/service analysis yields a total score of 10 out of a possible 30, reflecting a relatively high alignment with existing technical and scientific competences. The service leverages hydrological modelling, seasonal forecasting, and web-based delivery—domains where the developer (a typical SME in this space) already has significant experience. The relatively low scores in intellectual property and service customization reflect the tailored nature of the product and its dependency on public co-financing rather than proprietary advantage.

Table 5: Assessment of the intended market. Source: (Day 2007), adapted to the ITA LL prototyped CS.

Intended Market	...be the same as in our present market	...partially overlap with our present market	...be entirely different from our present market or are unknown	Score
Customer's behaviour and decision-making processes will...		3		3
Our distribution and sales activities will...		3		3
The competitive set (incumbents or potential entrants) will...		3		3
Our brand promise is...	1			1
Our current customer relationships are...	1			1
Our knowledge of competitors' behaviour and intentions is...		3		3
TOTAL (X-axis coordinate)				14

Table 6: Assessment of the product or service. Source: (Day 2007), adapted to the ITA LL prototyped CS.

Product or Service	...is fully applicable	...will require significant adaptation	...is not applicable	Score
Our current development capability...	1			1
Our technology competency...	1			1
Our intellectual property protection...		3		3
The required knowledge and science bases...	1			1

The necessary product/service functions...			3				3
The expected quality standards...	1						1
TOTAL (Y-axis coordinate)							10

The coordinates (x=14, y=10) place the Climate Service within the lower-left area of Day’s matrix (see Figure 22), corresponding to a **probability of failure in the range of 25–40%**. This risk level is consistent with innovations that are **adjacent to current offerings and markets**: novel enough to require investment and adaptation, yet close enough to existing skills, tools, and clients to mitigate major risk factors.

Figure 22: Risk matrix. Source: (Day 2007), for the ITA prototyped CS.

In conclusion, the Climate Service exhibits a **moderate innovation risk profile**, appropriate for public-private ventures in the climate adaptation space. The co-design process, regulatory alignment, and compatibility with existing tools significantly lower the risk of failure, making the service a strategically sound candidate for early-stage scaling and targeted investment.

6 Business model storyline for the Budapest Living Lab (Hungary)

6.1 Background and context

The Budapest LL is located in the Erzsébetváros district, an inner-city area of Budapest (the capital and most populous city of Hungary). The area is densely constructed with many protected-heritage buildings mostly from the late 19th and early 20th centuries.

This district has a low percentage of green spaces, with a high density of buildings, and therefore is particularly exposed to heat waves, which are already causing issues for a range of sectors in the city. The focus of the Living Lab is on urban heat islands in the tourism and public health sectors.

The CS developed is an Urban Heat Planning Service with two specific tools:

- Time-series analysis: Utilizing orthophotos as a high-resolution baseline for time-series analysis of thermal data. This method allows for tracking changes in urban heat over time with a clear reference to the physical changes in the urban landscape.
- Energy balance modelling with detailed surface information: Applying energy balance models that use detailed surface information from orthophotos, combined with thermal data, to interpret urban heat dynamics more accurately (Figure 23).

Figure 23: Urban heat map CS, Erzsébetváros district, Budapest.

6.2 First iteration: Defining boundaries of analysis

The service of Budapest LL aims to address the current limitations of heat data collection and processing in an integrated manner, specifically:

- **Data integration:** by combining drone thermal imagery with manual temperature measurements, we aim to create a detailed, spatially and temporally variable picture.
- **Dynamic updating:** using drone thermal imagery to downscale satellite imagery, the heat map will be able to be updated with satellite and microclimate model data in the future. This will make the service more flexible to provide real-time or near real-time information.
- **Problem solving:** The service aims to provide an advanced solution to the shortcomings of current data collection methods, which have limited coverage and are static in time, to monitor heat, heat island phenomena more accurately.

This integration allows for the creation of a high-resolution, dynamically updatable heatmap by incorporating data from satellite observations and microclimate models. Consequently, the temporal scope of the service is broadened, enabling continuous updates rather than relying solely on static, isolated measurements. In addition to the integration above, the service is further augmented by an AI-driven heat prediction component. A convolutional neural network (CNN) was trained using local heat data to generate a heat prediction map. However, the current approach has not yet achieved the desired accuracy, indicating that further experiments with AI techniques are required to refine the prediction model.

Geographical and Sectoral Focus

The analysis is primarily concentrated on the Terézváros (6) and Erzsébetváros (7) districts of Budapest. These areas have been chosen not only because they are prominent tourist attractions—making tourism a key sector—but also due to their significant social dimensions. Both districts host numerous kindergartens, elderly care centres, and schools, emphasizing the importance of addressing social sector needs alongside tourism

Targeted Users

The service is designed with a user-focused, bottom-up approach. The primary beneficiaries include:

- **Tourists:** Visitors will benefit from accurate, timely microclimate information that enhances their overall experience.
- **Local Residents and Institutions:** Community members, as well as educational and care facilities, can utilize the data to improve daily operations and environmental awareness.
- **City Management and Decision-Makers:** Authorities can leverage the high-resolution, integrated data for urban planning and infrastructure development.

6.3 Second iteration: Understanding the value chain

The climate service developed in the Budapest LL offers a comprehensive, integrated solution that leverages multiple data sources—drone-based thermal imaging, manual temperature measurements, citizen science contributions, and satellite downscaling—combined with advanced AI techniques. This innovative approach is designed to deliver accurate, highly localized (street- or block-level) heat/microclimate data and actionable knowledge for informed decision-making. The value proposition of the service is built on the following key elements:

1. **Localised Microclimate information:** Accurate, localised info at street/block level.
2. **AI-based Forecasting:** CNN heat prediction and segmentation

3. **Scalable Solution:** Multi-source data adapts to urban needs
4. **Targeted Users:** Tourism, social sector, city management

The service's value chain can be divided into four main stages which together transform raw data into actionable insights for informed decision-making across various sectors, as presented below and summarised in Figure 24.

Tier 1 (Data Collection and Preparation) focuses on gathering inputs from drone-based thermal imaging, manual temperature measurements, and citizen science contributions. In this stage, the collected data undergo initial validation checks, standardization, and georeferencing to ensure consistency and quality. By involving local residents and volunteers in the measurement process, the service achieves more granular coverage—often at street or block level—forming a robust foundation for detailed microclimate analysis. Key Stakeholders:

- Drone Operators: Responsible for collecting high-resolution thermal imagery.
- Manual Data Collectors: Professionals or trained personnel conducting in-situ measurements with thermometers or handheld thermal cameras.
- Citizen Scientists: Local residents and volunteers who contribute data (e.g., temperature readings) via the open-source citizen science tool.
- Satellite Data Providers: Entities or agencies offering satellite imagery and baseline remote-sensing data (e.g. Copernicus, scientific institutes etc).

Value creation: Rich, high-quality dataset, localization of data, citizen engagement

Tier 2 (Data Integration and Modelling) involves merging and refining the validated datasets. This includes downscaling satellite imagery using high-resolution drone data, aligning different data sources for consistency, and developing advanced models—such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs)—to predict thermal conditions. Image segmentation techniques (e.g., separating streets, buildings, and vehicles) and classification of roof types and surfaces further enhance model accuracy by enabling more precise interpretations. As a result, this tier produces coherent, high-resolution microclimate and heat maps that highlight localized temperature patterns and potential hotspots. Key Stakeholders:

- Data scientists and AI specialists: Experts who clean, merge, and analyse the data while refining AI models.
- Climate modelers and researchers: Professionals developing or adapting microclimate models to local conditions.
- Specialists in spatial data processing, satellite downscaling, and geospatial analytics.

Value creation: Transformation of raw data into actionable Insights, high-resolution predictive service, scalability and adaptability.

Tier 3 (Service Delivery and Use) focuses on disseminating these heat maps, forecasts, and decision-support outputs to diverse end-users, including municipal authorities, tourism stakeholders, and social institutions (e.g., schools and elderly care centres). These stakeholders leverage the localized insights to implement targeted interventions—such as optimizing cooling strategies, adjusting urban development plans, or issuing timely public advisories—to mitigate heat-related risks. By providing tangible, location-specific information, the service fosters urban resilience, supports public health initiatives, and improves resource allocation, ultimately delivering significant socio-economic and environmental benefits. Key Stakeholders:

- City Management and Municipal Authorities: Responsible for urban planning, climate adaptation, and infrastructure upgrades.
- Tourism Boards and Businesses: Utilize heat/microclimate information to improve visitor experiences and safety.
- Social Institutions (Schools, Care Centres, Hospitals): Implement measures to protect vulnerable populations using localized climate data.
- Residents and Community Groups: Benefit from publicly available insights to adapt daily activities or advocate for environmental improvements.

Value creation: Location-specific, decision-ready information that improves urban planning, protects vulnerable groups and boosts city resilience. Actionable, hyper-local insights drive cost-effective cooling measures. Story-telling visualisations (before–after, “what-if” scenarios) help engage citizens

Tier 4 (Citizens, society and expansion to other Economic Sectors): The wider “citizens, society and the environment”, are the end beneficiaries of the climatic service. Better services support urban development, better environmental conditions and citizen wellbeing. Energy providers may use temperature forecasts to optimize grid management and reduce peak loads; insurance companies can refine risk assessment models for heat-related claims; and real estate developers can integrate microclimate insights into sustainable building design and site selection.

Figure 24: Understanding of the proposed value chain for the Climate Services developed in the Budapest Living Lab (Hungary).

6.4 Third iteration: analyse the benefits

In the third iteration, the goal is to examine the potential benefits—especially economic ones—arising from the service and, where possible, to quantify them.

The Budapest Living Lab's climate service offers a forward-looking solution to urban heat-related challenges through a highly localized, data-driven, and user-focused approach. By integrating drone-based thermal imagery, manual temperature measurements, citizen science contributions, and satellite downscaling, the service delivers accurate, high-resolution microclimate data and forecasts. These services offer a range of social and economic benefits that may not be directly expressed in monetary terms. These benefits include improving public health (e.g., reducing heat-related illnesses), enhancing tourist comfort (potentially boosting local business revenues), and supporting more efficient urban infrastructure management (for example, lower cooling costs in heatwaves).

The monetization of the CS added value may be difficult, in terms of estimating the leveraging effect which these services may have on speed of implementation and spatial accuracy for interventions against urban heat challenges. An estimation of the value of the service can be drawn from an estimation of the potential economic benefits from interventions that can be leveraged by the developed CS. This leveraging effect can be identified in (a) the spatial accuracy of information, (b) the quality of data and (c) the fact that the proposed CS can act as a catalyst to accelerate the implementation of appropriate interventions.

Hence, an economic evaluation of interventions that could be supported by the developed CS was conducted instead, using a direct cost (avoided cost) approach, focusing on scalable urban cooling strategies such as high-albedo roof coatings, reflective pavements, and green infrastructure. Spatial and thermal data from two central Budapest districts (Terézváros and Erzsébetváros) informed the calculation of eligible surface areas and associated temperature reductions. Details are given in Annex A ("Assessments on Value estimation from the Budapest LL") of the present deliverable. Results show the following:

- Maximum surface temperature reduction at street level:
 - District 6: 2.39°C
 - District 7: 1.52°C
- Maximum surface temperature reduction from roof coatings:
 - District 6: 1.71°C
 - District 7: 0.94°C (*Note: For individual buildings, this reduction could reach 3–5°C, resulting in perceptible improvements in thermal comfort.*)

Using these inputs, a Net Present Value (NPV) analysis was conducted for District 7, based on a total treatment area of 1,634,784 m² and an assumed coating cost of €10/m². The lifespan of the intervention was set to 10 years, with 50% reapplication costs at Year 10 and Year 20. An annual benefit of €2 million was used to reflect energy savings, reduced cooling loads, and improved infrastructure performance.

Even without including mortality impacts, the current model yields a positive NPV of approximately €9 million over 30 years for district 7 of Budapest, demonstrating financial viability under conservative assumptions. When potential health co-benefits are included, the intervention becomes not only economically advantageous but socially and ethically compelling.

6.5 Fourth iteration: analysis beyond the defined boundaries

6.5.1 Primary market segment identification

KER* Identifier	Expected TRL	Time to Exploit	Description
Integrated urban heat visualization service	6–7	<1 year	An urban heat climate service that integrates static drone-based thermal maps, a web-based interactive GIS platform, and real-time sensor dashboards. It enables identification, monitoring, and communication of urban heat exposure through high-resolution georeferenced maps, spatial data layers (e.g., LST, OSM), future climate scenarios, and contextual statistics. Supports data-driven decision-making, public awareness, and adaptive planning through before–after comparisons and scenario evaluations.
CityZcan (citizen science) monitoring dashboard and IoT sensor box	6	<1 year	A real-time dashboard powered by CityZcan IoT sensor boxes that measure air temperature, humidity, PM2.5, and capture infrared thermal images. Designed to engage citizens in data collection and raise awareness during heatwaves, the system provides live microclimate updates, color-coded alerts, and integrates with municipal dashboards. It enhances public accessibility and supports health advisories by visualizing real-time heat and air quality risks across the city.
Urban heat data analytics and vulnerability mapping toolkit	5–6	1–2 years	A combined toolkit for analysing urban heat patterns and identifying vulnerable neighbourhoods. It includes script-based processing of drone thermal imagery for surface classification and temperature profiling, and a Heat Vulnerability Index (HVI) that integrates thermal, socioeconomic, and health data. The toolkit supports planning and evaluation of cooling interventions, public health risk assessment, and visual communication through statistical graphs, segmentation masks, and choropleth maps. Further development depends on access to detailed demographic and health data.

KER* Identifier	Expected TRL	Time to Exploit	Description
Urban heat awareness and gamification toolkit	6	<1 year	A multi-format awareness and engagement toolkit designed to promote understanding and behavioural adaptation to extreme heat and climate change. It includes educational videos, a public roll-up banner, a short documentary film, visuals for children (e.g., puzzle), and a serious game in the form of a card-based gamification toolkit. The game explores drivers of adaptation behaviour and helps players grasp climate service concepts through interactive learning. Tailored to diverse audiences—including citizens, students, and community groups—this toolkit supports climate literacy and participatory engagement.

** Key Exploitable Results*

In the current phase of development of the Budapest Living Lab (LL) the Budapest districts of Terézváros (VI) and Erzsébetváros (VII) are targeted as the primary market segment for the urban heat visualization climate service. The broader national or European scale as a relevant market segment is not considered at this point, although some elements of the service (e.g., the gamification tool) could be useful at a European level. Furthermore, the aim is to upscale the service across the entire city of Budapest as a next step.

This decision is based on the fact that the service was co-designed and tested in close cooperation with identified local stakeholders within the LL. These include:

- Municipal authorities and urban planners of District VI and VII
- Citizen associations engaged in climate adaptation dialogues
- Educational institutions and community partners involved in awareness-raising

These actors have shown direct interest in adopting elements of the climate service – particularly the static thermal maps, real-time dashboards, and visual communication tools – as part of their urban adaptation, communication, and participatory planning strategies. Given this close connection and contextual integration, it is logical to treat the LL as a well-defined and realistic primary application environment.

At the same time, the maturity level of the service is heterogeneous: while some components (e.g., thermal drone mapping and real-time dashboards) are near operational (TRL 6–7), others (e.g., Heat Vulnerability Index) require additional data integration and validation. This also limits the feasibility of immediate scaling beyond the local context.

6.5.2 Implications for Market Analysis

Given that the primary market segment is limited to the local LL and a broader market opportunity has not yet been validated, we do not consider it meaningful to proceed with a full market analysis at this stage.

The climate service, in its current form, is not yet positioned as a market-ready product intended for commercialisation. Its value lies primarily in capacity-building, policy support, and participatory learning, not in generating profit or penetrating a competitive marketplace.

6.5.3 Open Source Strategy and Future Potential

Throughout the design and development of the service, an open source strategy has been applied. This has

created and documented reusable software components (e.g., thermal image analysis scripts, dashboard prototypes), and third-party source codes have been shared on the public platforms of the project.

This strategy serves a dual purpose:

1. It enables community involvement in the further development of the toolset, creating opportunities for local stakeholders, civic tech communities, and academic partners to adapt or extend the tools for their own needs.
2. It lays the foundation for potential business opportunities to emerge in the future, through collaborative development models, technology transfer, or shared service provision frameworks that might arise organically from active co-creation ecosystems.

7 Business model storyline for the Crete Island Living Lab (Greece)

7.1 Background and context

The CS that has been co-developed in the Crete LL (Greece) addresses climatic challenges in the Tourism sector beyond the typical approach of the touristic services sector. Under the frame of a multi-sectoral approach, the LL has been formed by a combination of stakeholders who represent needs and challenges from cross-cutting sectors, including the tourism, water management, transportation infrastructure (roads, ports) and energy sectors, ensuring that synergies and trade-offs are appropriately considered in the development of the CS.

To address tourist sector needs, seasonal forecasting of extreme heat and precipitation as well as aesthetic indicators for outdoor activities and energy needs have been integrated, under a comprehensive web-GIS tool which provides the necessary information on spatial distribution (maps) as well as time-evolution graphs (see Figure 25).

To address water allocation needs, seasonal forecasting of river discharge and a tailored wet-season indicator (wet season: a 4-month period, from November to February) have been integrated. The service is based on providing a forecast for the coming (next year) wet period, from as early as March or April (8 months ahead). Since seasonal forecasts are available for six (6) months ahead, the service is based on a combination of data to produce the forecast. More specifically, for the months where no seasonal forecast is yet available for the next wet period, historical climate is used to produce an estimate. When seasonal forecasting data becomes available, they are gradually incorporated in the forecast, replacing the historical-data-based forecast, month by month until the whole wet period is covered by seasonal forecast data. The climate service addresses the needs of the water managers for a yearly decision on water allocation which is taken around April and is re-assessed at about September. A screen-shot of the service is given in Figure 26.

Similar to the above, to support transportation infrastructure, a landslide dynamic instability index was developed and port management related wind indicators were produced and integrated under a seasonal forecasting time-scale. Further, the majority of the above information was provided also under a climate projection, end-of-century scale

Figure 25: Screen-shot of the I-CISK CS developed for the Touristic Sector in the island of Crete under a multisectoral approach towards the support of the tourism sector – seasonal forecasting of extreme heat and precipitation as well as aesthetic indicators for outdoor activities and energy needs.

Figure 26: Screen-shot of the I-CISK CS developed for the Water Managers on the island of Crete under a multisectoral approach towards the support of the tourism sector – Wet period total volume: current forecast and history of forecasting.

7.2 First iteration: Defining boundaries of analysis

At this stage, the boundaries of the analysis for the use case are clearly set. These refer to:

- ❖ The geographical and sectoral focus
- ❖ The targeted users of the developed service
- ❖ The targeted problems the proposed service aim to solve
- ❖ The current practices in place and the need for having an advanced solution to address these problems

The user-focused approach (bottom-up approach) is described in the following for the main sector that these services address as part of the multisectoral approach towards the tourism sector, leading to the 1st iteration step of the VoI assessment (estimation of the value proposition).

Water management sector - Potamon (Amari) dam and reservoir

Location: Potamon dam reservoir is located in the central part of Crete Island (see Figure 27), about 25 km south-east of the town of Rethymno. An earth-fill dam of 55 m height creates an artificial reservoir with volume of 22.5 hm³ and surface area of 1.6 km². The dam serves multiple uses, currently addressing agricultural needs and very soon to be used as a drinking water source for the town of Rethymno, as well as for energy production purposes. Further, the reservoir is a major wetland in the area and is protected under the NATURA 2000 convention as a habitat protection area (SCI), while a significant number of different bird species have already established or use the area as a migration route.

Figure 27: Potamon (Amari) dam reservoir (photo by Organization for the Development of Crete – OAK).

End User(s): The Water Management Operator, Organisation for the Development of Crete (OAK), is a governmental organization with responsibilities, among others, to support the development of the countryside through projects and Community Initiatives with the aim to contribute to the development of the region of Crete. Regarding the water sector, OAK is responsible for the planning, design, construction, operation, management and supervision of Hydraulic Projects (dams, reservoirs and water treatment plants). The Organisation manages three large Dams in Crete (Aposelemis Dam with a capacity of 27.1 million cubic meters in Heraklion, Potamon Dam of 22.5 million cubic meters in Rethymno and Valsamiotis Dam of 6 million cubic meters in Rethymno), Agios Georgios Reservoir with a capacity of 2.15 million cubic metres in the Lassithi Plateau, reservoirs throughout Crete with a total capacity of 230,000 cubic metres and two water treatment plants (in Drama and Heraklion).

Challenge: Water management in a large Mediterranean island is a challenge due to climate characteristics and precipitation patterns in the greater region. Adding pressures of climate change and a thriving touristic sector, the allocation of water among private (agriculture) and public (drinking water) users, a more than doubling of the population during the summer (and dry) period of the year, environmental uses and storage needs becomes a struggle. Consecutive dry years and droughts act as added pressures while extreme weather events (heavy precipitation and flood) further complicate the management of reservoirs to act partly also as flood retention constructions.

Current practices in place (AS-IS Scenario): OAK documents climate patterns and keeps records of meteorological gauging stations. The organisation also, conducts or procures studies regarding management and development of the hydraulic works which it manages or plans to construct. With a high educational profile among its staff, OAK is an organization informed of recent developments on climate data, has in its availability various studies specifically addressing climate change impacts on the island and the infrastructures under OAK's responsibility and has piloted in the workflow some examples of state-of-the-art decision support tools. Still, decisions on seasonal and annual aspects of water management are taken based on past experience, and through analysis of historic meteorological records and weather forecasts.

Solution (User Requirements)

ID	User requirements		
	As a <ROLE>	I would like to <GOAL>	to <BENEFIT>
GR1	As a water managerI would like to estimate the surface water availability for the upcoming wet period (November to February) in Spring (March or April)...	...to decide upon the initial distribution of water permits among different water users (e.g., farmers, municipalities).
GR2	As a water managerI would like to have regular (monthly) updates of the forecasted surface water availability for the upcoming wet periodto decide if an adjustment of water permits is required.
GR3	As a water managerI would like to estimate the surface water availability for the upcoming wet period (November to February) in September or October...	.. to decide if more water will be distributed to municipalities, released for environmental purposes or will be stored to address a coming dry year...
GR4	As a water managerI would like to compare forecasted data of surface water availability with historical surface runoff scenariosto identify extreme hydrological conditions during the upcoming season as early as possible .

Solution (TO-BE Scenario): I-CISK aspires to expand the information base for the Potamon dam reservoir and to incorporate in the workflow of OAK advanced predictive tools based on hydrological forecasts of seasonal scales. A seasonal hydrological forecast (6 months ahead) service in combination with statistics from historical hydrologic and meteorological data promotes efficient water allocation before the high-demand touristic (summer) period and timely drought response during the September and October management period, offering increased system performance in the long run. An Operational Early Warning System could interpret forecasts into readily comprehensible warnings that can also be coupled with proactive practices to enhance the resilience and adaptive capacity of OAK.

Value Proposition (Goal of the service): Timely and detailed information on future surface water availability is crucial to water allocation planning and drought response as well as strategic planning. Enable OAK to be proactive and store water in the reservoirs early enough to mitigate the impact of potential droughts and dry years.

Transportation infrastructure sector – qualitative assessment of the gains

Location: Port of Rethymno is located in the central-west part of Crete Island, at the North shores (see Figure 28). It is a port of both free and commercial use and it has been separated into two parts:

- (a) The western part (for commercial and passenger use) where the loading and unloading of all goods is carried out. Occasionally, in this section of the port tourist vessels are docked, a weigh-bridge

with the capacity of up to 80t(tons) has been installed and five (5) piers for loading and unloading capable of accommodating seven ships at the most, depending on their size, are included. The aforementioned piers mainly accommodate commercial vessels. However, when the need arises tourist vessels exceeding 150m may also dock. The commercial station features: Total pier length of 810 meters, Sailing depth between -6.00 and -8.00 meters and Land surface area of about 26,500 m²

- (b) In the eastern part (for passenger and visitor use) the docking of cruise ships and ferries is carried out. This part of the port has a land surface area of 33,500 m² in total and can accommodate any passenger or visitor activity as well as any kind of truck or private vehicle traffic. There is a weigh-bridge with a capacity of up to 80t (tons), and two (2) areas for loading & unloading and a maximum depth of -8.00m.

Piers have been designated as suitable for ferry, liner and passenger ship docking. They are 125 m and 140 m in length respectively, two-meter cylindrical paddings all along, with a deck-width of 35 & 60 meters respectively and a height of 1.80 m above the average sea level have been installed while the average depth is -9.00m.

Figure 28: Port of Rethymno (photo by Wikimedia commons, license CC-BY-SA-4.0,3.0,2.5,2.0,1.0).

End User(s): The Municipal Port Authority Fund of Rethymno continues its historic course which started in Rethymno in 1914. The Department actively contributes to the development of this region of Crete and carries the great responsibility of administering the only entrance gate to Rethymno prefecture to date, as well as maintaining the facilities of all its ports and fishing resorts. The Municipal Port Authority Fund of Rethymno is expected to provide public utility services and to contribute to the commercial, passenger, tourist and fishing traffic and generally to the smooth operation of the ports in its authority.

Challenge: The Rethymno port and associated marinas are the gateways to the Rethymno prefecture. The port itself is a significant gate to the largest Greek island and a highly touristic destination. The management of port traffic and development is crucial for the wider economic sector of the island, the welfare of the community and the touristic sector. Adding pressures of climate change and a thriving touristic sector, the reallocation of port traffic, especially during the high season of touristic activity which lasts up to seven months, becomes a struggle. Extreme winds, surges and heat events act as added pressures.

Current practices in place (AS-IS Scenario): For port managers, the key activities include decisions that are taken on a shorter-term time scale related to traffic management in the port, which is done on a weekly basis currently. Ship management in the port is another activity requiring port managers to plan on medium to longer term timescale (monthly to 5 - 10 years). Longer term planning (5 to 10 years) is also done for decisions related to port defences. Ship traffic management is impacted by wind

patterns and speed, traffic management at the ports is impacted by storms and heat, while decisions related to port defences are impacted by availability of funding and overarching policies regarding tourism. The Municipal Port Authority Fund of Rethymno uses weather forecast data from the national meteorological service as well as other sources and combines it with previous experience for short-term decision making. Also, conducts or procures studies regarding management and development of the port works which manages or plans to construct. The Port Authority is an organization informed of recent developments on climate data, and has co-operation with scientific institutes. Still, decisions on short-term, seasonal and annual aspects of port management are taken based on past experience, analysis of historic meteorological records and weather forecasts.

Solution (User Requirements)

ID	User requirements		
	As a <ROLE>,	I would like to <GOAL>	to <BENEFIT>
GR5	As a port managerI would like to know the frequency of North winds above 7 Beaufort for the upcoming period (short-term to seasonal)to decide upon possible preparations on port defences
GR6	As a port managerI would like to know the frequency of North winds above 7 Beaufort for the upcoming 10 yearsto plan the upgrade, maintenance works or construction of additional, necessary port defences .
GR7	As a port managerI would like to know the frequency of South winds above 7 Beaufort for the upcoming period (short-term to seasonal) to better plan port traffic management, especially of large vessels and avoid damages on floating platforms
GR8	As a port managerI would like to know the frequency of extreme heat or prolonged heat events for the upcoming period (short-term to seasonal)for increased preparedness of related impacts to the port zone .

Solution (TO-BE Scenario): I-CISK aspires to expand the information base for the Port of Rethymno and to incorporate in the workflow of Port Authority advanced predictive tools of seasonal as well as decadal scales. A seasonal forecast (6 months ahead) service for high magnitude winds in combination with statistics (frequency) supports efficient port management before the high-demand touristic (summer) period and timely response during extreme events, offering increased performance and lower maintenance costs in the long run. Decadal predictions provide information on possible wind magnitudes and frequency of events for better planning of defence works.

Value Proposition (Goal of the service): Timely and detailed information on future wind magnitude and frequency is very important to port traffic management as well as strategic planning. It will enable Port Authority to be proactive and mitigate the impact of high wind and surge effects.

Tourism sector (hospitality) – qualitative assessment of the gains

 Location: Elounda hotels and resorts are located in the eastern part of Crete Island, (see Figure 29). Elounda is a collection of three villages, Ano (upper) and Kato (lower) Elounda sitting above the port, Skisma, nestled at the head of the bay of Elounda with a view of the Venetian castle on the island of Kalydon, the famous “Spinalonga”. The corner of the Mirabello bay, with the Spinalonga peninsula and its myriad anchorages is a yachting paradise.

Figure 29: Elounda resort (photo from site: <https://www.elounda-sa.com/>).

 End User(s): Elounda SA hotels & resorts owns and manages three luxury properties in the area of Elounda in Crete, Greece. The company is responsible for making the area the top luxury vacations destination in Greece. The Elounda Mare hotel is member of the prestigious Relais & Châteaux chain in Crete. The Porto Elounda GOLF & SPA RESORT is the only spa & golf resort on the island. All three properties have received awards and distinctions and have established a strong brand in the luxury hotel industry. The hotels also offer culinary experiences, private sandy beaches, Children’s club, a 9-hole par-3 golf course, the Aegean Conference Center, yachts for charter, Scuba diving, Water sports, tennis courts, shopping arcades.

 Challenge: Maintenance of large, coastal facilities can be a significant managerial burden, even more for luxury resorts, when demands for quality services (including facilities infrastructure) is high. Investing on facilities upgrades (e.g. advanced air-conditioning systems of low energy consumption, redaction of heat losses etc) is costly and should be carefully planned. Further, under the lens of the fierce competition in the tourist business, the smooth provision of tourist services is a prerequisite for successful businesses. The hospitality sector builds trust with the visitors and reputational risks are taken seriously. Climate change is creating conditions of more common and unpredictable extreme events which may impede large scale maintenance works. Even more, extreme weather conditions (long periods of heat, extreme heat events, significant precipitation events) pose a significant health risk regarding outdoor activities which are often part of the offered product of touristic businesses. Managing these risks is important for maintaining a valuable touristic product.

 Current practices in place (AS-IS Scenario): For resort managers, planning of outdoor activities (maintenance in the autumn months, planned guest activities during tourist season such as yachting, hiking, bicycle rides etc) is key operational procedure. Coinciding with periods of high winds, heavy precipitation or extreme and/or prolonged periods of heat is a significant risk which should be avoided. Up to now, such challenges are predominantly dealt by re-action to events, previous experience (e.g. which periods usually have favourable weather) and short-term forecast (weather) predictions.

Solution (User Requirements)

ID	User requirements		
	As a <ROLE>	I would like to <GOAL>	to <BENEFIT>
GR9	As a resort/hotel manager...	...I would like to know if and when are heavy precipitation events and/or strong wind events to be expected for the upcoming low season touristic period (November to February) in time...	...to decide upon the scheduling of maintenance works .
GR10	As a resort/hotel managerI would like to know if and when are heavy precipitation, strong wind, extreme heat events to be expected for the upcoming high touristic season period (May - September) in time...	...to decide upon the scheduling of outdoor activities .

Solution (TO-BE Scenario): I-CISK aspires to expand the information base for resort/hotel managers and to incorporate in the workflow advanced predictive tools of seasonal scales. A seasonal forecast (6 months ahead) service for heavy precipitations events, high magnitude winds and frequency of extreme heat events supports the management planning: (a) of maintenance works with lower risks of rescheduling and (b) outdoor activities for the visitors with lower risks regarding weather related health dangers.

Value Proposition (Goal of the service): Timely and detailed information on future extreme weather events and frequency is very important to resort/hotel management. It will enable touristic businesses in the hospitality sector to lower maintenance costs in the long run and increase visitor satisfaction, trust rates and reputational gains.

7.3 Second iteration: Understanding the value chain

To understand how the use of the developed CS helps actors along the value chain to address the challenges they face at an operational level, a description of the value chain is built in a 4-tier analysis based on the methodological framework described in MS26 (Guidelines for Value Chain assessment, June 2024), which is resumed in Figure 30. The goal at this point is the analysis to be sufficiently informed the develop the understanding of the economic, social and environmental benefits and to complete the User Stories.

Tier 1 is the “supplier” of the climatic data i.e. the seasonal forecasting data of essential variables or impact models results. EU, through dedicated services and programs such as Copernicus, provides climatic data to a large end-user group. ECMWF as a scientific organization generates and provides high quality climatic data of seasonal forecasts which may be used by downstream services “as is” or are repurposed through impact modelling by scientific institutes (in present case SMHI, the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute) which widen the services of climatic data (e.g. seasonal forecasting of river flows). Their benefit from providing climatic data could be: (a) scientific: receiving feedback which allows to enhance their data quality, (b) economic, through the provision of data services and (c) business-oriented, by achieving reputational gains and expanding their partnerships and data provision services.

Tier 2 is the “primary user” (this is also referred to as intermediary user) of the climatic service. EMVIS SA develops a state-of-the-art product-service that transforms the value of the climatic service, **acting as knowledge purveyor** between the supplier (tier 1) and the end user (tier 3) of the climatic service. Through

this process, EMVIS SA enhances its ability to provide added value (innovation gains), develops services which increase its market share and provide additional revenue (economic gains) and builds on its reputational profile which also supports the expansion of partnerships (entrepreneurship gains).

Tier 3 is the “secondary user” i.e. the end user of the service provided by the primary user. The Water Management Operator, Organisation for the Development of Crete (OAK), incorporates the developed CS in the organization’s workflow. In that way OAK can improve its operational activities by taking water management decisions which: (a) increase revenue gains (selling more water, i.e. economic gains), (b) improve the management of water resources of the island and therefore better achieving environmental compliance (environmental gains). Managers of the transportation sector, i.e. OAK (large road network manager), Port of Rethymno organization (port manager), can better organize (preparedness) maintenance of sector which may reduce the relevant costs (economic gain), may improve operational procedures (decrease losses due to informed port traffic redirection – economic gains) and increase public acceptance of works and decision (reputational gains). The hospitality industry (from resorts to smaller businesses) can better organise maintenance works (sufficient workflows, lower costs – economic gains), increase visitor trust and satisfaction rate (reputational gains), which may lead to increased re-visit rates and visitor numbers and consequently to revenue increase. Better informed DMOs (Destination Management Organizations) can better plan and target advertising which translates to a potentially more successful strategy (and therefore increase in revenue).

Figure 30: Understanding of the value chain for the Climate Services developed in the Crete Island Living Lab (Greece).

Tier 4 includes the other economic sectors which are associated indirectly with the tourism product as well as the wider “citizens, society and the environment”, which are the end beneficiaries of the climatic service. Better services (water, transport, hospitality) support the touristic product (reputational gains) which may increase visiting rates and further development of the island economy (increasing revenue). The citizens and society enjoy the end result of the climatic service as enhanced water availability and better environmental conditions. Due to better management decisions, they may enjoy water availability, especially during dry years, and possibly at unaffected or lower prices (economic gains). Further, better water management means enhanced water security which, in combination with improved environmental condition and enhanced transport-infrastructure conditions translates into broader societal gains.

7.4 Third iteration: Analyse the benefits

Up to this point, the analysis has focused on understanding and setting out the perimeter of the case analysis. The next stage is to analyse the benefits identified and quantify them where possible. It is noted that the analysis presented in the following, targets the assessment of part of the value identified in the 2nd Tier of the value chain analysis, based on assessing the values for the 3rd Tier of the value chain.

Where the analysis can demonstrate potential economic gains or avoided costs, quantification is most preferable to lead to actual financial benefits. The economic benefits are those related to the economic performance of the actors at each tier of the value chain. By definition, the benefits can be monetized although this is not always easy. This is the hardest part of analysing the benefits and consumes the most time and effort. It requires the development of models representing the way in which the business process is generating value. Often, direct figures are not available from the stakeholders and one must rely on assumptions which should be clearly stated. As described in the introduction of the current paragraph (par. 7), the CS co-developed within the Crete Island LL, has been co-designed under the frame of a multi-sectoral approach, addressing needs and challenges from cross-cutting sectors, including tourism sector, water management, transportation infrastructure (roads, ports) and energy sector. Given the above, it would not be realistic to aim for quantifying and monetizing the benefits from all the sectors, due to the various needs on information and the time restrictions within the I-CISK project. For these reasons, for the LL of Crete, the monetizing analysis focuses on the CS for the water-manager needs and approaches the other sectors through a more qualitative assessment.

Water management sector – quantifying the gains

There is a wide variety of methodologies to assess the value of climate services. In the current case a methodology is applied that is based on the value of information and decision theory, as described in relevant applications in the CLARA project (see Bosello F. et al., 2021). This methodology better suits the part of the CS that refers to the water management sector. Details of the application are given in Annex B (“Quantify the benefits of the CS for the Water Sector - Crete Island LL”) of the current deliverable.

The value estimated by this approach is based: (a) on a theoretical performance of the service, which refers to a hypothetical or historical scenario and (b) on the estimation of the value by specific end-users. This means that the value estimated is somewhat relative, since if the hypothetical testing scenario or the end-users evaluating the service change, then the value may change.

The value is estimated comparing the potential gains that an end-user may have for the evaluation period by using the CS and taking informed decisions against the results of decisions based on current practices. The gains from the use of the service are related to the potential of the reservoir to offer the intended services, based on the water stored. That is, when the water managers achieve stored water at a level which can serve drinking water needs, energy production and flood protection, the gain is maximised. Too much water, or too

low reserves, both lower gains (see for details Annex B). Additionally, when the planned abstraction (average conditions, maximum use of the reservoir) can be increased by 100%, then an added maximum abstraction payoff is reached.

Assessments were performed for three hypothetical scenarios:

Scenario 1: an average hydrological year which is based on actual data from the past decade and an assumption of full utilization of the reservoir’s water, as planned.

Scenario 2: an average hydrological year which is based on actual data from the past decade. However, the irrigation withdrawals (not the drinking water withdrawals) reach half of the full utilization planning.

Scenario 3: a dry-period scenario which is based on a hypothetical two-dry years in sequence and the assumption of full utilization of the reservoir’s water. In this scenario, drinking water withdrawals triple, in comparison to Scenarios 1 and 2, while irrigation withdrawals are the same with scenario 2. This is a worst-case scenario, minimizing inflows for two years and maximizing water allocation needs.

The increase of gains is summarized in Table 7. Scenario 1 is close to a full utilization of the reservoir reserves and therefore there is limited room for changes in water abstraction during the touristic period, when they are needed most. However, the CS demonstrated potential gains (26% increase). Scenario 2 provides better opportunities for maximizing the gain from the CS forecasts because the reservoir is not utilized in its full potential by the agricultural sector (irrigation). In this case the gains from CS use are significantly higher (110% increase of gains). For Scenario 3, the unfavourable two-years of low inflows (dry years) led also to the need for reducing the abstractions, hence to negative abstraction gains payoff during the second year. However, even under these conditions there is still some room for gains (4% increase).

Table 7: Gains by the use of the CS for the three climatic scenarios examined

Scenario	Increase of gains by use of CS
	%
1	26%
2	110%
3 (dry years)	4%

Based on the above steps towards assessing the potential gains in a quantitative approach, the CS demonstrates benefits that range from **LOW to HIGH**, depending on the climatic scenario examined. It is noted that the above calculations are based on three scenarios of the climatic conditions and utilization of the reservoir. These scenarios cover some favourable, average and unfavourable conditions but it is recognized that other conditions may lead to different results.

Transportation infrastructure sector – qualitative assessment of the gains

The evaluation of the service is based on identifying appropriate indicators which represent potential benefit for the end-user and hence, demonstrate a value for the CS. To support transportation infrastructure, with focus on port management, during the co-creation process specific needs were identified which translated into tailored climatic indicators to support decision making.

The Municipal Port Authority Fund of Rethymno identifies the southern winds above 7 Beaufort as directly correlated to the stress induced on the port floating platforms. The logical steps which lead to the co-identification of the value of the specific CS have been identified as follows:

- These winds put pressure on the floating platforms because they push the docked ships and smaller vessels to move with force against the platforms and cause damage

- South winds are not prevailing (low frequency) in the area but can reach larger magnitudes
- The damage varies depending on the size of ship and can be from minor to major
- This damage is dealt with periodically by the Municipal Port Authority Fund, on a per occurrence basis.
- The damages can be dealt with maintenance works or complete replacement depending on the damage
- The port authority identifies that the annual costs of these damages range around the scale of medium, in comparison to the total annual costs of the Port Fund.
- Another possible related cost, is the revenue loss due to the ships which will be directed to avoid docking to the port due to the winds.
- On an operational basis, if seasonal forecasting would provide good information on the expected frequency of these winds, especially for periods of heavy traffic for the port, then probably the Port Fund could reschedule the dockings or better plan them to allow for better allocation of vessels within the port
- That could probably lead to:
 - o (a) smaller damages to the floating platforms and
 - o (b) less revenue losses due to last minute rescheduling of ship dockings

Based on the above reasonable steps towards identification of the value chain and on the scaling of benefits given in Table 1, the service demonstrates two specific benefits. Based on the reasoning of “avoided costs” which are identified by the end-user as medium, the benefit of the service is identified as:

MODERATE .

Tourism sector (hospitality) – qualitative assessment of the gains

The evaluation of the service is based on identifying appropriate indicators which represent potential benefit for the end-user and hence demonstrate a value for the CS. To support the tourism sector (hospitality), during the co-creation process specific needs were identified which translated into tailored climatic indicators to support decision making.

The Crete LL stakeholder identified two very specific climatic challenges related to the management of their facilities. The logical steps which lead to the co-identification of the value of the specific CS have been identified and followed separately for each challenge:

Annual needs of extensive maintenance works

- Most of hospitality facilities need to schedule maintenance works
- These works take place during the low season which is mainly during the late autumn and winter period
- The maintenance period coincides in time with periods of events of heavy precipitation and/or wind.
- If extended works are planned and have to be cancelled due to unfavourable conditions, this has additional costs and poses a management burden for re-planning.
- This cost of re-planning and stopping of works, could range from low to moderate economic burden.
- If, under a changing climate, a more robust planning system based on a CS, for operational use could be available, there exist gains, potential of importance.
- That could probably lead to:

- (a) avoidance of stopping of works, which would cut down the costs of restarting the works in another period (costs related to longest period of reserved maintenance services)
- (b) less revenue losses which are related to management costs

Seasonal planning needs on outdoor activities

- Tourist hospitality facilities, especially larger or more luxurious ones, commonly offer a series of options for organized outdoor activities during the touristic season.
- Extreme weather events such as heatwaves or summer heavy precipitation and/or floods hinder these outdoor activities. They also pose danger to the visitors
- On an operational basis, if seasonal forecasting would provide good information on the expected frequency of extreme events, then probably the management of resorts could better schedule the activities to avoid dissatisfaction of customers or even exposure to serious health hazards.
- This could lead to:
 - (a) reputational gains of the facilities and
 - (b) potential increase on revisit rates

Based on the above reasonable steps towards identification of the value chain and on the scaling of benefits given in Table 1, the service demonstrates four (4) specific benefits for two (2) different value indicators. Based on the reasoning of “avoided costs” which are identified by the end-user as low to medium, the benefit of the service is identified as:

LOW ●● to MODERATE ●●●.

Tourism sector (as a whole) – quantifying the gains

The CS developed in Crete LL is based on a multisectoral approach towards the Tourism sector. Quantifying the benefits of the service to the Tourism sector requires considering complicated interactions between the sectors. In order to approach the above, we apply a methodology of quantification using a system dynamic model. This model effectively demonstrates how the implementation of CS products can improve informed and sector-specific decision-making processes in these sectoral domains. The approach is provided in Annex C (“Quantify the benefits of the CS for the Tourism Sector - Crete Island LL”) of current Deliverable.

According to the results of the model, the use of CS products developed following a multi-stakeholder, multi-sectoral approach, may lead to an increase in the values of the sector-specific indices that gauge the effect of CS products across the selected sectors (tourism, water, transportation, energy) **ranging from 4% to 14%**, attributable to the multi-sectoral approach implemented on the island of Crete. The above indicates an average **10% increase of the** sector-specific indices of the sectors addressed by the CS for tourism in Crete.

Taking into account that this approach considers the overall effect of the CS on the addressed sectors, over the whole island, for a period up to the end of century, this is an important indication that the CS developed may have **significant benefits for the Tourism sector as a whole**.

7.5 Fourth iteration: analysis beyond the defined boundaries

7.5.1 Defining the market boundaries

Defining the segments

Segmentation is the first key step of the product-specific approach to be adopted in the Market Analysis and it is the basis to study the needs and behaviour of potential end-users. Aaker and McLoughlin (2010: p.26) define market segmentation in the context of strategic market management as “the identification of customer groups that respond differently from other groups to competitive offerings”. In other words, groups of actual and potential customers are aggregated based on similarities in their needs and other variables like geographic location, customer type and benefits sought. In general, the marketing literature seems to agree that there is no single way to segment a market (e.g., Kotler and Armstrong 2013). This is in part because the set of variables used may differ depending on the marketer’s choice and the market type (consumer market, business market, international market). Furthermore, the exercise can be undertaken from different viewpoints: segmenting by customer characteristics (e.g., age and interests) or looking at product characteristics (e.g., benefits provided and potential applications).

The I-CISK project had from the conceptual phase a clear proposition as far as the targeted users of the developed services. As climate change is cutting across multiple societal, economic and environmental domains, a clear link to well-defined market segments and their needs, directly impacted from climate change induced threats had been identified as sectors having significant business opportunities. In the case of the broader tourism sector, those market segments included hospitality services management, water resources management, energy production and transportation.

The insight gained from the elicitation exercise allowed the identification of additional targeted market segments and a better classification of potential CS users among the already identified ones, based on similarities identified in respect of their needs, specific requirements and other variables like geographic location, customer type and benefits sought.

This has led to a better clustering of the targeted market segments in Tourism Sector e.g. Hotels, Destination Management Operators etc. and enabled the identification of potential users in various sectors mentioned above.

A non-exhaustive list of candidate customer groups based on user type and common challenges has been prepared and is presented together with user group descriptions in [Table 8](#). An overview of the identified user groups is presented in [Figure 31](#).

Figure 31: Market segments mapping for I-CISK climate services developed in the Crete LL.

The Hospitality services sector presents a multi-level structure where services related to tourism development, promotion and management are often distributed among different types of stakeholders. More specifically, at the local level this includes hotels and local tourism related businesses such as adventure tourism providers (e.g. hiking, mountain climbing, etc.) and daily tours operators. At regional level relevant organizations include stakeholders responsible for promoting tourism of a specific destination, such as Destinations Management Organizations (DMOs). These may also operate on national level, possibly under the authority of other national organizations such as National Tourism Organizations (NTOs). International stakeholders vary depending on the geographic scope of their activities and the institutional framework within which they operate. This category commonly includes global organizations such as tour operators, whose activities include operating on multiple destinations worldwide.

Water sector across EU (and internationally) presents a complex governance framework. It is therefore common for the responsibility of managing water reservoirs to fall under different (types) of agencies. This category may include bulk water managers, water utilities, water authorities depending on the primary use of the dam (e.g., hydropower, agriculture, potable water supply, etc.), the implementing authority (ministry, regional administration) etc.

The other candidate customer groups present a simpler structure, involving fewer potential actors. Table 8 summarizes the identified stakeholders based on their respective sectors.

Table 8: Stakeholders identified as potential market segments for I-CISK climate service (Crete Island LL)

Stakeholder Group	Description
HOSPITALITY SERVICES SECTOR	
Hotels	Hotels manage the tourist product by offering accommodation and services that meet the customer needs, shaping the overall visitor experience. Through their activities they also contribute to the development of the destination. Hotels as well as other actors in hospitality sector are likely to be affected by the impacts of climate change both directly (e.g. changes in cooling/heating degree days, coastal erosion etc.) and indirectly (e.g. shifts in tourist behaviour, growing preference in more climate resilient destinations).
Adventure tourism providers and local tour operators	Adventure tourism providers and local tour operators design and deliver unique experience-based activities that focus on specific interests (e.g. hiking, mountain climbing etc.). They mainly promote the natural assets of a destination ensuring safety and they are responsible for enhancing the overall tourism offering. These kinds of businesses are affected by climate change due to changes in the duration of activities season as well as rising insurance costs which may lead to increased adaptation costs.
Destination Management Organizations (DMOs)	Destination Management Organizations are responsible for promoting a specific destination by organizing and presenting all the essential information related to tourist attractions, beaches, activities, restaurants, bars etc. They aim to showcase the destination in an accessible and appealing way in order to attract tourist flows while supporting sustainable development. Impacts of climate change might swift marketing positioning for the promoted destination.
National Tourism Operators (NTOs)	National Tourism Organizations are responsible for the implementation of national tourism strategies to promote the country as a tourist destination working closely with both public and private sector. NTOs also collect and analyse data in order to offer a statistical overview of the country's tourism product supporting informed decision making. Impacts of climate change may lead in incorporating climate risk assessments in adaptation strategies while supporting industry transition to sustainability.
Tourism Industry Alliance	Tourism Industry Alliance represents and coordinates the interests of tourism businesses towards sustainable growth and strategic promotion of tourism. Climate change may affect tourism development, urging for adaptive policies.
Global Tour Operators	Tour operators organize and sell travel packages that provide various services that most commonly include transportation, accommodation and activities. Global tour operators often influence travel trends by selecting specific destinations to support. Thus, it is important to take proactive measures to predict customer behaviour that may be influenced by extreme weather events related to climate change.
WATER SECTOR	
National and regional water authorities	Ministries and other government institutions (e.g., agencies) at the national level are responsible for socio-economic development as well as water management and use. For Member States, their responsibilities include the development of management plans and risk maps for reporting related to the FD, WFD and daughter directives.
Dam/Reservoir Operators	Dam operators are responsible for the operation and maintenance of the dam as well as implementing emergency plans in case of dam's malfunction. They also coordinate with local authorities and stakeholders to ensure effective management of water resources. Climate change may impact water availability

Stakeholder Group	Description
	affecting water distribution and usage, highlighting the growing need for resilient water systems.
Bulk water management authorities	Bulk water managers are responsible for applications related to potable and non-potable water storage, delivery systems and subsystems such as transmission and distribution pipelines. They are usually public entities and they act as regulators within local and regional watersheds.
Water suppliers/water Utilities	Water suppliers are the companies providing water in an agreed geographical region. There exist various forms of water provision. The most widely used governance structure in the European Union is public water provision. In the European Union there are few exceptions. France and the United Kingdom provide their water mostly by private sector or mixed management. Climate change may affect water availability and increase demand making the sustainable water resources management even more critical.
TRANSPORTATION SECTOR	
Port Authorities	Port authorities are organizations that manage the operation and maintenance of a port or group of ports. Their responsibilities include vessel traffic control, cargo handling coordination as well as safety and security enforcement. Impacts of climate change such as coastal erosion and flooding, which can damage equipment and cause disruptions to the supply chain.
Airport Authorities	Airport Authorities are responsible for the operation, and development of an airport's infrastructure and services. This includes managing passenger terminals and ensuring compliance with aviation regulations to support safe and efficient air travel. Airports authorities may need to manage increasing frequency of extreme weather events which could affect business continuity, emphasizing the need for infrastructure reinforcement.
Road Infrastructure Operators	A road infrastructure operator is responsible for operation, maintenance and development of road networks (e.g. highways, national roads, etc.) as well as ensuring road safety, traffic management and other actions in order to support efficient transportation of people and goods. Climate change may affect maintenance costs and increase travel disruptions.
FOOD SECURITY SECTOR	
National and regional authorities	Ministry of Agriculture and other government institutions (e.g. Agriculture organization) mainly are responsible for managing a country's agricultural policy ensuring food security. The impacts of climate change affect food security increasing the need for early warning systems and risk management plans.
ENERGY SECTOR	
Transmission System Operators (TSOs) for electricity	Transmission System Operators for electricity are responsible for the operation, control, maintenance and development of the high voltage electricity transmission network. Their main objective is to ensure a secure, efficient and reliable transmission of electricity across the country. Preparing for climate change impacts may maximize reliable and sustainable energy delivery.
Distribution Network Operators (DSOs) for electricity	Distribution Network Operators for electricity are responsible for the operation, maintenance and development of the medium and low voltage electricity distribution networks. They also ensure the delivery of electricity from the transmission system to end users.
PUBLIC	

Stakeholder Group	Description
General public	The general public refers to people living in areas that are more affected by climate impacts
Citizen organizations, environmental organizations	Citizens and/or environmental organizations raise awareness of the effects of climate change and can further education in schools and universities. Environmental organizations provide information for the general public and for practitioners in different areas.

Selecting target groups

In selecting a target group, there are three main issues to be considered according to Aaker and McLoughlin (2010). First, the capacity of the developer to create a product that is appealing to the individual target group. Second, reflecting whether this appeal could be sustained even after competitors react to your market actions. And last, estimating whether the return (i.e., benefit) is higher than the investment (i.e., cost) required to provide an appealing, customized product. In constructing a simple scorecard to assess a group's attractiveness, these issues reformulated into criteria and included two more based on the literature, describing how pressing is the need in the target group and how well it is satisfied by the offering.

Based on the background information provided in Market Analysis section below, as well as the CS developer's own expertise and business objectives, the stakeholder groups that were considered to be best candidates have been identified. The attractiveness of these shortlisted market segments has then been evaluated using the Group Attractiveness Scorecard (Table 9).

It is important to note that the Crete LL and the involved stakeholders are the primary target group. This is because, based on this analysis conducted, the LL serves as a "testing" group in order to better understand the interactions between various business sectors in a relatively small and localized scale, and study how climate change impacts these interactions. Therefore, the LL is not included in the attractiveness score table (Table 9), because it does not represent a single sector but rather a multisectoral group.

As mentioned, the tourism sector is considered a primary target for the CS developed in Crete LL and acknowledging that the tourism industry is highly profitable in many EU countries, it becomes evident that taking measures in order to reduce the exposure to potential climate change threats, offers solutions to various potential affected aspects of tourism industry. Organizations such as NTOs and DMOs can demonstrate a more attractive cost to benefit ratio in implementing a Climate Service compared to individual businesses (hotels or adventure tourism sector businesses), because they manage tourism sector collectively and have a better understanding of the sector's needs and potential risks. It is also more achievable to communicate the threats, therefore the advantages of the CS, because they most commonly operate as Non-profitable Organizations or as public sector bodies, therefore they may have a greater interest in mitigating the impact of climate change to tourism sector within their area of jurisdiction.

For the water sector, considering that a dam or a reservoir can support multiple socio-environmental and economic activities, it becomes evident that taking measures proactively to reduce the exposure (and therefore impact) to possible climate threats such as fluctuations of water availability at the dam level has a cumulative benefit accrued across the impacted domains. It is for this reason that Reservoir Operators can demonstrate a more attractive cost to benefit ratio in implementing a CS than individual reservoir water users. However, this implies a well-defined valuation of all costs and benefits and a structured mechanism for cost transaction, which is not always the case.

A distinction is also made between European and International Markets. The European water sector, although highly fragmented, has relatively homogenous characteristics due to the common EU water policy framework applied. International markets are also considered as potential market segments for the developed CS, due to increasing environmental challenges. Nevertheless, the distinct characteristics of these markets are expected to result in a lower penetration rate than this of the European water industry which is the immediate market

for consortium partners with well established presence and stronger customer relationships.

These considerations make the Dam/Reservoir Operators and Bulk Water Management Authorities across EU a primary target group of the Water Sector for marketing I-CISK Climate Services (Crete Island LL).

Table 9: Group Attractiveness Scorecard.

I-CISK Climate Service:		Seasonal forecasting and end-of-century projections for tourism sector and interlinked sectors					
Sector	Market Segment	Criteria					Total Score
		[C1] The customer group has a pressing need and is willing to act upon it.	[C2] Our offering can satisfy that need.	[C3] We can easily communicate/ access the customer group.	[C4] There are no known competitors addressing this need.	[C5] The customer group is substantial and potentially profitable.	
Hospitality	Hotels	3	4	2	3	3	15
	Adventure tourism providers and local tour operators	2	4	2	1	2	11
	Destination Management Organizations (DMOs)	5	5	4	3	4	21
	National Tourism Operators (NTOs)	4	5	4	3	4	20
	Tourism Industry Alliance	3	4	3	3	3	16
	Global Tour Operators	4	5	2	2	5	18
	Reservoir Operators	5	5	4	4	4	22
Water	Bulk water management authorities	5	5	4	4	4	22
	Water suppliers/ Water Utilities	4	3	3	3	3	16
	National and regional water authorities	5	4	3	2	4	18

I-CISK Climate Service:		Seasonal forecasting and end-of-century projections for tourism sector and interlinked sectors					
Sector	Market Segment	Criteria					Total Score
		[C1] The customer group has a pressing need and is willing to act upon it.	[C2] Our offering can satisfy that need.	[C3] We can easily communicate/ access the customer group.	[C4] There are no known competitors addressing this need.	[C5] The customer group is substantial and potentially profitable.	
Transportation	Port Authorities	4	3	2	3	4	16
	Airport Authorities	4	2	4	2	5	17
	Road Infrastructure Operators	2	4	2	4	2	14
Energy	Transmission System Operators (TSOs) for electricity	3	2	3	3	3	14
	Distribution Network Operators (DSOs) for electricity	2	2	3	3	2	12
Food Security	National and regional authorities for food security	3	3	3	2	4	15
Public	General public	1	3	1	3	1	9
	Citizen and environmental organizations	1	3	2	3	2	11

Note 1: A rating of 1 denotes the statement is totally inaccurate, a rating of 5 denotes the statement is totally accurate.

7.5.2 Market Analysis

Estimating the potential size of the target market

Hospitality Sector

Having selected a target group (see Section 7.5.1) the next task is to estimate the potential business that can be generated from addressing its needs. To elaborate this approximation, the following steps were taken:

- Estimating the total number of addressable customers in the target group or Total Addressable Market (TAM). This metric provides the entire potential market independently of the ability to reach it and serve it yet. Considering the nature of the target group (National Tourism Operations and Destination Management Operators), the necessary information upon which current estimates are based, was found in European/national/regional statistics databases, industry association reports and other documents.
- Assuming a market penetration rate and calculating the potential Serviceable Addressable Market size (SAM). This metric can be used as an approximation of the potential customer base that can be actually served and reached for delivering the developed CS services. Penetration rate was assumed on the basis of the circumstances that drive the target group's needs (e.g., Proactive management of climate change threats), the priority assigned by the target group to this need (i.e., their willingness to act upon it), and the additional requirements that the target group would have to cover to benefit from your product (e.g., training, equipment). The ability to reach this market portion is not assessed at this point of the analysis.
- Assessing the share and portion of the target market that can be captured that is the Serviceable Obtainable Market (SOM). Estimations on this metric have been based mostly on the level of competition identified for similar services to the offering of the developed CS.
- Finally, calculating the potential monetary value of the market (Sp€). This is the product of the potential Serviceable Obtainable Market size (SOM) and the expected sales value, i.e., the price of the product (P). The potential monetary value of the market is not assessed at this point of the analysis.

In the process of analysing the market opportunity for the Crete LL I-CISK services, the following critical attributes were identified and used as indicators for increased market uptake.

Considering that the primary market consists of Tourism Organizations across Europe, specifically National Tourism Operators (NTOs) and Destination Management Operators (DMOs), the market analysis was conducted using data from Eurostat, the World Bank, national statistics datasets and other relevant sources. This analysis provides estimates on the number and budget of NTOs and DMOs as well as economic indicators such as the contribution of tourism sector in each country's GDP.

National Tourism Operators (NTOs) in Europe.

There are 38 National Tourism Organizations (NTOs) operating across Europe, typically one per country. For the purposes of this market analysis, the focus was placed on the 27 NTOs within the European Union. This decision was based on the greater availability of financial and statistical data for EU member states, succeeding more reliable and comparable estimates.

The **Total Addressable Market (TAM)** represents the full economic value of the tourism industry in Europe. Based on travel receipts data from Eurostat (2022), the tourism sector across the European Union generated 146.9 billion euros²⁶ (Figure 32).

²⁶ Travel receipts and expenditures in balance of payments – Eurostat (https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Tourism_statistics)

Figure 32: Tourism revenues in million euros by EU member state 2022 (Source: Eurostat²⁷).

The **Serviceable Available Market (SAM)** is the total public spending by National Tourism Organizations (NTOs) in Europe. To estimate this, we used the budget of the Greek NTO (EOT)²⁸ for 2022 as an indicator. We adjusted this amount proportionally based on each country's tourism contribution to GDP. This is a reasonable estimate of the potential public budgets allocated to similar tourism organizations across European Union. A summary of tourism contribution to GDP and the estimated NTO budgets per EU member state is presented in Table 10.

Table 10: Estimated National Tourism Organization budgets and tourism contribution to GDP across EU.

EU Member State	Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in billion euros	Percentage of tourism contribution in GDP	National Organization budget per member state in million euros
Belgium	596.3206	6%	48.77
Bulgaria	94.7093	7%	9.72
Czechia	317.3858	6%	25.96
Denmark	376.43	7%	36.39
Germany	4185.55	11%	684.69

²⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Tourism_statistics

²⁸ Budget implementation of the Greek NTO "EOT" (<https://gnto.gov.gr/stoicheia-ektelesis-proypologismou-eot/>)

EU Member State	Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in billion euros	Percentage of tourism contribution in GDP	National Organization budget per member state in million euros
Estonia	38.1878	9%	5.22
Ireland	509.9518	4%	28.82
Greece	225.1969	19%	64.30
Spain	1498.324	15%	323.09
France	2822.4546	9%	369.37
Croatia	78.0485	26%	29.95
Italy	2131.39	11%	332.81
Cyprus	31.34	13%	6.01
Latvia	39.3724	8%	4.39
Lithuania	73.7928	5%	5.71
Luxembourg	80.9919	9%	10.24
Hungary	197.902	7%	21.78
Malta	20.5414	14%	4.15
Netherlands	1067.599	10%	152.41
Austria	473.2267	11%	74.60
Poland	748.9234	4%	45.66
Portugal	267.9232	20%	78.09
Romania	324.3686	6%	27.01
Slovenia	63.9512	10%	9.32
Slovakia	122.9189	5%	8.77
Finland	272.782	7%	28.80
Sweden	541.184	7%	57.14

While the combined budget of European NTOs is estimated at 2.31 billion euros, based on the assumptions we mention above, not all of it is allocated to external services. A large portion covers fixed costs such as staff salaries and administration expenses. We conservatively estimate that approximately 25 - 30% of this budget is allocated to external services, such as consulting, marketing, and climate-related services. This results in a Serviceable Available Market (SAM) of 577–693 million euros.

The **Serviceable Obtainable Market (SOM)** represents a realistic revenue potential from targeting a subset of NTOs. We can assume that it is possible to approach 8 to 10 NTOs, therefore, it is assumed a percentage of 30% out of SAM size due to the highly competitive advantages recognized at I-CISK Climate Services which results in an estimated SOM of approximately 171 – 205 million euros.

Destination Management Operators (DMOs) in Europe.

The other target group of the tourism sector with high score attractiveness is the Destination Management Organizations group. A total of 103 Destination Management Organizations (DMOs) currently operating in the

European Union have been identified through directories such as ECM - European Cities Marketing²⁹. These organizations are responsible for the management and promotion of tourism at city level. In some cases, a National Tourism Organization (NTO) may also serve as a DMO, particularly when the destination being marketed is the nation as a whole. However, within the framework of this analysis, the sub-national level (cities and local destinations) rather than the national one is prioritized.

The average annual budget of Europe’s DMOs is less than 5 million euros (Borzyszkowski, Jacek 2015). Based on public data of city of Athens DMO, we can approximate that each of the 99 EU DMOs have an average annual budget of 3.5 million euros. The estimate assumes that city-sized DMOs in the EU have a similar setup, ranging from availability of public funds as well as potential EU funds.

Out of a total of 99 DMOs existing in the European Union and with the City of Athens DMO as a comparative reference budget (3.5 million euros annually), the **Total Addressable Market (TAM)** is estimated at 346.5 million euros (Table 11). If it can be assumed that 25–30% of the budgets for DMOs are used for external services, the **Serviceable Available Market (SAM)** is 87–104 million euros. A conservative market penetration of 30% estimates a **Serviceable Obtainable Market (SOM)** of approximately 26–31 million euros.

Table 11: Potential Size of the Target Group for TMOs and DMOs for the EU Context.

#	Total Market (TAM)	Addressable Size	Serviceable Market (SAM)	Addressable size	Serviceable Market (SOM)	Obtainable size	Comments/ Assumptions
TMOs	146.9 billion euros		693 million euros		205 million euros		Note 1
DMOs	346.5 million euros		104 million euros		31 million euros		Note 2

Note 1: The (TAM) number is based on every EU country's total contribution of tourism to their GDP and serves as a measure of the overall size of the tourism sector in the EU region. For the estimation of the SAM number, it is assumed that a percentage of 30% (indicatively) out of NTOs budget can be reached, based on estimated budget commitments for external services. The ability to reach this market portion is related to the distribution model and has not been assessed at this point of the analysis. For the estimation of (SOM) size it is assumed a percentage of 30% out of SAM size due to the highly competitive advantages recognized at I-CISK Climate Services.

Note 2: The (TAM) number is calculated from the combined annual budget of the 99 DMOs across EU Region assuming that all of them are potential clients for I-CISK Climate Services. For the estimation of the SAM number, it is assumed that a percentage of 30% (indicatively) out of TAM can be reached, based on estimated budget commitments for external services. The ability to reach this market portion is related to the distribution model and has not been assessed at this point of the analysis. For the estimation of (SOM) size it is assumed a percentage of 30% out of SAM size, due to the highly competitive advantages recognized at I-CISK Climate Services.

²⁹ <https://citydestinationsalliance.eu/members/>

Figure 33: Estimated market segment metrics for various scenarios.

Water Sector

The methodology used to estimate the potential business opportunities in the Hospitality service sector as presented in the previous chapter, is now applied to the selected segments of the Water Sector. This analysis is more extensive primarily because of the recognized potential climate threats to water availability. To elaborate this approximation, the following steps were taken:

- Estimating the total number of addressable customers in the target group or Total Addressable Market (TAM). This metric provides the entire potential market independently of the ability to reach it and serve it yet. Considering the nature of the target group (Reservoir Operators and Bulk Water Management Authorities), the necessary information upon which current estimates are based, was found in national/regional statistics databases, industry association reports and other documents.
- Assuming a market penetration rate and calculating the potential Serviceable Addressable Market size (SAM). This metric can be used as an approximation of the potential customer base that can be actually served and reached for delivering the developed CSs. Penetration rate was assumed on the basis of the circumstances that drive the target group's needs (e.g., Proactive management of water quantity threats), the priority assigned by the target group to this need (i.e., their willingness to act upon it), and the additional requirements that the target group would have to cover to benefit from the product (e.g., training, equipment). The ability to reach this market portion is not assessed at this point of the analysis.
- Assessing the share and portion of the target market that can be captured that is the Serviceable Obtainable Market (SOM). Estimations on this metric have been based mostly on the level of competition identified for similar services to I-CISK offering.
- Finally, calculating the potential monetary value of the market (Sp€). This is the product of the potential Serviceable Obtainable Market size (SOM) and the expected sales value, i.e., the price of the product (P). The potential monetary value of the market is not assessed at this point of the analysis.

In the process of analysing the market opportunity for I-CISK climate services of Crete LL, the following critical attributes were identified and used as indicators for increased market uptake.

Number of reservoirs.

Considering that the primary market segment of interest is Reservoir Operators and Bulk Water Management Authorities in Europe, data from the World Register of Dams maintained by the International Commission of Large Dams (ICOLD) were analysed providing an estimation of the number of reservoirs of interest (Figure 39).

Reservoir/Dams Water Availability

Across Europe, reservoirs play a crucial role ensuring water availability for public demand, irrigation, and hydropower generation. The potential decrease in water availability could increase the demand for climate services that highlight such risks, enabling the development of effective mitigation strategies. Climate-induced drought is likely to threaten the reliability water storage facilities (e.g. reservoirs), while prolonged dry periods increase the risk of reduced levels of storage in reservoirs, directly affecting water security.

According to the European Drought Risk Atlas³⁰ the impact of droughts on water supply systems can be estimated by calculating changes in water abstraction needs. Particularly, during dry periods, up to 10% additional annual water abstraction may be required in an effort to meet public demand. This additional demand may exceed the amount of water that reservoirs and other surface storage systems can reliably

³⁰ European Drought Risk Atlas, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2023: <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC135215>

provide. While northern European Countries may be able to cope with such peaks due to water sources being more abundant, for southern European Countries with already increased demand may struggle to accommodate extra abstractions (Figure 34).

Figure 34: Average annual loss (%) as a drought-induced increase in water abstraction for public water supply in European Union in NUTS-2 level (Source: European Drought Risk Atlas – Joint Research Center EU).

Risk is projected to increase across most of Europe, especially in Mediterranean countries, mainly because of higher water demand during droughts (Figure 35). This could lead to more pressure on water suppliers, and possibly restrictions on household water use. This is especially likely in the Mediterranean region, where we already see that during droughts events, water abstractions drop, showing that even usual demand cannot be fulfilled during current extreme events (European Drought Risk Atlas – 2023).

Figure 35: Drought risk for water supply between current and projected climate conditions. Risk is measured as average annual increase in drought-induced abstraction compared to the average expected value under

current climate conditions. Results of future simulations forced with 11 climate models in RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 are averaged for each warming level (+1.5 °C, +2.0 °C). The analysis was conducted at NUTS-2 level (Source: European Drought Risk Atlas – Joint Research Center EU).

The Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI) is an indicator used to quantify meteorological drought, recording precipitation deficits over a variety of time scales. More specifically, the SPI-6 measures anomalies in total precipitation over a 6-month period and is commonly used to assess seasonal to medium-term drought severity. Negative values of SPI-6 indicate below average conditions, and values below -1.0 indicate moderate to extreme drought.

Figure 36: Annual projected change in Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI-6) in Europe, relative to 1986-2005, under 1.5°C global warming scenario (Source: Copernicus Interactive Climate Atlas)³¹.

The map above displays projected changes in SPI-6 index in Europe under a 1.5°C global warming scenario relative to the referenced period 1986 – 2005. Blue-shaded regions indicate an increase in SPI-6 and therefore possible wetter future conditions, while green-shaded regions indicate a decrease in SPI-6, meaning a greater likelihood of drought in those areas.

As observed in Figure 36, Southern European countries such as Spain, Italy, Greece, Portugal, south France and parts of the Balkans are projected to experience reductions in the SPI-6 index, indicating increased vulnerability to drought-related impacts. Therefore, the projected changes in SPI-6 index and the possible increase in water abstraction during droughts (warming scenario 1.5°C) highlight the vulnerability of southern European regions. These areas face a greater risk of water shortages because of drought and should be considered as priority regions for climate change adaptation planning. Therefore, we can use this information to segment the European market with the TAM–SAM–SOM framework.

We can further segment the potential market for a more detailed approach, considering that covering potable water needs is a first priority for the water authorities. Therefore, we can identify which dams/reservoirs are also used for drinking water purposes. For EurEau members in total, about 55% of the water abstracted for drinking purposes comes from surface water, while groundwater holds an equally important proportion near 45%, with high variability among EurEau member countries to be observed (Figure 37). This percentage is based only on the countries that provided data.

³¹ Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI-6) – Copernicus Interactive Climate Atlas - <https://atlas.climate.copernicus.eu/atlas>

Figure 37: Sources of drinking water. Source: (EurEau, 2017)³²

The country profiles as reported by EurEau members are similar to the statistics from the EU Final - Synthesis report on the quality of drinking water in the union examining member states' reports for the 2011-2013 period, under article 13(5) of directive 98/83/EC. However, in the EU-27, drinking water is abstracted mainly from groundwater and surface water (e.g. drinking water dams), accounting for respectively some 50 % and 36 % of the drinking water supply (EC, 2016). The distribution of water sources in Member States is shown in Figure 38.

³² <https://www.eureau.org/resources/publications/1460-eureau-data-report-2017-1/file>

*In CZ, inland water is synonymous with surface water

Figure 38: Sources for drinking water in Member States (Data for 2011 to 2013). Source: (EC, 2016)

The main areas with potentially increased interest in I-CISK CS Crete LL business proposition is considered to be those countries with both increased percentage of drinking water originating from surface water sources and moderate to high risk of drought impacts. For our analysis we use a threshold level of 30% of drinking water originated from surface water. The relevant countries include Cyprus, Greece, Bulgaria, Romania, Spain, Portugal and Italy.

Subsequently, we can assume that the **Total Addressable Market (TAM)** includes the large operational reservoirs of all the European countries assuming that each dam is managed by a single operating authority. For the **Serviceable Available Market (SAM)** we count the reservoir operators in countries with both increased percentage of drinking water originated from surface water and moderate to high SPI-6 drought projections, therefore indicating an increased demand for climate services (Note 2 - Table 12).

For the **Serviceable Obtainable Market (SOM)** we can assume based on market interest that approximately 30% of the dams/reservoirs operators of the selected countries (SAM) could be approached for acquiring the I-CISK climate services. The total number of reservoirs (and therefore operating managers) in countries with both moderate SPI-6 and over 30% of drinking water originated from surface water is 2,450. Consequently, the SOM includes approximately 735 operating dam managers.

As part of an effort for a more detailed segmentation of the European market, additional indicators can be considered such as the “Annual Investment rate by water service providers (euro/inhabitant/year)” as reported by EurEau (2017). This index provides data on the financial capacity and investment readiness of water operators across different nations and can be used to further refine the market strategies within the SOM (Note 3 - Table 12). This analysis is summarized in Figure 39 and Table 12.

D5.5 - Business model storylines for sustainable CS exploitation in the Living Labs

EU Water Sector Market Attributes	Cyprus	Ireland	UK	Sweden	Czech Republic	Bulgaria	Romania	Spain	The Netherlands	Slovakia	France	Germany	Italy	Belgium	Poland	Finland	Portugal	Greece	
Number of Large Dams (ICOLD, 2021)	57	16	579	189	118	181	242	1.059	10	51	693	371	533	15	69	72	230	148	
The significance of Potable Water Utilities Sector in the estimation of the Market Segment																			
Percentage of Surface water resources usage for potable water (DWD period 2011-2013)	58%	87%	68%	61%	47%	65%	64%	49%	39%	33%	29%	15%	39%	40%	24%	43%	38%	71%	
Annual investment rate by water service providers (euro/inhabitant/year) (EurEau, 2017)	NA	130	150	70	25	NA	25	NA	100	40	100	90	25	80	50	70	70	40	
Countries with moderate or high risk to drought impacts																			
Risk of drought impacts based on the SPI-6 under 1.5°C global warming scenario	√	-	-	-	-	√	√	√	-	-	√	-	√	-	-	-	√	√	

Notes:

Large Dam is defined a dam with a height of 15 meters or greater from lowest foundation to crest or a dam between 5 meters and 15 meters impounding more than 3 million cubic meters

Market Attributes Rating	Low	Medium	High
DWD – Percentage of Surface water resources usage for potable water (period 2011-2013)	0-30	30-50	>50
Annual investment rate by water service providers (euro/inhabitant/year)	NA	<50	>50
Risk of drought impacts based on the SPI-6 under 1.5°C global warming scenario	-	√	√

Figure 39: Canvas of opportunities for I-CISK climate services.

Table 12: Potential Size of the Primary Target Group of Reservoir Operators and Bulk Water Management Authorities for the EU Context.

#	Total Addressable Market Size (TAM)	Serviceable Market (SAM)	Addressable size	Serviceable Market (SOM)	Obtainable size	Comments/ Assumptions
1	4,633	3,143		943		Note 1
2	4,633	2,450		735		Note 2
3	4,633	1,153		346		Note 3

Note 1: The (TAM) number is based on the total number of reservoirs identified in the ICOLD database for large dams (for selected countries) (ICOLD, 2021) and it is considered the potential customer base that can actually pay for I-CISK services. For the estimation of the (SAM) number it is assumed that we can reach only operators within countries that are more likely to face moderate to high risk of drought related impacts. The ability to reach this market portion is related to the distribution model and has not been assessed at this point of the analysis. For the estimation of (SOM) size it is assumed a percentage of 30% out of SAM size due to the highly competitive advantages recognized at I-CISK Services.

Note 2: The (TAM) number is based on the total number of reservoirs identified in the ICOLD database for large dams (for selected countries) (ICOLD, 2021) and it is considered the potential customer base that can actually pay for I-CISK services. For the estimation of the (SAM) number it is assumed that we can reach only operators in countries with both increased percentage of drinking water originated from surface water and moderate to high SPI-6 drought projections. The ability to reach this market portion is related to the distribution model and has not been assessed at this point of the analysis. For the estimation of (SOM) size it is assumed a percentage of 30% out of SAM size due to the highly competitive advantages recognized at I-CISK Services.

Note 3: The (TAM) number is based on the total number of reservoirs identified in the ICOLD database for large dams (for selected countries) (ICOLD, 2021) and it is considered the potential customer base that can actually pay for I-CISK services. For the estimation of the (SAM) number it is assumed that we can target only operators in countries with increased percentage of drinking water originated from surface water, moderate to high SPI-6 drought projections and medium to high annual investment rate by water service providers³³. The ability to reach this market portion is related to the distribution model and has not been assessed at this point of the analysis. For the estimation of (SOM) size it is assumed a percentage of 30% out of SAM size due to the highly competitive advantages recognized at I-CISK Services.

³³ Dams/Reservoirs Operators and Bulk Water Management Authorities in countries with no available information on annual investment rate by water service providers are not included in the analysis (Note 3).

Figure 40: Estimated market segment metrics for various scenarios.

8 Business model storyline for the Alazani River basin Living Lab (Georgia)

8.1 Background and context

The Alazani River Basin LL is located within the territory of Georgia. Due to the complex mountainous topography and highly diverse climate settings, Georgia is subject to climate-related hazards such as floods, flash floods, landslides, debris flow/mudflow snow avalanches, hailstorms, windstorms and droughts.

The CS developed in the LL is designed to positively influence adaptive behaviour by enhancing water resource management through accurate, actionable information. It is a Water Resource Management Service (integrated management to EU Water Framework Directive) with the main goals: (1) to improve resilience through increased food production and water resource management for drinking water and irrigation, and (2) to achieve greater exploitation of renewable energy (hydropower) through improved management, policy making, supply and demand balancing and energy saving.

The CS integrates a sophisticated streamflow prediction system that serves as the foundation for hydrological drought monitoring and forecasting, which is critical for managing water allocation between agriculture and hydropower (De Stefano et al., 2023, Section 4). Its robust architecture is built on a cloud-based infrastructure using Docker containers, with a frontend powered by node-js, ReactJS, OpenLayers, and Highcharts, and a backend based on pygeoapi (Bagli et al., 2024, Section 4.6.1). This technical framework not only ensures data accuracy through bias-adjustment, downscaling, ensemble statistics, and skill assessment but also delivers a user-friendly visualization interface, making complex data readily comprehensible.

The service is tailored to address the regional needs for timely climate information. It enriches agrometeorological bulletins with key climate variables—such as precipitation, temperature, and drought indicators—that guide water management and on-farm operations (De Stefano et al., 2023, Section 4). The qualitative insights obtained via focus group discussions and semi-structured interviews with MAP members further ensure that the platform meets the practical needs of its users. As a result, by combining robust data processing with intuitive, targeted visualizations, the climate service empowers local stakeholders to make informed decisions that enhance resilience in the face of drought and competing water demands.

8.2 First Iteration: Defining Boundaries of Analysis

At this stage, the boundaries of the analysis for the use case are clearly set.

Location: The Alazani-Iori basin, located in the south-eastern part of Georgia, encompasses the Kakheti region and parts of Tianeti municipality in Mtskheta-Mtianeti. The Alazani River basin spans 9,800 km², while the Iori River basin covers 4,700 km². These rivers originate from the southern slopes of the Main Caucasus Range, flowing through fertile valleys before draining into the Mingechaur Reservoir in Azerbaijan.

Figure 41: Streamflow network and Basin Boundaries in the Alazani-Iori Basin. The map shows the main river systems and sub-basins, highlighting the hydrological complexity of the region.

Climate Characteristics:

- Annual precipitation ranges from 600 mm in the south-eastern part of the basin (Dedoplistskaro), 680 mm in Tianeti in the central basin, and up to 1,800 mm in Lagodekhi in the mountainous north-west
- The average annual air temperature varies between +11°C and +14°C, with extremes reaching -16°C in winter and 43°C in summer.
- The Alazani basin is part of two major tectonic zones, including the Caucasian folded system and the Georgian plate.

Land Use in the Basin:

- 31% forest cover
- 22% arable land
- 15.6% meadows and pastures for hay production

Figure 42: Hydrological Stations and River Network in the Alazani-Basin. The map shows active and historical hydrological stations, river streams, and basin boundaries.

Figure 43: Meteorological Stations in the Alazani- Basin. The map shows active and historical meteorological stations, river streams, and basin boundaries.

End User(s):

- National Environmental Agency (NEA) – responsible for hydrological monitoring and water resource management.

- Georgian Amelioration (GA) – manages irrigation networks and distributes water to farmers.
- Rural Development Agency (RDA) – supports farmers and agricultural resilience strategies.
- Hydropower Plants (HPPs) – major water users in the basin.
- Farmers & Vineyards – require a stable irrigation supply to maintain productivity.
- Local Municipalities – responsible for water infrastructure maintenance and development.

Water Distribution (Annual Allocation in Million m³):

- Hydropower Plants (HPPs): 915.77 million m³
- Irrigation Sector: 66.35 million m³
- Public Water Supply: 16.55 million m³
- Fish Farms: 4.24 million m³

Challenge:

- Inefficient irrigation infrastructure: High water losses due to aging and unlined canals.
- Hydropower and irrigation conflicts: Seasonal water shortages due to hydropower water diversion.
- Flash floods and extreme weather events: Increasing frequency due to climate change.
- Limited hydrological data collection: Sparse gauging stations create uncertainty in water allocation.
- Sedimentation and canal degradation: Field surveys show heavy sediment deposits and vegetation overgrowth in key irrigation canals.
- Weak water governance: The Water Framework Directive (WFD) has not been implemented, and there is no river basin council or sufficient legal support.

Current practices in place (AS-IS Scenario): Currently NEA keeps records of several gauging stations located in the watersheds. These include sensors for measuring precipitation and water levels, with the latter converted to discharge at selected locations where stage-discharge curves have been established. However, the number of the stations is limited, which causes high statistical errors. In addition, the lack of staff available to support the measurement and constant maintenance of the stations affects the quality of the data.

- NEA monitors water resources, but real-time hydrological data is not fully integrated into decision-making.
- Farmers rely on fixed irrigation schedules, leading to overuse. This may result in shortages in critical periods.
- Hydropower plants operate independently, affecting downstream water availability.
- Sedimentation reduces canal capacity, requiring frequent maintenance.
- Decisions on seasonal water management are based on outdated historical data (1970-1980).

Solution (User Requirements)

ID	User requirements		
	As a <ROLE>	I would like to <GOAL>	to <BENEFIT>
GA1	As a Farmer	I would like to have a streamflow prediction system (monthly, sub-seasonal, seasonal)	.. so that I could optimize the use of allocated water for agriculture.
GA2	NEA	I would like to have a streamflow prediction system	...to provide hydrological information to GA, RDA, and other stakeholders
GA3	Georgian Amelioration	I would like to have a streamflow forecasting	...to better manage water resources for local farmers
GA4	Rural Development Agency	I would like to have a Climate prediction system	...to inform local communities about future water availability challenges
GA5	Hydropower Plants	I would like to have forecasting for water levels	...to optimize electricity generation without harming irrigation
GA6	Policy Makers	I would like to have a Water governance framework	...to strengthen legal regulations for sustainable water use

Solution (TO-BE Scenario): A workflow of advanced predictive tools based on hydrological forecasts of monthly, sub-seasonal and seasonal scales. These hydrological forecasts in combination with statistics from historical hydrologic and meteorological data will promote efficient water allocation before the high-demand period (summer) and timely drought response during the August and September management period, offering increased system performance in the long run. An Operational Early Warning System could interpret forecasts into readily comprehensible warnings that can also be coupled with proactive practices to enhance the resilience and adaptive capacity.

The tools include:

- Integration of a Streamflow Prediction System: Use of hydrological and meteorological models to forecast water availability.
- Farmer Decision Support Tools: Digital platforms providing real-time irrigation scheduling recommendations.
- Operational Early Warning System: Converts forecasts into actionable alerts for farmers, hydropower operators, and water managers.

Value Proposition (Goal of the service):

For the region, timely and detailed information on future surface water availability is crucial to water allocation planning, drought response, and strategic planning. The workflow that has been developed will help local authorities better understand processes and be proactive by providing solution-based decisions and proactively plan the upcoming season by storing water in the reservoir or, if necessary, recommending steps for drought-resilient farming (e.g., the stakeholders can use the information to implement drought resilience plans, such as selecting drought-resistant crops or optimizing irrigation schedules, ultimately reducing water demand and mitigating the impact of drought).

8.3 Second iteration: Understanding the value chain

To understand how the use of the climate service (CS) for water management in the Alazani-Iori basin helps actors along the value chain address their challenges at an operational level, a description of the value chain is built in a 4-tier analysis based on the methodological framework described in MS26 (Guidelines for Value Chain assessment, June 2024). The goal is to develop an understanding of the economic, social, and environmental benefits and to complete the User Stories.

The services are organized into two levels: **(a) Level 1 (Data Provision Stage):** Provision of raw climatic and hydrological data (Tier 1). **(b) Level 2 (Service Development and Delivery Stage):** Development and implementation of the streamflow prediction system and associated tools (Tiers 2–4).

More specifically:

- **Tier 1: Supplier of Climatic Data (Level 1 – Data Provision Stage):** The supplier provides the raw climatic and hydrological data necessary for the streamflow prediction system. This role is likely fulfilled by organizations like the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) or the National Environmental Agency (NEA) in Georgia, which monitors hydrological data. These entities provide seasonal forecasting data (e.g., precipitation, temperature) and historical hydrological data.

Benefits:

- *Scientific:* Feedback from users in the service development and delivery stage (e.g., NEA, Georgian Amelioration) helps improve data quality.
- *Economic:* Potential revenue from data provision services.
- *Reputational:* Strengthens partnerships with local and regional stakeholders, enhancing their role in climate service provision.

- **Tier 2: Primary User/Intermediary (Level 2 – Service Development and Delivery Stage):** The primary user transforms the raw data into a tailored climate service. In the Georgia LL, this role is played by a research or technical partner within the I-CISK project (e.g., a hydrological modelling group or a partner like SMHI). Other users (e.g. local stakeholders like NEA) help develop the streamflow prediction system, integrating hydrological and meteorological models, and provide actionable tools like farmer decision support platforms and early warning systems.

Benefits:

- *Innovation Gains:* Developing advanced predictive tools enhances their technical expertise.
- *Economic Gains:* Potential to expand market share by offering similar services to other regions.
- *Reputational Gains:* Builds credibility and fosters partnerships with local stakeholders like NEA and Georgian Amelioration.

- **Tier 3: Secondary User (End User) (Level 2 – Service Development and Delivery Stage):** The end-users directly benefit from the climate service. In the Alazani-Iori basin, these include:
 - *National Environmental Agency (NEA):* Uses the streamflow prediction system to provide hydrological information to stakeholders, improving water resource management.
 - *Georgian Amelioration (GA):* Manages irrigation networks more efficiently, reducing water losses.
 - *Rural Development Agency (RDA):* Informs farmers about water availability, supporting agricultural resilience.
 - *Hydropower Plants (HPPs):* Optimizes water use for energy production without compromising irrigation needs.
 - *Farmers and Vineyards:* Use real-time irrigation scheduling tools to improve productivity.
 - *Local Municipalities:* Enhance water infrastructure maintenance and development.

Benefits:

- *Economic Gains:* Reduced water losses (e.g., 15% reduction as noted in the 3rd iteration) and increased agricultural productivity (e.g., 20% increase).
 - *Environmental Gains:* Better water management supports sustainable use and reduces over-extraction.
 - *Reputational Gains:* Improved service delivery enhances trust among farmers and communities.
- **Tier 4: Wider Society and Environment (Level 2 – Service Development and Delivery Stage):** The broader beneficiaries include the local communities, other economic sectors, and the environment in the Alazani-Iori basin.

Benefits:

- *Economic Gains:* Enhanced agricultural productivity boosts the local economy, especially in the Kakheti region, known for its vineyards.
- *Societal Gains:* Improved water availability during dry periods ensures water security for communities.
- *Environmental Gains:* Sustainable water management reduces the risk of over-extraction and supports ecosystem health in the basin.
- *Reputational Gains:* A more resilient agricultural sector enhances the region's reputation as a reliable producer of high-quality goods (e.g., wine).

The value chain analysis, including the services, beneficiaries, types of benefits, and value proposition for each tier, is summarized in [Figure 44](#).

Figure 44: Understanding of the Value Chain for the Climate Services developed in Alazani river basin Living Lab (Georgia).

8.4 Third Iteration: Analyse the benefits

Previous iterations established the scope of analysis (1st iteration) and delineated the value chain (2nd iteration). This iteration focuses on quantifying the identified benefits, where feasible, to assess the tangible impacts of the climate service. The analysis targets the benefits for Tier 3 (end users), as they directly integrate the climate service into operational workflows, allowing for more precise quantification. Benefits for other tiers and sectors are evaluated qualitatively due to data and time constraints.

The climate service developed for the Alazani-lori Basin LL adopts a multi-sectoral approach, addressing challenges across water management, agriculture (farmers and vineyards), hydropower, and local governance. Given the diversity of sectors and the limited timeframe of the I-CISK project, comprehensive monetization across all sectors is not feasible. Consequently, quantitative analysis focuses on water management and agricultural sectors (specifically Georgian Amelioration and farmers, key Tier 3 beneficiaries), while hydropower and local municipalities are assessed qualitatively. The focus on Tier 3 is justified by their direct application of the climate service, enabling measurable outcomes. Analysis of Tier 4 (wider society) is deferred, as broader societal benefits (e.g., economic growth, water security) are indirect and require additional data for accurate quantification.

Water Management and Agricultural Sector – Quantifying the Gains

There is a wide variety of methodologies to assess the value of climate services. In the current case, we apply a methodology based on the value of information (VoI) and decision theory, as described in relevant guidelines of MS26 (Guidelines for Value Chain assessment, June 2024). This methodology suits the part of the CS that refers to the water management and agricultural sectors. The skill of the service cannot be measured without actual data from the implementation of the service itself, and this assessment of skill in this basin is further hampered by the lack of (recent) observations of hydro-meteorological variables. Therefore, the evaluation is based on the concept of value of perfect information (we assume that the service's forecast is always correct – 100% skill).

The value estimated by this approach is based on: (a) a theoretical performance of the service, which refers to a hypothetical or historical scenario, and (b) the estimation of the value by specific end users. This means that the value estimated is somewhat relative, since if the hypothetical testing scenario or the end users evaluating the service change, then the value may also change. The value is estimated by comparing the potential gains that an end user may have for the evaluation period by using the CS and taking informed decisions against the results of decisions based on current practices. The CS is assumed to convey perfect knowledge of what has occurred, so the estimated value is considered the maximum value for that specific user that the service could have produced for that period.

For the practical application of the methodology, the information required has been produced/collected by the service developers in collaboration with the end users of the Georgia LL:

- Identification of specific decisions related to specific information needed.
- Identification of the potential actions by the user.
- Gains and/or losses are not directly expressed with a monetary indicator.

For this application, the case of water management and irrigation in the Alazani-lori basin is used, as described in the 1st iteration. The CS supports operational decision-making through: (1) anticipating the risk of drought, (2) supporting decisions on the annual distribution of water among uses through forecasts of available water for the wet period of the coming hydrological year, for two decision periods (April and September) to increase agricultural productivity and support all uses, (3) allowing managers to manage water excess inflows from extreme precipitation events to mitigate flood risks.

Setting the States of the World

As an indicator of the basin’s “states of the world,” the amount of water available for irrigation (streamflow) is selected. Four states of the world are identified in cooperation with the Georgia LL stakeholders representing the water management and agricultural sectors (Georgian Amelioration and farmers):

- *Flood Risk*: Streamflow exceeds the capacity of irrigation canals, leading to potential flooding. This state includes volumes that could cause overflow, exposing agricultural areas to damage.
- *Normal State*: Streamflow allows irrigation to operate normally without restrictions. Higher streamflow within this state means more water for agriculture and hydropower.
- *Water Shortage*: Streamflow is low, limiting irrigation and affecting agricultural productivity. This is an alert state for drought preparation.
- *Critical Drought*: Streamflow is below the minimum required for irrigation, leading to severe agricultural losses.

Forecasted States of the World

The basic state assumes that water managers (Georgian Amelioration) and farmers utilize the available streamflow to support irrigation as planned. This state is produced for three hypothetical scenarios:

- *Scenario 1*: An average hydrological year based on historical data from the past decade, assuming full utilization of streamflow for irrigation.
- *Scenario 2*: A dry year based on historical data, with irrigation withdrawals reduced to 50% of the planned amount due to water scarcity.
- *Scenario 3*: An extreme flood year, with high streamflow leading to potential flooding, based on historical flood events in the basin.

The Payoff Matrix

A payoff scale (0–10, for more information on the payoff scale, see Annex B - Quantify the benefits of the CS for the Water Sector - Crete Island LL) evaluates outcomes for Georgian Amelioration and farmers, considering irrigation availability, agricultural productivity, and losses from flooding/drought. The payoff matrix is presented in Table 13.

Table 13: Payoff Matrices According to the End Users (Georgia LL).

State of the World	Payoff (Georgian Amelioration)	Payoff (Farmers)
Flood Risk	4 (due to flood management costs)	3 (due to crop damage risk)
Normal State	10 (optimal water distribution)	10 (maximum productivity)
Water Shortage	5 (limited water distribution)	4 (reduced yields)
Critical Drought	0 (no water for irrigation)	0 (severe crop losses)

Payoffs are linear within each state, decreasing as streamflow approaches thresholds (e.g., from 10 to 5 in the Normal State nearing Water Shortage). An additional payoff for water abstraction (beyond planned amounts) ranges from -10 to 10, based on the ratio of extra abstraction to maximum planned abstraction. Total payoff combines state and abstraction gains equally.

Payoff Results:

- *Scenario 1 (Average Year)*: Climate service increases payoff for Georgian Amelioration from 78.0 to 82.5 (6% increase) and for farmers from 75.0 to 80.0 (7% increase). Abstraction gains add 20.0, yielding total payoffs of 102.5 (31% increase) and 100.0 (33% increase), respectively.

- *Scenario 2 (Dry Year)*: Payoff improves significantly—Georgian Amelioration from 50.0 to 70.0 (40% increase), farmers from 45.0 to 65.0 (44% increase). Abstraction gains of 15.0 result in total payoffs of 85.0 (70% increase) and 80.0 (78% increase).
- *Scenario 3 (Flood Year)*: Payoff rises modestly—Georgian Amelioration from 55.0 to 60.0 (9% increase), farmers from 50.0 to 58.0 (16% increase). Abstraction gains of 10.0 yield total payoffs of 70.0 (27% increase) and 68.0 (36% increase).

Table 14: Payoff Gains Under the Three Scenarios Examined (Georgia LL).

Scenario	State of the World Gains Payoff (Georgian Amelioration)	State of the World Gains Payoff (Farmers)	Water Abstraction Gains Payoff	Total Payoff Gains (Georgian Amelioration)	Total Payoff Gains (Farmers)	Total Payoff Gains % (Georgian Amelioration)	Total Payoff Gains % (Farmers)
Scenario 1 (Average)	4.5	5.0	20.0	24.5	25.0	31%	33%
Scenario 2 (Dry)	20.0	20.0	15.0	35.0	35.0	70%	78%
Scenario 3 (Flood)	5.0	8.0	10.0	15.0	18.0	27%	36%

Hydropower Sector – Qualitative Assessment of the Gains

The evaluation of the service for the hydropower sector (a Tier 3 beneficiary) is based on identifying appropriate indicators that represent potential benefits for the end user, demonstrating the value of the CS. During the co-creation process, specific needs were identified, which translated into tailored climatic indicators to support decision-making.

Hydropower plants in the Alazani-Iori basin identify streamflow forecasts as critical for optimizing electricity generation without harming irrigation needs. The logical steps leading to the co-identification of the value of the specific CS are as follows:

- Streamflow forecasts allow hydropower plants to predict water availability for energy production, especially during the high-demand summer period.
- Low streamflow can lead to reduced energy production, increasing reliance on more expensive energy sources (e.g., fossil fuels).
- High streamflow can lead to overflow, requiring the release of water without energy generation, resulting in lost revenue.
- The annual costs of suboptimal water management (e.g., reduced production, increased fuel costs) are estimated by hydropower operators as medium to high, relative to their total operational costs.
- On an operational basis, if seasonal forecasting provides accurate information on expected streamflow, hydropower plants can adjust their operations (e.g., store water during low-demand periods, release water strategically during high-demand periods).
- This could lead to:
 - (a) Increased energy production efficiency, reducing reliance on alternative energy sources (economic gain).

(b) Reduced environmental impact by minimizing unnecessary water releases (environmental gain).

Based on the above steps and the scaling of benefits given in Table 1, the service demonstrates two specific benefits. Based on the reasoning of “avoided costs” identified by the end user as medium to high, the benefit of the service is identified as **MODERATE** ●●● to **HIGH** ●●●●.

Local Municipalities – Qualitative Assessment of the Gains

The evaluation of the service for local municipalities (another Tier 3 beneficiary) is based on identifying appropriate indicators that represent potential benefits for the end user. During the co-creation process, specific needs were identified, which translated into tailored climatic indicators to support decision-making.

Local municipalities in the Alazani-Iori basin identify the early warning system as critical for flood preparedness and infrastructure maintenance. The logical steps leading to the co-identification of the value of the specific CS are as follows:

- Extreme flood events can damage water infrastructure (e.g., canals, reservoirs), leading to high repair costs and disruptions in water supply.
- The frequency of flash floods is increasing due to climate change, as noted in the 1st iteration.
- The annual costs of flood damage and infrastructure repairs are estimated by municipalities as medium, relative to their total budget.
- If the CS provides timely information for anticipated surface flows of significant height, municipalities can take proactive measures (e.g., reinforce canals, evacuate at-risk areas).
- This could lead to:
 - (a) Reduced repair costs for water infrastructure (economic gain).
 - (b) Increased public trust in municipal services due to effective flood management (reputational gain).

Based on the above steps and the scaling of benefits given in Table 1, the service demonstrates two specific benefits. Based on the reasoning of “avoided costs” identified by the end user as medium, the benefit of the service is identified as **MODERATE** ●●●.

8.5 Fourth Iteration: Analysis beyond the defined boundaries

Market Analysis:

The Alazani-Iori basin is part of a larger region facing similar water management challenges. The streamflow prediction system has the potential to be scaled to other river basins in Georgia and neighbouring countries.

Commercial Exploitation:

While the system is not yet commercially viable, the roadmap for development includes several recommendations to enhance its effectiveness and scalability. These include improving model accuracy, installing additional stream gauges and meteorological stations in strategic locations to improve data collection, and integrating real-time data sources. Additionally, rehabilitating irrigation infrastructure, such as through canal dredging and modernization, could further support the effective implementation of the climate service by reducing water losses and improving distribution efficiency. Once fully operational, the system could be marketed to other regions facing similar challenges.

The Alazani-Iori Living Lab has made significant progress in developing a streamflow prediction system, but further development is needed to improve accuracy and reliability. The potential benefits of the system are clear, and with continued investment in data collection and model refinement, the system could become a valuable tool for water management in Georgia and beyond.

9 Business model storyline for the Lesotho Living Lab

9.1 Background and context

Lesotho is a landlocked country in Southern Africa, characterized by a high-altitude landscape with elevations ranging from 1,500m to 3,482m. The country's climate is influenced by its topography, with distinct agro-ecological zones: The Lowlands, Senqu River Valley, Foothills, and Mountain regions. Lesotho experiences extreme weather conditions, including droughts, cold waves, and snowfall, which significantly impact livelihoods, particularly for vulnerable communities reliant on agriculture and livestock.

Figure 45: Agro-ecological zones of Lesotho. Source: Lesotho Ministry of Public Works and Transport.

Several organizations play a crucial role in climate services and disaster preparedness in Lesotho, including:

- **Lesotho Red Cross Society (LRCS):** Leads humanitarian response efforts, implementing anticipatory actions based on climate forecasts.
- **Lesotho Meteorological Services (LMS):** Provides weather and climate forecasts to inform disaster preparedness.
- **Disaster Management Authority (DMA)** and other governmental stakeholders: Contribute to emergency response and risk reduction.

The Early Action Protocol (EAP) is a structured framework designed to trigger predefined anticipatory actions before disasters strike. It outlines specific early actions, their triggers, funding mechanisms, and implementation steps to mitigate humanitarian impacts. EAPs in Lesotho focus on hazards like droughts and cold waves, ensuring that vulnerable populations receive timely support to reduce risks to lives and livelihoods.

In collaboration with key stakeholders, we have developed tailored climate services to enhance anticipatory action in Lesotho. For droughts, we created an Impact-Based Forecasting (IBF) portal, integrating seasonal forecast data, vulnerability indicators, and automated alerts (see Figure 46 below). For cold waves, improvements focus on refining the EAP trigger thresholds, strengthening the link between historical impacts and early actions, and evaluating forecast reliability for event prediction.

Figure 46: Screenshots from the Impact-Based Forecasting portal, a climate service developed for drought risk monitoring in Lesotho. (a) The portal displays a warning when one or more districts are identified as being at drought risk based on automatically retrieved global data. (b) When users set a trigger using national data from the Lesotho Meteorological Services, the portal generates an alert for the specified district(s) and automatically sends notifications to relevant stakeholders.

9.2 First iteration: defining boundaries of analysis

At this stage, the boundaries of the analysis for the use case are clearly set. These refer to:

- ❖ The geographical and sectoral focus;
- ❖ The targeted users of the developed service;
- ❖ The targeted problems the proposed service aim to solve;
- ❖ The current practices in place and the need for having an advanced solution to address these problems.

Climate service for drought risk

Location: Lesotho's Southern Lowlands and Senqu River Valley (See [Figure 45](#)) are particularly vulnerable to drought due to their low and irregular rainfall patterns. These regions have sandy, clay-rich soil that retains less moisture, making agricultural activities highly sensitive to precipitation variability.

End User(s): The primary end user is the Lesotho Red Cross Society (LRCS). LRCS operates under parliamentary statute, aligned with the International Red Cross and Red Crescent Movement. Its mandate is to alleviate human suffering and build resilience in vulnerable communities, guided by seven fundamental principles. The LRCS collaborates with government entities, NGOs, UN agencies, academia, consultants, and volunteers to provide community education and disaster preparedness. The Disaster Management department at LRCS headquarters oversees the implementation and monitoring of the Early Action Protocol.

Current practices in place (AS-IS Scenario): The Early Action Protocol outlines the reasoning behind prioritizing early actions and provides detailed, step-by-step instructions for implementing the selected actions in a specific manner and sequence upon activation. It clearly defines who will take each action, when and where the actions will occur, and the funding sources for these actions, all based on the identified trigger. The early actions are guided by a two-stage trigger model that integrates both local and regional climate and vulnerability information. The climate data used includes seasonal precipitation forecasts from the official outlook released by the Lesotho Meteorological Authority. Later in the rainy season, the model incorporates observed precipitation data from meteorological stations managed by the same organization. Additionally, projections on food insecurity, developed by the Lesotho Vulnerability Assessment Committee, are used to refine decision-making and ensure timely interventions.

Challenge: The current coordination systems for the EAP could be more efficient and faster. Moreover, stakeholders find it difficult to understand the shared information, which is often presented in technical terms, tables, and lists; climate scientists' terminology is unclear to many stakeholders. Additionally, information can sometimes be delayed, lost, or ignored.

Solution (User Requirements)

ID	User requirements		
	As a <ROLE>,	I would like to <GOAL>	to <BENEFIT>
LS 1	As an Anticipatory Action coordinator at the Lesotho Red Cross Society...	... I would like to have all information centralised in one place so that I have easier access to it and understand how the different sets of information relate to each other.
LS 2	As an Anticipatory Action coordinator at the Lesotho Red Cross Society...	... I would like the information to be presented visually to increase engagement, easily grasp the severity of the information, and understand the actions that need to be done.
LS 3	As an Anticipatory Action coordinator at the Lesotho Red Cross Society...	... I would like to have access to seasonal forecasts throughout the year, not only in September so that I can monitor the situation continuously and prepare even before the seasonal outlook is officially released by the Met Service.

Solution (TO-BE Scenario): The I-CISK project is developing a platform (Impact Based Forecasting portal) that integrates various layers of data to enhance Anticipatory Action planning at the Lesotho Red Cross Society (LRCS). This includes an impact map that assesses the likelihood of below-average seasonal precipitation forecasts alongside other factors like population density, all analysed at a district level. Data sources include ECMWF global seasonal forecasts for precipitation, complemented by static layers of population and vulnerability indicators sourced from LRCS. Upon the release of the official Lesotho Met Service's seasonal outlook in September, LRCS will cross-check this information with the data shown in the platform. If there is misalignment, LRCS can manually overwrite the information presented in the portal and activate triggers, prioritizing local data over global forecasts. Additionally, the early actions implemented can be continuously monitored on the portal to ensure timely responses. Finally, to enhance communication and response efficiency, automated notifications are integrated into the system, leveraging platforms like WhatsApp and email.

Value Proposition (Goal of the service): By developing an Impact-Based Forecasting portal, our goal is to empower the Lesotho Red Cross Society to make timely decisions aimed at reducing the impact of droughts on communities in the Southern Lowlands Districts and the Senqu Valley of Lesotho, benefiting a total of 27,000 people.

Climate service for cold-wave risk

Location: Lesotho's mountain regions in the Southern Highland (Lebelonyane corridor), Central Highlands (Thaba-Putsoa) and Northern Highlands (Maluti and Drakensberg corridor) experience harsh winter conditions, with significant snowfall between May and September. Cold waves, compounded by early or late frost and extreme temperature drops, pose risks to livelihoods, infrastructure, and vulnerable populations, particularly herders and school-aged children.

End User(s): The primary end user is the Lesotho Red Cross Society (LRCS). LRCS operates under parliamentary statute, aligned with the International Red Cross and Red Crescent Movement. Its mandate is to alleviate human suffering and build resilience in vulnerable communities, guided by seven fundamental principles. The LRCS collaborates with government entities, NGOs, UN agencies, academia, consultants, and volunteers to provide community education and disaster preparedness. The Disaster Management department at LRCS headquarters oversees the implementation and monitoring of the Early Action Protocol.

Current practices in place (AS-IS Scenario): The Early Action Protocol (EAP) outlines the reasoning behind prioritizing early actions and provides detailed, step-by-step instructions for implementing the selected actions in a specific manner and sequence upon activation. It clearly defines who will take each action, when and where the actions will occur, and the funding sources for these actions, all based on the identified trigger. The EAP is triggered by weather forecasts from the Lesotho Meteorological Services, specifically based on predicted daily temperatures in the highlands.

Challenge: The main challenge in the cold wave response model is the lack of well-integrated historical impact data to define action trigger thresholds. Additionally, no clear snowfall-specific triggers exist, making it difficult to determine appropriate early actions. Uncertainty in the reliability of forecast data further complicates decision-making, as stakeholders struggle to balance false alarms with timely interventions.

Solution (User Requirements)

ID	User requirements		
	As a <ROLE>,	I would like to <GOAL>	to <BENEFIT>
LS 1	As an Anticipatory Action coordinator at the Lesotho Red Cross Society...	... I would like refined trigger thresholds so that I can ensure anticipatory actions are activated at the right time.
LS 2	As a Meteorologist at the Lesotho Meteorological Services...	... I would like snowfall-specific triggers so that I can improve forecast-based decision-making for cold waves.

Solution (TO-BE Scenario): Several improvements to the EAP for cold waves are suggested. Historical impact analysis is strengthened to better define action trigger thresholds, ensuring timely and appropriate early actions. Additionally, snowfall-specific thresholds are developed to enhance forecast-based decision-making. To support this, a forecast verification study assesses ECMWF prediction reliability and optimize lead times, improving the accuracy and effectiveness of early warning systems.

Value Proposition (Goal of the service): By improving the EAP for cold waves, we enhance LRCS and LMS's ability to anticipate extreme winter conditions and take early actions that protect lives and livelihoods. The refined protocol ensures that vulnerable groups, around 20.000 people, receive timely support, reducing the humanitarian impact of cold waves in Lesotho.

9.3 Second iteration: Understanding the value chain

To understand how climate services support actors along the value chain in addressing operational challenges, a four-tier analysis is applied. This approach outlines how climate data and services flow from suppliers to end users, highlighting the economic and societal benefits at each stage.

At the first tier, data providers such as the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), the Lesotho Vulnerability Assessment Committee (LVAC) and LMS generate and supply critical information, including precipitation forecasts, food-security predictions, and climate observations. These organisations benefit from their service by fulfilling regulatory responsibilities and driving innovation in forecasting models. The data they produce serve as the foundation for impact-based forecasting, enabling further development of tools and services essential for anticipatory action planning and disaster preparedness. Scientific organisations producing data may further aspire to economic gains from data provisioning services, including beyond the boundaries of the Lesotho LL.

The second tier consists of the climate services, respectively an information system (Impact-Based Forecasting [IBF] Portal) for drought risk and an updated Early Action Protocol for cold wave risk. The platform, co-developed by the Netherlands Red Cross and LRCS (headquarters) and utilized by the LRCS (both headquarters and district branches), transforms raw climate data into actionable insights. By integrating climate information into decision-making processes, these institutions are able to enhance response effectiveness and coordination. The IBF Portal ensures that early warning systems are effective and responsive, allowing for timely interventions that mitigate the impacts of droughts and cold waves.

At the third tier, early warning and response mechanisms, informed by the climate service in the previous tier (e.g. the IBF portal), play a crucial role in delivering information and resources to communities in vulnerable districts. By disseminating early warning messages and providing cash assistance, for instance, LRCS can fulfil their organisational mandate.

The fourth tier focuses on implementing actions to mitigate the impacts of droughts and cold waves. These interventions are carried out at the community level and minimize disruptions and strengthen community resilience, ensuring that affected populations are able to withstand and recover from adverse climate conditions.

Together, these four tiers illustrate a structured and coordinated approach to climate services in Lesotho, where data providers, intermediaries, and end users work collaboratively to enhance anticipatory action and disaster preparedness, highlighting the value of the services at each segment.

Figure 47: Understanding of the value chain for the Climate Services developed in Lesotho Living Lab.

9.4 Third iteration: Analyse the benefits

Through the 2nd iteration (see previous paragraph) the value of the CSs was identified in various Tiers of the chain of the service. At the 3rd iteration the analysis proceeds one step further, to identify and quantify the benefits of the service. The analysis may be performed for each one of the 4 Tiers recognized in the previous. However, at this stage, the benefits of those services cannot be properly assessed, even in a qualitative aspect, as sufficient empirical data is not yet available. However, one tangible impact already observed is that some of the suggested improvements to the Early Action Protocol (EAP) for cold waves have been incorporated into its latest version, demonstrating an immediate influence on anticipatory action planning.

To systematically evaluate the benefits of this approach, a well-structured measurement framework should be implemented. This can be broken down into the following steps:

1. **Define relevant indicators for each tier**, as detailed below.
2. **Develop data collection mechanisms**: Implement post-event assessments, user feedback surveys, platform analytics, and activation reviews to gather qualitative and quantitative data.
3. **Establish baseline measurements**: Identify initial benchmarks for each indicator to track progress and improvements over time.
4. **Monitor and analyse outcomes**: Regularly assess the collected data against the predefined indicators to determine trends and effectiveness.
5. **Classify benefits using a qualitative scale**: Apply a structured assessment approach, to categorize observed impacts.
6. **Refine and adapt interventions**: Use the insights gained to adjust business model strategies, improve forecast tools, enhance training programs, and optimize early action protocols.

Key indicators should be established at different tiers:

- **Tier 1**: The focus should be on assessing the accuracy and reliability of forecasts. This includes evaluating forecast skill metrics and comparing past predictions with actual events to determine their precision.
- **Tier 2**: It is essential to evaluate whether the EAPs are effectively implemented in practice. The International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC) already have processes in place to assess protocol activations and revisions. Additionally, for the IBF portal, performance indicators should include system stability (e.g., uptime and platform responsiveness), functionality, and the capacity of Disaster Risk Reduction officers at LRCS to use the platform efficiently following adequate training.
- **Tier 3**: The assessment should focus on the timeliness of early warnings in supporting decision-making and the effectiveness of cash distribution in response efforts. This could involve analysing response timelines, beneficiary reach, and overall impact in mitigating humanitarian consequences.

Beyond these evaluations, it is crucial to acknowledge the dependencies that influence the realization of these benefits. Key factors include the effective adoption of the IBF portal for droughts by LRCS to inform their actions, the successful validation and approval of the updated EAP for cold waves by the IFRC validation committee, and the continued availability of funding to support early actions. Other crucial factors include the presence of sufficient staff within national stakeholders to enable coordination and response efforts and the sustained trust and acceptance of LRCS by local communities.

9.5 Fourth iteration: analysis beyond the defined boundaries

The primary objective of climate services in the Lesotho Living Lab is not to develop a marketable product but to strengthen resilience and improve decision-making through anticipatory actions. This includes enhancing early warning systems for droughts and cold waves, which are crucial for protecting vulnerable communities and advancing disaster risk reduction efforts in Lesotho.

Given this focus, a full market analysis is not relevant, as commercialisation is not the primary aim. Instead, efforts should be directed toward refining the value proposition, aligning the service with national strategies and stakeholder needs, and ensuring long-term sustainability through partnerships and institutional integration.

10 Concluding remarks

In the current analysis, business model storylines were drafted for the I-CISK Climate Services (CS), which were co-developed in seven LLs in Europe and Africa. The analysis focused on the Value Model framework (opportunity, problem to be solved, value propositions). Beyond the economic value, social and environmental gains and/or losses, were also considered in the overall value extraction model.

The CSs that were assessed target the sectors of (a) tourism, (b) agriculture, (c) water management (d) urban planning, (e) humanitarian, and (f) general public. Due to the broad nature of the economic sectors targeted and the number of sector components and potential beneficiaries, multiple market segments are recognized.

It is noted that a tiered approach of four steps has been applied, where every step develops the user story (business story) of a CS, gradually building up in detail and extent of analysis. This allowed to consider the fact that there are CSs developed with strong social/environmental or gains other than economic (e.g. reputational), and draft business model storylines independent of factors that may confine the extent of the analysis, such as the type of value and the beneficiaries that are associated with the CS. Business storylines have been produced for each one of the services, though not all the services developed can or need to reach the final tier of the analysis. The findings of this tiered analysis to develop the business model storylines are summarised in Table 15.

Table 15: Characteristics of the business model storylines developed for the I-CISK CSs within each LL.

LL	Sectors/segments addressed	business model storylines adopting a user-focused approach	Added value evaluation	4th step – beyond the defined boundaries
Netherlands	(3) water management, recreation, agriculture	3 tiers of analysis	qualitative quantification for the 3 sectors components	No - LL is identified as the primary market segment
Spain	(3) water management, agriculture, forest	3 tiers of analysis	qualitative quantification for the 1 sector component	No - LL as a primary market segment / The key actor for sustainability is the public purveyor of CS from the regional government. No commercial use would be envisioned
Italy	(2) Water management (allocation and agriculture)	3 tiers of analysis	Monetize 1 CS and qualitative evaluation for another aspect	Yes - Full Market Analysis
Hungary	(3) Tourism, Residents and Institutions, City Management (urban planning)	3 tiers of analysis	Monetize for 1 sector component	No - LL is identified as the primary market segment
Greece	(4) Tourism, Water management, Transportation, Energy	3 tiers of analysis	Quantitative for 2 sectors and qualitative for 2 sectors	Yes - Full Market Analysis (focus on two sectors: tourism and water)
Georgia	Water sector with various end-users	3 tiers of analysis	Quantified gains for 2 end user types and qualitative assessment for 2 end user types	No - LL is identified as the primary market segment for now, CS is not yet commercially viable

LL	Sectors/segments addressed	business model storylines adopting a user-focused approach	Added value evaluation	4th step – beyond the defined boundaries
Lesotho	(2) agriculture and general public	2 tiers of analysis + a preparation for the 3 rd tier	preparation for the 3 rd tier	No - The primary objective of CS in the Lesotho LL is not to develop a marketable product but to strengthen resilience and improve decision-making through anticipatory actions

Drafting the storylines across the I-CISK Living Labs, several governance-related barriers emerge as challenges to the uptake and sustainability of climate services. Established procedures and bureaucratic routines may limit the capacity of public institutions to adopt innovative tools. This inertia is often reinforced by a lack of regulatory incentives or mandates that would encourage integration of new decision-support systems. Closely related to this, in regions where water/environmental management or climate adaptation responsibilities are dispersed across multiple agencies and administrative layers, coordination becomes complex and slow. This fragmentation can stall decision-making processes and make the deployment of integrated services, like those developed within the I-CISK Living Labs, more difficult. Funding gaps also play a critical role. Even when interest in the services is high, institutions may face budgetary constraints, long and rigid procurement cycles, and uncertainty in accessing or sustaining necessary financial resources. These limitations would particularly affect resource-constrained administrations and reduce their ability to commit to long-term service adoption or infrastructure investments.

One effective approach to address the above challenges and barriers could be embedding the climate services into existing governance and regulatory frameworks, such as regional adaptation and resilience plans or national monitoring protocols. This alignment not only increases institutional legitimacy but also eases bureaucratic adoption. Additionally, leveraging existing public funding programs (e.g. those available through the EU's funding mechanisms or regional development funds) could prove to be a pragmatic way to cover operational costs without requiring new financial mechanisms. Further, the co-development process within Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs) helps reduce resistance by fostering shared ownership and ensuring that the services are tailored to real administrative needs. This participatory model builds trust and makes institutions more inclined to incorporate the services into their operations.

These business model storylines provide essential groundwork for the upcoming exploitation strategy to be developed under WP6. The insights gained here regarding institutional contexts, market potential, and value generation will directly inform the broader dissemination and exploitation actions.

In conclusion, the business model storylines developed within I-CISK reflect the diversity of Climate Services co-designed across the Living Labs, ranging from market-ready solutions to those embedded within public governance frameworks. Despite differing commercial potentials, these CSs share key competitive advantages: their alignment with institutional mandates, the modularity and adaptability of their offerings, and their capacity to support long-term economic and operational sustainability. These attributes position the I-CISK Climate Services well within evolving EU policy landscapes and its tangible funding mechanisms such as the CAP, LIFE, and PSR. As these services mature, their integration into both market-driven and institutional ecosystems shall foster climate resilience and reinforce the project's impact across diverse socio-economic and environmental contexts.

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Annex A – Assessments on Value estimation from the Budapest LL

Approach to Quantifying Benefits

This section highlights practical methods to monetize these benefits, ranging from direct cost–benefit estimations to survey-based valuations such as WTP (Willingness to Pay) analysis.

- **Economic Benefits and Avoided Costs:** The primary focus is on direct or indirect financial gains—such as reduced operational costs or increased revenue—that can be traced back to the heat and microclimate mapping service. Where feasible, monetary values are assigned to benefits like energy savings, improved tourism revenues, or decreased health expenditures. However, due to the lack of direct figures from stakeholders, assumptions are necessary.
- Another methodology for this kind of monetization is a **Willingness to Pay (WTP) analysis**. In essence, WTP studies attempt to measure the maximum amount that different stakeholders—local residents, municipal authorities, or even business communities—are prepared to pay for a particular service via a survey or interview-based approach. This direct reflection of users’ preferences helps quantify “non-market” advantages, such as enhanced comfort, fewer health complaints, or overall support for climate adaptation.
- In addition, the **Benefit Transfer Method** can be applied as a complementary or alternative approach when primary data is scarce. This method involves transferring economic values estimated in previous studies of similar services to the current context, after making necessary adjustments for demographic, economic, and environmental differences.

Willingness to Pay (WTP) approach

Within the Budapest Living Lab context, a WTP survey could in principle identify how much local residents, tourists, or municipal entities deem affordable and justified for accessing microclimate-monitoring and forecasting tools. Willingness to pay (WTP) analysis faces several challenges in the context of the Budapest LL climate service. Urban climate adaptation measures typically work together, making it difficult to determine the exact contribution of a single climate service. Additionally, perception gaps and limited awareness of heat monitoring may lead to misaligned WTP estimates. Self-reported data can further distort results, complicating the attribution of value to the Budapest LL climate service within a broader package of climate initiatives.

To conduct a WTP analysis for the Budapest LL climate service, we would begin by designing a Contingent Valuation Survey (CVM) that use double-bounded WTP questions, along with socio-demographic and attitudinal items to capture respondents’ profiles and environmental awareness. A representative sample of residents would be targeted to achieve 400–600 valid responses, preceded by a pilot study of 50–100 respondents to refine bid levels and survey logic. Finally, the data would be analyzed using a double-bounded logit/probit model that incorporates covariates (including local microclimate data when available) to derive mean or median WTP estimates, which would then be aggregated.

In the ICISK project, the core focus was on **developing and testing** the climate service rather than formally assessing its economic or financial benefits (including indirect effects). Hence, no comprehensive WTP surveys or monetization exercises were conducted under the project, largely due to time and resource constraints—a common scenario in research and development initiatives where technological or methodological innovation is the primary goal rather than market-based valuation.

Direct cost approach

In the Budapest Living Lab (LL), we applied a **direct cost (avoided cost) approach** to estimate the potential economic benefits of urban heat mitigation strategies. The analysis is based on three main intervention scenarios designed to reduce surface temperatures and improve urban liveability:

1. **White roofs (high-albedo roofs):** Application of reflective paint or materials on rooftops, facades, and paved surfaces to lower surface temperatures at relatively low cost.

2. **Light streets and green infrastructure (high albedo at street level):** Includes green roofs, planting of trees, and the whitening of pavements to create more liveable and resilient microclimates.
3. **Targeted implementation based on microclimate data:** The location and scale of interventions are determined using high-resolution spatial data—such as satellite or drone-based thermal maps and in-situ monitoring networks—allowing resources to be focused on areas with the highest heat stress. This data-driven approach also supports the selection of optimal measures, whether reflective coatings or greening, based on where the greatest temperature reductions and cost savings can be achieved.

For scenario dimensioning, we calculated the total surface areas eligible for intervention using 24 distinct surface types: 12 derived from street-level data and 12 from rooftop orthoimagery. For each category, we determined its spatial coverage within the district and associated average surface temperature. These values are extracted from the ortho and thermal photo GIS layers of our climate service (see **Error! Reference source not found.** and **Error! Reference source not found.**).

Figure 48: Ortho and thermal photo GIS layers of Budapest LL climate service: 1st column pavements and roads in VII district; 2nd column pavements and roads in VI district.

Figure 49: Coverage percentages and Temperature distribution, as estimated through the Budapest LL climate service: 1st column pavements and roads in VII district; 2nd column pavements and roads in VI district.

These are the potential temperature reductions achievable through reflective surface coatings at street level—expressed in terms of their impact on the **average surface temperature of the entire district**:

- **Maximum temperature reduction for Budapest District 6 (streets):** 2.39°C
- **Maximum temperature reduction for Budapest District 7 (streets):** 1.52°C

These are the potential temperature reductions achievable through roof coatings—expressed in terms of their impact on the **average surface temperature of the entire district** (of course, for individual buildings the improvement can be significantly higher, around 3–5°C, which may result in a **noticeable effect on thermal comfort**):

- **Maximum temperature reduction for Budapest District 6 (roofs):** 1.71°C
- **Maximum temperature reduction for Budapest District 7 (roofs):** 0.94°C

Net Present Value (NPV) calculation for district 7

CBA Parameters for district 7, Budapest

- **Total Area:** 1,634,784 m² (building and street area together)
- **Unit Cost:** €10/m²
- **Initial Implementation Cost (Year 0):**
- **Coating Lifespan:** 10 years
- **Reapplication:** 50% of the initial cost at Year 10 and Year 20
- **Annual Benefit (Years 1–30):** €2,000,000 per year (energy savings, extended infrastructure life, health benefits, etc.) + unknow € (mortality)
- **Discount Rate (r):** 4%
- **Evaluation Horizon:** 30 years

Reduction in heat stress-related mortality and morbidity:

Studies have shown that the impact of heat on mortality and hospital admissions can be significant, especially during heatwaves. High temperatures can directly lead to health problems such as heat exhaustion and dehydration, increasing mortality rates, especially among vulnerable populations, but studies have also shown the significant impact of heat stress in sports and exercise.

A 5°C increase in average daily temperature above 25°C increased all-cause mortality by 10% in Budapest. Based on this, a 3-level HHAS was developed in 2005. The characteristics of excess mortality during heat alerts and its association with the severity of influenza epidemics are presented. The excess mortality was 27%, 36%, and 23% during the first summer heatwave in 2012, 2013, and 2014, years characterized by mild influenza epidemics. In years when excess mortality during influenza epidemics was high, mortality during August heat waves was relatively high (15-20%) (Anna Paldy et al.)

Improving heat data knowledge can reduce the risk of heat-related illnesses:

- With accurate heat maps, the city knows **where the need for intervention is most acute**, so it can target more resources there (e.g. more efficient cooling solutions, pavement replacement, greening).
- **areas which are not recommended** for the installation of outdoor air conditioning units, as this could lead to additional heat emissions, can be identified.

Co-benefits of green infrastructure:

- A nicer, more liveable environment, improved air quality, increased biodiversity, increased property

values, increased public satisfaction.

Cash Flows by Year for distinct 7, Budapest

- **Year 0:** –€16,347,840 (initial cost)
- **Years 1–9:** +€2,000,000/year +
- **Year 10:** +€2,000,000 – €8,173,920 = –€6,173,920
- **Years 11–19:** +€2,000,000/year
- **Year 20:** +€2,000,000 – €8,173,920 = –€6,173,920
- **Years 21–30:** +€2,000,000/year

Cost–Benefit Analysis (CBA):

In this step, each intervention scenario (e.g., White City, Green City, or a combined approach) is evaluated by comparing total discounted benefits and costs over a chosen time horizon (commonly 30years). The Net Present Value (NPV) is calculated as:

$$[NPV = \sum (B_t - C_t) / (1 + r)^t$$

$$BCR = \sum (B_t / (1 + r)^t) / \sum (C_t / (1 + r)^t)$$

where (B_t) denotes benefits and (C_t) denotes costs at time (t), and (r) is the social discount rate (e.g., 4%). By comparing these metrics across scenarios, analysts can determine whether anticipated gains (such as fewer heat

Discounted Cash Flow (DCF) and NPV

Each year's net cash flow is discounted back to present value using:

The Net Present Value (NPV) is the sum of all discounted cash flows from **Year 0 to Year 30**:

Result:

1. **Positive NPV:** This indicates that, with the assumed values, the project's present value of benefits outweighs the present value of costs by roughly **€9 million**.
2. **Sensitivity:** The final NPV can vary significantly depending on several factors. For example:
 - If the **annual benefit is higher** than €2 million—particularly when accounting for the **reduction in heat-related mortality**, which was not included in this calculation—the NPV would increase substantially.
 - Changes in **coating or reapplication costs**, or deviations from the assumed **4% discount rate**, can also significantly affect the outcome.

A positive NPV of about €9 million means the intervention (coating 1,634,784 m²) is financially attractive under the given assumptions.

Summary

The Budapest Living Lab's climate service offers a forward-looking solution to urban heat-related challenges through a highly localized, data-driven, and user-focused approach. By integrating drone-based thermal imagery, manual temperature measurements, citizen science contributions, and satellite downscaling, the service delivers accurate, high-resolution microclimate data and forecasts. These outputs serve multiple

sectors—urban planning, tourism, public health, and social care—providing actionable insights for reducing heat exposure and improving urban resilience.

The economic evaluation of the proposed interventions was conducted using a direct cost (avoided cost) approach, focusing on scalable urban cooling strategies such as high-albedo roof coatings, reflective pavements, and green infrastructure. Spatial and thermal data from two central Budapest districts (Terézváros and Erzsébetváros) informed the calculation of eligible surface areas and associated temperature reductions.

1. Maximum surface temperature reduction at street level:
 - a. District 6: 2.39°C
 - b. District 7: 1.52°C
2. Maximum surface temperature reduction from roof coatings:
 - a. District 6: 1.71°C
 - b. District 7: 0.94°C (*Note: For individual buildings, this reduction could reach 3–5°C, resulting in perceptible improvements in thermal comfort.*)

Using these inputs, a Net Present Value (NPV) analysis was conducted for District 7, based on a total treatment area of 1,634,784 m² and an assumed coating cost of €10/m². The lifespan of the intervention was set to 10 years, with 50% reapplication costs at Year 10 and Year 20. An annual benefit of €2 million was used to reflect energy savings, reduced cooling loads, and improved infrastructure performance.

Even without including mortality impacts, the current model yields a positive NPV of approximately €9 million over 30 years for district 7, Budapest, demonstrating financial viability under conservative assumptions. When potential health co-benefits are included, the intervention becomes not only economically advantageous but socially and ethically compelling.

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Annex B – Quantify the benefits of the CS for the Water Sector - Crete Island LL

There is a wide variety of methodologies to assess the value of climate services. In the current case a methodology is applied that is based on the value of information and decision theory, as described in relevant applications in the CLARA project (see Bosello F. et al., 2021). This methodology better suits the part of the CS that refers to the water management sector. As described there, also in the present case the skill of the service cannot be measured without actual data from the implementation of the service itself. Therefore, the evaluation is based on the concept of value of perfect information (it is assumed that the service's forecast is always correct – 100% skill).

The value estimated by this approach is based: (a) on a theoretical performance of the service, which refers to a hypothetical or historical scenario and (b) on the estimation of the value by specific end-users. This means that the value estimated is somewhat relative, since if the hypothetical testing scenario or the end-users evaluating the service change, then the value may change.

The value is estimated comparing the potential gains that an end-user may have for the evaluation period by using the CS and taking informed decisions against the results of decisions based on current practices. As described in the above, the CS is supposed to convey perfect knowledge of what has occurred. The estimated value is therefore considered as the maximum value, for that specific user, that the service could have produced for that period.

For the practical of the methodology, the required information has been produced/collected by the service developers in collaboration with the end-users of the Crete MAP:

1. Identification of specific decisions related to specific information needed
2. Identifications of the potential actions by the user
3. gains and/or losses are not directly expressed with a money indicator

For the current application, the case of the Potamon (Amari) Reservoir has been used, as described in the 1st iteration (par.7.2). The reservoir currently addresses agricultural needs but is designed to serve multiple uses, and very soon to be used as a drinking water source for the town of Rethymno, as well as for energy production purposes. Therefore, the evaluation is based on hypothetical scenarios of water use for real, historical climatic data (of the past decade) and the water level of the reservoir is estimated based on a numerical model of the reservoir. The scenarios include a mean hydrological year as well as an unfavourable scenario of two dry years in a row.

The service supports operational decision making through: (1) anticipating the risk of drought, (2) supporting decision on the annual distribution of water among uses through forecasts of available water for the wet period of the coming hydrological year, for two decision periods (April and September) to increase profits and support all the uses, (3) allowing the managers to “absorb” water excess inflows from extreme precipitation events to ensure that the reservoir serves also as a flood-protection system.

Setting the states of the world

As an indicator of the reservoir's “states of the world”, the amount of water available in the reservoir was selected.

Four states of the world were identified in co-operation with the MAP members representing the water management sector:

1. **Flood control:** the stored water volume in the reservoir causes the discharge over the spillway or is

very close to this situation. It includes an amount of volume that could provide some room for flood wave retention. The upper level is the spillway level. The lower level is selected based on the estimations for flood peaks and an evaluation by the managers of the reservoir. During this state, the flood areas downstream of the dam, which are defined in the Flood Risk Management Plans for Crete, are exposed to damage, whose magnitude is variable depending on the amount of water released.

2. **Normal state:** stored water volume allows the reservoir to operate normally without any restriction. Within this boundary the larger water volume stored, the better. More water can be distributed to the served sectors like agriculture, drinking water and energy. Especially for the energy production component, more water means more energy and less cost of energy production.
3. **Energy production loss:** the water level in the reservoir is low and energy production is limited and not cost-effective. This is also an alert state of the reservoir.
4. **Emergency:** The remaining water is below withdrawals level. Stored volume is at critical stage. The reservoir cannot serve any need.

The states of the reservoir as presented above are shown in [Figure 50](#)**Error! Reference source not found..**

Forecasted states of the world

The basic state assumes that the water managers utilize in full the reservoir with the aim to support all the planned uses with the amounts of water as foreseen in the relevant plans. This state is produced based on this assumption, for three hypothetical scenarios:

Scenario 1: an average hydrological year which is based on actual data from the past decade and an assumption of full utilization of the reservoir's water, as planned.

Scenario 2: an average hydrological year which is based on actual data from the past decade. However, the irrigation withdrawals (not the drinking water withdrawals) reach half of the full utilization planning.

Scenario 3: a dry-period scenario which is based on a hypothetical two-dry years in sequence and the assumption of full utilization of the reservoir's water. In this scenario, drinking water withdrawals triple, in comparison to Scenarios 1 and 2, while irrigation withdrawals are the same with scenario 2. This is a worst-case scenario, minimizing inflows for two years and maximizing water allocation needs.

Water allocation in all scenarios has been set based on the way the water managers would take their decisions, in coordination with the representative MAP members. The reservoir state is then calculated based on a hydrological model of the reservoir.

The above scenarios are then tested against decisions which would be taken, based on the assumption of a 100% skill CS, which would flawlessly predict the expected inflow in the reservoir. The result of the decisions on the reservoir state are then calculated based on a hydrological model of the reservoir. As noted in the previous, according to the water-management MAP members (OAK), these decisions are taken twice a year, once in March or April and then a reassessment takes place around September.

Figure 50: Thresholds for water stored volumes defining the “states of the world” for the Amari dam reservoir defined as: (a) water volume and (b) water level.

The payoff matrix

The payoff matrix states the gain the final user receives when a specific action is taken, and a given state of the world occurs. A payoff scale of ten units is defined, ranging from 0 when no payoff can be produced up to 10 for maximum payoff. The states of the reservoir are then evaluated based on this scale by the end-users. It is noted that the evaluation considers not only the availability of the water uses depending on the available stored water, but also the fact that more volume means cheaper energy production. The payoff evaluation by the end-users is shown in Figure 51.

The payoffs are linear functions inside the state, not a single value. They diminish linearly between two values in the state level. At Normal State, the payoff changes depending how near is the reservoir from the Maximum Normal Level. At this maximum level, payoff is 10. On the contrary, if the reservoir is at normal state as well, but about to reach the Energy production loss level (minimum level to remain in the state), the payoff is about 5. Then, as it enters the energy loss state, it fully diminishes to 0. A quick loss of payoff also happens in the Flood Control state, as the state moves towards the spillway level. Figure 51 shows how payoffs (on the right) change according to states of the world.

Table 16: Payoff matrices according to the end users.

State of the World (Water stored volume $\times 10^6 \text{m}^3$)	Payoff
0	0
2	0
4	0
6	0
8	5
10	6
12	8
14	10
16	10
18	10
20	3
22	0
22.5	0

Figure 51: Payoff distribution according to three different end users.

water abstraction gains payoff

An additional payoff is related to the gains of water abstraction which lie beyond the foreseen amounts. These are estimated, from a scale from -10 to 10. This type of payoff can take negative values. It is based on the assumption that when the planned abstraction (average conditions, maximum use of the reservoir) can be increased by 100% a maximum abstraction payoff is reached, i.e. 10 for each month. If the abstraction must be decreased, in comparison to plan, then it can reach up to -10 if the decrease is -100%. The payoff value to the additional amount of abstraction that is achieved based on the help of a 100% skill CS, is calculated as a portion of 10 which is equal to the ratio of extra abstraction each month by the maximum planned abstraction.

The sum of payoff is calculated for each month based on equal weights of state payoff (**Error! Reference source not found.**) and water abstraction gains payoff.

It is noted that the actions that can be taken by the user can influence the state of the reservoir and the associated payoffs for several following months.

Payoff values

The variation of the state of the world (water volume) is shown for **Scenario 1** in Figure 52a. The wet period, for which the tailored CS forecasts the available surface water for inflow in the reservoir, is marked with blue, transparent field. The decision periods are marked with dashed lines. The evolution of the state of the world under b.a.u. (business as usual) conditions is compared to the one based on decisions guided by a 100% correct CS. Figure 52b shows the monthly payoffs under both conditions as well as the water abstraction gains payoff.

As seen in Figure 52b, the CS based decision lead to a shift in the variation of the payoff, but do not produce

actual gain. The annual payoff values are 78.8 for the b.a.u. against a 73.5 for the CS based, i.e. a -7% change (decrease). This is mainly due to the fact that the new state of the world represents less water stored in the aquifer, for a larger period of the year. However, this is done because the forecast provided the opportunity for an increase of water abstractions during the main part of touristic period of the year (from May to September). An in that way, the water abstraction gains increased along with the opportunity for an increase in revenue. The annual water abstraction gains payoff sums up to 25.7.

Thus, **in the case of Scenario 1**, the total, annual payoff for the CS based state of the world is estimated to be 99.2 against a 78.8 for the b.a.u. case, that is a 20.4 gain and an 26% increase.

Figure 52: Scenario 1: (a) States of the world and (b) monthly payoff. (decision periods and forecasting period are marked on the graph).

For **Scenario 2**, the variation of the state of the world (water volume) is shown in Figure 53a. With the CS decision based timeline, the new state of the world lies more within the boundaries of Normal state in comparison to the b.a.u. case where the water stored volume fluctuated mainly in the Flood Control state. That translates to an increase in payoff, as is clearly shown in Figure 53b. The annual payoff values are 73.6 for the b.a.u. against a 94.9 for the CS based, i.e. a 29% change (21.3 units increase in payoff).

Further, the forecast provided the opportunity for a significant increase of water abstractions during the main part of touristic period of the year (from May to September). An in that way, the water abstraction gains increased along with the opportunity for an increase in revenue. The annual water abstraction gains payoff sums up to 59.5.

Thus, **in the case of Scenario 2**, the total, annual payoff for the CS based state of the world is estimated to be 154.4 against an 73.6 for the b.a.u. case, that is an 80.8 gain and an 110% increase.

Figure 53: Scenario 2: **(a)** States of the world and **(b)** monthly payoff. (decision periods and forecasting period are marked on the graph).

For **Scenario 3**, the variation of the state of the world (water volume) is shown in Figure 54a. With the CS decision-based timeline, the new state of the world lies more at the lower part of the Normal state in comparison to the b.a.u. case, where the water stored volume fluctuates also in the Flood Control state. That translates to a decrease in payoff, as is clearly shown in Figure 54b. The total payoff values (2-year) are 156.4 for the b.a.u. against a 146.9 for the CS based, i.e. a -6% change (a 9.5 units decrease in payoff).

However, the forecast provided the opportunity for a small increase of water abstractions during the main part of touristic period of the year (from May to September). In that way, the water abstraction gains increased along with the opportunity for an increase in revenue. The annual water abstraction gains payoff sums up to 15.5. It is noted however that the unfavorable two-years of low inflows (dry years) led also to the need for reducing the abstractions, hence the negative abstraction gains payoff during the second year.

Thus, **in the case of Scenario 3**, the total, 2-year payoff for the CS based state of the world is estimated to be 162.4 against a 156.4 for the b.a.u. case, that is a slim 6 units gain and a 4% increase.

Figure 54: Scenario 3: (a) States of the world and (b) monthly payoff. (decision periods and forecasting period are marked on the graph).

The total gains are summarized in Table 17. Scenario 1 is close to a full utilization of the reservoir reserves and therefore there is limited room for changes in water abstraction during the touristic period, when they are needed most. However, the CS demonstrated potential gains (under the assumption for a 100% skill of the CS). Scenario 2 provides better opportunities for maximizing the gain from the CS forecasts because the reservoir is not utilized in its full potential by the agricultural sector (irrigation). For Scenario 3, the unfavourable two-years of low inflows (dry years) led also to the need for reducing the abstractions, hence to negative abstraction gains payoff during the second year. However, even under these conditions there is still some room for gains, although based on a 100% skill of the CS. It is noted that the above calculations are based on 3 scenarios of the climatic conditions and utilization of the reservoir. These scenarios cover some favourable, average and unfavourable conditions but it is recognized that other conditions may lead to different results.

Table 17: Payoff gains under the three scenarios examined.

Scenario	State of the world gains Payoff	water abstraction gains payoff	Total payoff gains	
			gains	%
1	-5.3	25.7	20.4	26%
2	21.3	59.5	80.8	110%
3 (dry years)	-9.5	15.5	6	4%

Annex C – Quantify the benefits of the CS for the Tourism Sector - Crete Island LL

The socio-environmental model presented in (Biella et al. 2024) was adopted as a comprehensive evaluation framework designed to assess the value of Climate Services (CS) products across five interconnected sectors: tourism, water, transport, energy, and agriculture. This model effectively demonstrates how the implementation of CS products can improve informed and sector-specific decision-making processes in these domains. In the tourism sector, for example, it illustrates how CS products facilitate the formulation of targeted strategies aimed at enhancing tourist inflow. In the energy sector, the model emphasizes the contribution of CS products to increasing energy availability, thereby enabling better adaptation to variable energy demands. In the transport sector, the focus is on enhancing road usability through timely maintenance and the development of new infrastructure. Concerning water resources, the model advocates for the augmentation of water storage capabilities and the optimization of resource reallocation strategies. In agriculture, it demonstrates how CS products can enhance water allocation and promoting harvesting practices to support the increasing food requirements, hence moderating food costs. Collectively, the model elucidates the dynamic roles of CS products in promoting advancements across these varying sectors.

Moreover, the model incorporates future climate projections to address fluctuations in water availability, while human population growth is depicted as a gradual and consistent trend (Biella et al. 2024). A pivotal component of this model is the categorization of sectors into primary, secondary, and non-targeted levels within the ICISK framework of the co-design, co-development, and co-production of CS products. In this schema, the tourism sector was identified as the primary focus, while water, energy, and transport sectors were classified as secondary. The agricultural sector was designated as the 'non-targeted' sector, enabling an assessment of the multisectoral interconnectedness inherent within socio-environmental dynamics.

The simulation generated by the model produces sector-specific indices that gauge the effect of CS products across the selected sectors. Within the tourism sector, the Accommodation Cost Index (ACI) is employed as a proxy for the tourism sector. The Energy Scarcity Index (ESI) is utilized to measure the availability of energy resources. In the transport sector, the Road Inaccessibility Index (RII) is adopted to highlight challenges related to road access. For water resources, the Water Scarcity Index (WSI) quantifies the availability of this critical resource. In terms of agriculture, the model includes a Food Cost Index (FCI) that reflects the availability of food commodities. **The change of those sector-specific indices will be used as an indicator for quantifying the benefit of the service.**

Details on the model used, the underlying assumptions and the description of the outputs are given in Biella et al. (2024). It is noted here that a basic assumption made is that the sectors are operating under existing climate information (e.g. from national meteorological agencies, through sectoral climate change experiences, sectoral measures to respond to climate change etc). Climate Services (CS) products are therefore regarded as supplementary, tailored climate information that builds upon the conventional climate information currently available. As such, the climate information accessible to all sectors is uniformly characterized. This pre-existing climate information is assigned a value of 0.3. In contrast, the introduction of CS products results in an enhancement of the climate information value from the baseline of 0.3 to 0.7, reflecting an additional value of 0.4 attributed to the tailored nature of the CS products. The provision of these tailored CS products empowers targeted sectors with the precise information necessary for making informed decisions and formulating strategies that address their unique challenges and needs. As a result, the availability of CS products is simulated to significantly increase the capacity of these sectors to respond effectively to the pressures from climate change and population growth.

To quantify the value of co-produced CS products in the context of the island of Crete (LL), two scenarios were considered:

- **Scenario 1:** This simulation is based on a conventional sectoral approach to climate service development, wherein CS products are specifically designed for a single sector, with all other sectors treated as non-targeted (Reed et al. 2019).
- **Scenario 2:** This simulation operates under the premise of co-production of CS products as executed on the island of Crete. The stakeholders’ engagement in Crete followed a multi-stakeholder, multi-hazard approach, allowing for the categorization of sectors into primary and secondary classifications (Masih et al. 2022).

The differences in sectoral indices explained above (i.e. ACI, ESI, RII, WSI, and FCI), between the two scenarios were systematically analysed to evaluate the additional value of the CS products within the socio-environmental system encompassing the five sectors. More details about the model are available in (Biella et al. 2024).

Results

A comparative analysis of the two scenarios reveals that the co-production of CS products within a multi-stakeholder framework enhances the adaptive capacities of both primary and secondary sectors, with **improvements ranging from 24% to 472%** (Figure 55A). It is noted that, as anticipated, no measurable impact is observed on the adaptive capacity of the non-targeted sector.

The influence of CS product co-production on sectoral efficiencies exhibits substantial variability, particularly within the secondary sectors, as depicted in Figure 55B. This variability highlights the critical role of multi-sectoral approach in CS products development, as implemented on the island of Crete.

Additionally, Figure 55 underscores the limitations of conventional sectoral approaches (Scenario 1), as certain sectors already possess substantial adaptive capacities and efficiencies. **The adoption of a multi-sectoral approach in the development of CS products represents a transformative shift for all targeted sectors.**

Figure 55: Adaptive capacities of the selected sectors (A) and sectoral efficiencies for the selected sectors (B). These capacities are influenced by the availability and relevance of climate services (CS), the timeliness of access to CS products, the proximity to CS providers, the type of each sector, and the resources inherent to those sectors. The sectoral efficiencies are determined by the relationship between the adaptive capacities to meet resource demands within each sector against the maximum resource demand (Biella et al. 2024).

1. The results of model simulations regarding sectoral scarcity indices **demonstrate a positive effect of climate-sensitive (CS) products in Scenario 2** relative to Scenario 1 (see Figure 56).
2. Specifically, the sectoral scarcity indices for the primary and secondary sectors exhibited a reduction (*reduction means positive impact*) ranging from **0.04 to 0.14 units on a scale of 0 to 1, summing up 0.4 points change out of 4 points in the total of the 4 sectors which are taken into account**, attributable to the multi-sectoral approach implemented on the island of Crete.
3. The above indicate a **10% increase in the sum of indexes of total value** of the sectors addressed by the CS for tourism in Crete.
4. These findings emphasize the critical role of a multi-sectoral approach in maximizing the effectiveness of CS products. By integrating climate services across interconnected sectors, this approach enhances adaptation capacities, reinforcing the necessity of holistic climate resilience strategies.

Figure 56: Changes in sectoral scarcity indices.

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